

DISTENDER D 9.1 Case Studies

D9.1: Case Studies
WP 9, T 9.1

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This document reflects on the objectives of the task T9.1 Development and planning of the case studies:

- Identifying characteristics of the core case studies and matching patterns with the followers, and
- Setting up focus on trade-offs between adaptation and mitigation actions/strategies.

It is a compilation of available information regarding each case study to date. The introduction addresses the frame of the document explaining the backgrounds, limitations and its structure. It is followed by the representation of each case study description, which, after the general description in principle follows the sequence of WPs in the DISTENDER project and ends with the expectations of the case study from DISTENDER. Overall overview and relations to the followers are addressed in conclusions section. Additional and supportive materials are collected as annexes in the appendix.

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Technical references

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Table of contents

Technical references	3
Table of contents	4
List of Tables	7
List of Figures	9
Disclaimer	10
0 Introduction	11
0.1 Formal background and proceeding	11
0.1.1 Formal background.....	12
0.1.2 The process to produce the deliverable D9.1	12
0.1.3 Methodology for implementation of the co-creative iterative approach heading towards D9.1	13
0.2 Case study description structure, sources of information and limitations	14
0.2.1 Case study description structure and sources of information	14
0.2.2 Limitations	15
1 Case study 01: Austria (BMK)	17
1.1 General description	17
1.1.1 Geography and Economics	17
1.1.2 Quick facts.....	18
1.2 Participation and co-creation – backgrounds	18
1.2.1 Stakeholders.....	18
1.2.2 Quick facts.....	20
1.3 Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds	21
1.3.1 Available materials and knowledge.....	21
1.3.2 Quick facts.....	22
1.4 Models – backgrounds	23
1.4.1 Available materials and knowledge.....	23
1.4.2 Domains for simulation models.....	23
1.4.3 Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest.....	24
1.5 Strategies – backgrounds	26
1.5.1 Available materials and knowledge: Mitigation related	26
1.5.2 Available materials and knowledge: Adaptation related.....	27
1.5.3 Quick facts.....	28
1.6 Expectations of case study from DISTENDER	29
1.7 References	30
2 Case study 02: The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS).....	33
2.1 General description	33
2.1.1 Geography and Economics	33
2.1.2 Quick facts.....	33
2.2 Participation and co-creation – background	34
2.2.1 Stakeholders.....	34

2.2.2	Quick facts.....	36
2.3	Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds.....	37
2.3.1	Available materials and knowledge.....	37
2.3.2	Quick facts.....	39
2.4	Models – backgrounds.....	39
2.4.1	Available materials and knowledge.....	39
2.4.2	Domains for simulation models.....	40
2.4.3	Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest.....	42
2.4.4	Quick facts.....	42
2.5	Strategies – backgrounds.....	43
2.5.1	Available materials and knowledge: general.....	43
2.5.2	Available materials and knowledge: mitigation related.....	44
2.5.3	Available materials and knowledge: adaptation related.....	48
2.5.4	Quick facts.....	51
2.6	Expectations of case study from DISTENDER.....	51
2.7	References.....	51
3	Case study 03: Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) (EURAF)*description mostly for Dehesas.....	53
3.1	General description.....	53
3.1.1	Geography and Economics.....	53
3.1.2	Quick facts.....	55
3.2	Participation and co-creation – background.....	56
3.2.1	Stakeholders.....	56
3.2.2	Quick facts.....	57
3.3	Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds.....	58
3.3.1	Available materials and knowledge.....	58
3.3.2	Quick facts.....	60
3.4	Models – backgrounds.....	61
3.4.1	Available materials and knowledge.....	61
3.4.2	Domains for simulation models.....	61
3.4.3	Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest.....	62
3.4.4	Quick facts.....	63
3.5	Strategies – backgrounds.....	64
3.5.1	Available materials and knowledge: general.....	64
3.5.2	Available materials and knowledge: mitigation and adaptation related.....	66
3.5.3	Quick facts.....	68
3.6	Expectations of case study from DISTENDER.....	68
3.7	References.....	69
4	Case study 04: Guimarães (GUIMARAES).....	71
4.1	General description.....	71
4.1.1	Geography and Economics.....	71
4.1.2	Quick facts.....	71
4.2	Participation and co-creation – background.....	72
4.2.1	Stakeholders.....	72
4.2.2	Quick facts.....	73

4.3	Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds	74
4.3.1	Available materials and knowledge	74
4.3.2	Quick facts	74
4.4	Models – backgrounds	75
4.4.1	Available materials and knowledge	75
4.4.2	Domains for simulation models	75
4.4.3	Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest	77
4.4.4	Quick facts	78
4.5	Strategies – backgrounds	79
4.5.1	Available materials and knowledge: general	79
4.5.2	Available materials and knowledge: mitigation related	79
4.5.3	Available materials and knowledge: adaptation related	81
4.5.4	Quick facts	83
4.6	Expectations of case study from DISTENDER	84
4.7	References	85
5	Case study 05: The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMTo)	86
5.1	General description	86
5.1.1	Geography and Economics	86
5.1.2	Quick facts	88
5.2	Participation and co-creation – background	88
5.2.1	Stakeholders	88
5.2.2	Quick facts	89
5.3	Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds	90
5.3.1	Available materials and knowledge	90
5.3.2	Quick facts	93
5.4	Models – backgrounds	93
5.4.1	Available materials and knowledge	93
5.4.2	Domains for simulation models	95
5.4.3	Potential climate impact and sectors of interest	96
5.4.4	Quick facts	98
5.5	Strategies – backgrounds	99
5.5.1	Available materials and knowledge: general	99
5.5.2	Available materials and knowledge: mitigation related	101
5.5.3	Available materials and knowledge: adaptation related	101
5.5.4	Quick facts	102
5.6	Expectations of case study from DISTENDER	103
5.7	References	104
6	Conclusions	105
6.1	Discussion	105
6.1.1	Relations to the followers	106
6.2	Final remarks	107
Annexes		108
Annex I: Questionnaire: Case Study Description		108
Annex II: Models		117

Annex III: Short descriptions of the models regarding WP5	118
Annex IV: Supplementary material, provided by the case study partners.....	120
IV.1 Supplementary material of the CS 03 Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) (EURAF)	120
IV.2 Supplementary material of the CS 05 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMTTo).....	122

List of Tables

Table 1: Quick facts regarding general information	18
Table 2: Quick facts regarding case study readiness	20
Table 3: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness	20
Table 4: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it	20
Table 5: Quick facts regarding related documents available.....	22
Table 6. Characteristics relative to the models' domain of the Case Study (red box in Figure 5).	24
Table 7: Key characteristics of the Case Study	24
Table 8: Impact models, relevant for the Austrian case study.....	25
Table 9: Quick facts on relevant documents available	28
Table 10: Examples of climate mitigation and adaptation selected by the case study.....	29
Table 11: Quick facts regarding general information	34
Table 12: Quick facts regarding case study readiness	36
Table 13: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness	36
Table 14: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it	37
Table 15: Quick facts regarding related documents available.....	39
Table 16. Characteristics relative to the larger model domain of the Case Study (black box in Figure 7).	41
Table 17. Characteristics relative to the domain level 1 of the Case Study (red box in Figure 7).	41
Table 18. Characteristics relative to the domain level 2 of the Case Study (green box in Figure 7).	41
Table 19: Key characteristics of the Case Study	42
Table 20: Impact models, relevant for the Case Study	43
Table 21: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation	44
Table 22: Current trends and action taken regarding climate adaptation.....	48
Table 23: Quick facts on relevant documents available	51
Table 24: Quick facts regarding general information. Please note that the information contained in this Table is mainly for the Spanish domain of the Case Study (Extremadura) since partners reported problems to get the information for the Portuguese part.....	55
Table 25: Quick facts regarding case study readiness	57
Table 26: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness	57
Table 27: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it	58
Table 28: Quick facts on relevant documents available.....	60

Table 29. Characteristics relative to the larger model domain of the Case Study (black box in Figure 8).	62
Table 30. Characteristics relative to the model domain level 1 of the Case Study (red box in Figure 8).	62
Table 31: Key characteristics of the Case Study	62
Table 32: Impact models, relevant for the Dehesas and montados Case Study.....	63
Table 33: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation and adaptation ...	67
Table 34: Quick facts on relevant documents available	68
Table 35: Quick facts regarding general information	71
Table 36: Quick facts regarding case study readiness	73
Table 37: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness	73
Table 38: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it	73
Table 39: Quick facts on relevant documents available	74
Table 40. Characteristics relative to the larger domain of the Case Study (red box in Figure 9).	76
Table 41. Characteristics relative to the domain level 2 of the Case Study (green box in Figure 9).	76
Table 42. Characteristics relative to the domain level 3 of the Case Study (blue box in Figure 9).	76
Table 43: Key characteristics of the Case Study	77
Table 44: Impact models, relevant for the Guimarães Case Study.....	78
Table 45: Current trends and actions taken regarding climate mitigation	79
Table 46: Current trends and action taken regarding climate adaptation.....	82
Table 47: Quick facts on relevant documents available	84
Table 48: Quick facts regarding general information	88
Table 49: Quick facts regarding case study readiness	89
Table 50: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness	90
Table 51: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it	90
Table 52: Quick facts on relevant documents available.....	93
Table 53. Characteristics relative to the larger model domain of the Case Study (black box in Figure 11).	95
Table 54. Characteristics relative to the model domain level 1 of the Case Study (red box in Figure x11.....	96
Table 55. Characteristics relative to the domain level 2 of the Case Study (blue box in Figure 11).	96
Table 56: Key characteristics of the Case Study	96
Table 57: Impact models, relevant for the CMT0 case study.....	98
Table 58: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation	101
Table 59: Current trends and action taken regarding climate adaptation.....	102
Table 60: Quick facts on relevant documents available	102
Table 61: Quick facts regarding case study scale-related characteristics.....	105
Table 62: Quick facts regarding case study interest for the climate impacts with references to the proposed models	106
Table 63: Matching table about the quick facts regarding case studies' related characteristics and interests of the followers	107
Table 64: Main parameters of Turin district heating system.....	131

List of Figures

Figure 1 Domains (boxes) covering the administrative boundaries of the Case Studies of DISTENDER (CS 01 Austria; CS 02 the NE of the Netherlands; CS 03 Dehesa and Montado; CS 04 Guimarães; CS 05 Metropolitan City of Turin). The specific meaning of each color box is explained later in the document	11
Figure 2 Illustration of the T9.1 Development and planning of the Case Studies - tasks, deliverables, timeframe (Source: UIRS, Kick off meeting, Madrid, 2022)	11
Figure 3 Illustration emphasizing the focus on T9.1.1 Definitions of the case studies. Note that A/M refers to adaptation and mitigation strategies (Source: UIRS, Kick off meeting, Madrid, 2022)	12
Figure 4 Working steps and timeline for T9.1.1 Definitions of the case studies (Source: UIRS, Kick off meeting, Madrid, 2022)	13
Figure 5 Models' domain for the Case Study (red box; see above text and Table 6 for details)	23
Figure 6: Water authorities map (left) and provinces maps (right) (Source: both maps provided by HUAS)	35
Figure 7 Model domains for the Case Study (black, red and green boxes; see above text and Tables 16-18 for details)	41
Figure 8 Model domains for the Case Study (black and red boxes; see text above and Tables 29 and 30 for details)	62
Figure 9 Model domains for the Case Study (red, green and blue boxes; see above text and Tables 40-42 for details)	76
Figure 10 Structure of the stakeholders recognised by the case study CMT0 (source: Smart Continent, ppt presentation of WP2, UIRS, 2022)	89
Figure 11 Model domains for the Case Study (black, red and blue boxes; see above text and Tables 53-55 for details)	95
Figure 12 Territory and population	123
Figure 13 Graphical representation on some territorial characteristics	123
Figure 14 Land consumption and population	125
Figure 15 Soil consumed by Homogeneous Zone & Soil consumed by Homogeneous Zone	126
Figure 16 Ecological functionality of land (ecological fragmentation and fragility)	127
Figure 17 Municipalities that provided areas suitable to requalification actions (CIRCA) + Areas identified for reforestation plan	127
Figure 18 Expansion of the TLR planned	129
Figure 19 Expansion planned with the implementation of the TORINO NORD EST project	130

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0 Introduction

0.1 Formal background and proceeding

WP9 defines the ecosystem of each case study upon which the other WPs will be applied. The D9.1 is a product of the first task (T9.1) of the WP9, which according to the project management plan is divided into two related subtasks T9.1.1 Definitions of the case studies (see locations of the different case studies in Figure 1) and T9.1.2. Participation to co-develop socio-economic scenarios (see Figure 2).

Figure 1 Domains (boxes) covering the administrative boundaries of the Case Studies of DISTENDER (CS 01 Austria; CS 02 the NE of the Netherlands; CS 03 Dehesa and Montado; CS 04 Guimarães; CS 05 Metropolitan City of Turin). The specific meaning of each color box is explained later in the document

Figure 2 Illustration of the T9.1 Development and planning of the Case Studies - tasks, deliverables, timeframe (Source: UIRS, Kick off meeting, Madrid, 2022)

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0.1.1 Formal background

The main aim of deliverable D9.1 is to provide a full description of the core case studies and their relationships with followers. This is elaborated with information extracted from task 9.1.1. In particular, on the one hand, through meetings with case study representatives to identify their areas of interest, main issues raised regarding climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies and relevant socio-economic insights. On the other hand, through discussions with partners covering subjects of socio-economic scenarios (WP3), numerical models (WP4, WP5, WP7) and strategies building (WP6), to outline focusses on the main climate risks, possible adaptation and mitigation strategies or relevant domains of simulations considering the predefined sectors such as water, energy, agriculture or health (see Figure 2).

Figure 3 Illustration emphasizing the focus on T9.1.1 Definitions of the case studies. Note that A/M refers to adaptation and mitigation strategies (Source: UIRS, Kick off meeting, Madrid, 2022)

0.1.2 The process to produce the deliverable D9.1

The working steps and the timeline to achieve the deliverable D9.1 was presented at the project kick of meeting and was followed using the co-creative iterative approach between case studies and other project partners as shown on Figure 3. The process was maintained by the T9.1 leader (UIRS) with support of WP9 leader (KVC).

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Figure 4 Working steps and timeline for T9.1.1 Definitions of the case studies (Source: UIRS, Kick off meeting, Madrid, 2022)

0.1.3 Methodology for implementation of the co-creative iterative approach heading towards D9.1

Early activities represented desk work encompassing activities such as studying the available materials about case studies which were available at the DISTENDER SharePoint repository provided at the meeting on June 14th 2022, and analyze them via the lens of DISTENDER focus. Based on that the UIRS team prepared a first draft of a questionnaire called Case Study Description (see Annex I) and circulated it in the partnership (18. 07. 2022). This included a blank template with instructions regarding how to fill in the template, as well as an already filled in example representing the Case Study 02: The NE of the Netherlands. This questionnaire reflects on case studies related work packages and is divided into six sections: General; Participation and co-creation backgrounds (relation to WP2); Socio-economic scenarios backgrounds (relation to WP3); Models backgrounds (relation to WP4, WP5, WP7); Strategies backgrounds (relation to WP6), and Case studies' expectations from DISTENDER (relation to WP9). All partners were invited to comment on the content and structure. More specifically, case study representatives were asked to fill in the information available to them, and work package leaders and staff were invited to propose additional topics of relevance for their tasks. By delivering this questionnaire the final stage of extracting focused information (see Figure 3) was approached.

Further, two meetings were held with the case study representatives organized in a joint effort of WP2 (stakeholders related issues) and WP9 (matters addressed in the questionnaire Case Study Description) on July 27th 2022 and July 28th 2022 to discuss the questionnaire items and any issues they may have with providing the required information, so the focus on the issues and the adjustments and priorities would be easily recognized and outlined.

Case study representatives sent back the filled-in questionnaire templates within the first week of September 2022, which corresponds to the stage of validation of the drafts of case study definitions and opens the last stage of the co-creation process, where mostly bilateral meetings between the case studies and the UIRS team were held. UIRS team compiled the information in a report (an early version of the D9.1) which was made available to all project

partners on the DISTENDER SharePoint. In order to advance the dialogue between the modelers and case study representatives, two on-line meetings were organized by WP9 in cooperation between WPs 5 and 7 on October 12th 2022 and October 19th 2022, respectively. They yielded additional information to complement case study descriptions and were denoted as the starting point for exchange, also on one-to-one basis, between modelers and case study partners.

After all these iterations the final shape was achieved after internal revision, when two internal reviewers provided insights and suggestions for improvements.

0.2 Case study description structure, sources of information and limitations

Although following the presented methodology equally with each case study, the collected quantity and quality of information per case study differ. This is partly due to different nature of the case studies and their interests and focuses on the field of climate adaptation and mitigation as well as their expectations from the DISTENDER, respectively. In this respect, an effort has been done to make the document coherent within and across the different case studies.

0.2.1 Case study description structure and sources of information

This deliverable is designed to provide a base for the working process with case studies across all case studies-related work packages. The questionnaire called Case study description (see Annex I) was used as a background for the structure of this deliverable (D 9.1). Thus, each case study is described against the following structure: General description, Participation and co-creation – backgrounds, Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds, Models – backgrounds, Strategies – backgrounds, and Expectations of case study from DISTENDER. The sources of information were case studies, their representatives and their internal or external sources. Although the provided materials vary, depending on the case study, an effort to present a coherent content across the case studies in all the addressed sections, has been done.

The *section General description* refers to the introduction into getting to know the case study and gives information about the geographical area and its characteristics (e.g., morphology, climate, population) and briefly outlining also the economic activities significant for the case study.

The *section Participation and co-creation - backgrounds* is targeting the experiences of the case studies in work with various stakeholders as well as in the knowledge needed for co-creation activities to inform WP2 about the state-of-the-art of each case study regarding the supportive activities addressed in WP2 Co-creation and Stakeholders engagement. Information gathered provide a picture of case study readiness for participatory co-creation and their understanding of such processes and experiences with them and is at the same

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time also a starting point for the second sub-task of the T9.1 the Participation to co-develop socio-economic scenarios (T9.1.2) and for further shaping of activities in WP3 and WP6.

The *section Socio-economic scenarios - backgrounds* is based on observations known to case studies that may inform WP3 Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios. It indicates or reflects on the documents that can inform about current/future case study development: from relevant spatial planning documentation, action plans, expert studies or any other documents that can well inform the current state in socio-spatial-economic situation and/or can be a fruitful input for future local socio-economic scenarios. Information gathered shows the case studies' reflection on the socio-economic scenarios often reflects this topic via spatial development agendas, plans and strategies, which may include climate change adaptation and mitigation, especially as social aspects such as economic development and population growth or migrations are parts of such spatial development documents. Targeted socio-economic data and related issues available in expert studies will be addressed in further focused development of WP3.

The *section Models - backgrounds* collects information known to the case studies on potential climate hazards, impacts or negative influences and by this prepare the insights for the impact models which are central to WP5 Risk and Vulnerability Assessment addressing health (GHG emissions, urban heat, air quality), water, energy and agriculture. In this section also the overall model domains are presented for each case study which cover the areas of simulation for all the mentioned models in each case study.

The *section Strategies - backgrounds* serves as a platform of available information to date in each case study that can as much as possible provide current trends and actions taken regarding climate mitigation and adaptation. The latter can serve as input for activities of WP6 Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies. The *section Expectations* gives the case studies an opportunity to express their expectations from the DISTENDER and serves as a check-point field of what can be addressed as the subject of DISTENDER and what are challenges that shall be addressed outside the project.

0.2.2 Limitations

This document is a qualitative description of the case studies and provides a frame for understanding of characteristics, knowledge available and potentials of the case studies in DISTENDER. The case studies are very diverse in many aspects. They differentiate not only in terms of size and governance level, having representatives of national (CS 01 Austria), regional (CS 02 The NE of the Netherlands, CS 03 Dehesa and montados and CS05 Metropolitan city of Turin), and municipal (CS 04 Guimaraes), but most of all regarding their expectations from the project which is also connected to recognitions of sectors addressed.

Two of the regional case studies, the CS 02 (The NE of the Netherlands) and the CS 03 (Dehesa and Montado) fit the most to the DISTENDER concept of models, scenarios and strategies, as they are quite sector-oriented, and have preferences for specific models. CS 04 (Guimaraes) is typical urban area case interested in the models addressing health issues, but also in all the other models, so is the CS 05 (Metropolitan city of Turin), which is also the

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most complex case occupying from many aspects very heterogeneous territory of more than 25x size of CS 04 (Guimarães). It includes several densely developed urban areas as well as considerable share of rural areas and wilderness, therefore is also highly interested in all DISTENDER models. The CS 01 Austria is also strongly sector-oriented but is not well framed yet towards the DISTENDER aims as being a national level, which also represents a complex situation. Thus, this document collects relational information and supportive materials for an in-depth development of the topics in each separate WP, where greater attention will be paid to the concrete focus of each WP.

Therefore, some sources provided by the case studies as being relevant for the proposed sections of the document may appear in more than one section as the sources provide relevant information for more than one aspect (e.g., socio-economic scenarios, strategies) of the DISTENDER. This may especially be present in the case studies of Guimaraes and Metropolitan city of Turin as their main covering documents may refer to municipality/metropolitan area spatial development, which includes also socio-economic aspects but also climate adaptation and mitigation measures that then influence socio-economic challenges and changes. Therefore, often socio-economic issues and aspects are not explicitly addressed. They shall be further discussed within the WP3, following also the sources provided in D9.1.

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1 Case study 01: Austria (BMK)

1.1 General description

The case study Austria is the only case study of the national level. Austria is a federal republic with nine provinces, where competence for climate action can lie either at federal or provincial level, depending on the area. The new government formed a new Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology. Responsibility for spatial planning, building codes, land use and infrastructure permit procedures at provincial level. Austria's government has set itself the goal of being climate neutral by the year 2040. Fighting the climate crisis and reaching net zero emissions by 2040 in the transport sector is particularly challenging, as greenhouse gas emissions have risen by more than 70% since 1990 (except in the year 2020 due to the Covid Crisis). The entire transport sector has to undergo a socio-technological upheaval. The case study main interest is in infrastructure sector and related socio-economic and climate change related impacts.

1.1.1 Geography and Economics

As to geography, Austria is a land-locked country covering part of the eastern Alps and the Danube region (see area of interest in Figure 5). Its total surface area accounts to 83,858 km² with a share of 37.5% settlement area. Austria's population reached 8.9 million inhabitants in 2020 and nearly a third of all Austrians (2.6 million) live within the metropolitan area of Vienna [1].

There are three climatic zones in Austria:

- Alpine Climate characteristics for the Central Alpine region and is significant for high precipitation, short summers, long winters.
- Continental Pannonian Climate characteristics for the eastern part of the country, with significant for hot summers with low overall humidity levels but frequent rain showers and mildly cold snowy winters, e.g., mean temperature for July is usually above 19°C, annual rainfall often less than 800 mm.
- Transitional central European Climate characteristics for the rest of the country and is significant for a wet and temperate climate [2].

Regarding economy, Austria's GDP reached \$428.9 billion, and its per capita GDP was \$48,105 in 2020. In this context, for the same year, the Austrian exports contributed approximately 52% to GDP. The economy of Austria is dominated by the industry, with a highly developed market economy, skilled labour force, and a very high standard of living for its population. Many of Austria's industrial jobs are in the mechanical, steel, chemical, electrical and electronics industries [3]. Service jobs involve about 74% of the labour forces, followed by industry jobs, at 25.3%. Agricultural employment only represents about 0.7% of the labour force.

As the focus of this case study is transport sector, special attention is also paid to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In the context of climate change, information on GHG

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emissions, which are also relevant for one of the health-related models, were selected as valuable and are summarised as follows. The transport sector accounts for 21.6 million tonnes of GHG which is a third of Austria's overall emissions. Compared with 1990, CO₂ emissions from transport have risen by 75%. Emissions from freight transport have more than doubled since 1990, with truck traffic alone already causing more emissions than the entire building sector.

1.1.2 Quick facts

Table 1 summarises general, relevant information about the Austrian case study, including the area of interest, referring to the case study's administrative area or boundaries; the population within the area, the main topographic features, the climate zones that it includes, and main economic activity.

Table 1: Quick facts regarding general information

subject	information
Area of interest (size)	83,858 km ²
Population in area of interest	8.9 million inhabitants (2020)
Topography of area of interest	Parts of the eastern Alps and the Danube region
Climate zone	Continental Pannonian climate Alpine climate Central European climate
Economy	Industry

1.2 Participation and co-creation – backgrounds

This section addresses two aspects regarding stakeholders. Firstly, it refers to the stakeholders recognised by the case study as relevant. In this particular case, mostly state's owned infrastructure companies are presented. Secondly, responses of the case study on the questionnaire (see Annex I) are elaborated referring to case study familiarity to participatory approaches and its readiness for participation.

1.2.1 Stakeholders

The main stakeholders recognised by the case study are: the Austrian Federal Railways (ÖBB) and the Austrian publicly owned corporation which plans, finances, builds, maintains and collects tolls for the Austrian highways (ASFINAG).

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- ÖBB [4] (Österreichische Bundesbahnen) Austrian Federal Railways, owned by the BMK, is presently the largest railroad company in Austria. Within the “ÖBB Rahmenplan”, the BMK provides a planning document of contractually agreed subsidies within a respective 6-year period. This is a compilation of planned projects and their investment sums, as well as the expenses for the maintenance of the rail network. Throughout Austria, ÖBB manages a rail network with a length of around 4,900 km and more than 16,000 protective structures that serve to protect these against natural hazards. In this respect strategy "Natural Hazard Management", drawn up in 2014, follows the phases of the risk cycle of potential damage: prevention, immediate response and restoration.
- ASFINAG [5] Autobahnen- und Schnellstraßen-Finanzierungs-Aktiengesellschaft, owned by the BMK, plans, finances, builds, maintains and collects tolls for the Austrian autobahns. The company operates a route network 2,249 km long with 379 junctions, 166 tunnels with 405.4 km of tubes and 5,818 bridges. ASFINAG currently represents the second biggest infrastructure provider in Austria. In 2014, ASFINAG developed a strategy for natural hazard management. This had the objective to create natural hazard warning maps, as a first step. The maps are currently already available for 85% of Austria's total surface area.

Both ÖBB and ASFINAG, as the biggest infrastructure provider have a crucial role for the case study. The stakeholders which belong to the highest interest and influence groups are, beside ÖBB and ASFINAG, Umweltbundesamt [6], SCHIG [7] and Statistik Austria [8]. The rest of the road transport network is administrated and maintained by the federal government (“Bund”), the nine provinces (“Länder”) as well as municipalities (“Gemeinden”).

Insights from WP2 (T2.1 Progress report)

At this stage, 33 stakeholders external to DISTENDER have been identified by BMK. Of these, 9% are end-users, 42% data providers and 18% providers of expertise assistance. They are of great relevance for activities that will take place in DISTENDER WP3 (Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios), WP4 (Downscaling climate scenarios), WP5 (Risk & Vulnerability assessment), WP6 (Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies), 7 (Cost-benefits evaluation and impacts) and WP8 (Decision Support System).

Insights from WP3 (initial interviews WP3 (WUR) - Case studies)

At the early stage of the WP3 discussion some key stakeholders identified by the BMK were:

- Environmental agency – because with its work related to climate scenarios.
- Energy sector: Chamber of businesses, specifically the business branch in the transport sector – because being very influential on the governance level, even if not a government actor.
- Possibly other related ministries.

1.2.2 Quick facts

Tables 2-4 display general information about the readiness of the Austrian Case Study in terms of stakeholder knowledge, co-creation and participation, as asked in the questionnaire (Annex I).

Table 2: Quick facts regarding case study readiness

Case study readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you have experiences with stakeholders' participation?			X
Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)?		X	
Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users?		X	
Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies?		X	
Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder's side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of?	X		

Table 3: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness

Stakeholder readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you know your stakeholder's readiness for participation?			X
Is it easy for the stakeholder to take action on an issue?			X
Do you know your stakeholder knowledge/expertise?			X

Table 4: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it

Case study involvement	Active participant	Preparation support	Organise/implement
workshop		X	

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1.3 Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds

This section elaborates on the key concept of WP3 following the socio-economic scenarios as Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP). It shows only a very early stage of this concept application towards the case studies, as it has just started its run within the WP3.

1.3.1 Available materials and knowledge

ÖROK and ÖREK

The Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning (ÖROK) [10] is a federal, state and local authority that coordinates nationwide spatial planning. The ÖROK develops and publishes the Austrian Spatial Development Concept (ÖREK). In addition, ÖROK carries out studies and projects on spatial development policy and forms an important interface to European regional and spatial development policy.

ÖREK_2030 [11] addresses informed readers and decision-makers in the field of (spatial) planning, as well as the relevant departments in Austria's provinces (Länder) and at ministries, regional and local planning bodies, stakeholders, companies and NGOs. Spatial planning and spatial development are defined as the joint responsibility of the federal government, the nine federal states (Länder), the cities, and the municipalities. The ÖROK and ÖREK are an expression of this understanding of shared responsibility. Climate change and its impacts are the key topics of the ÖREK 2030. Achieving decarbonisation in all areas of our lives is the key challenge, especially changing our mobility habits.

ÖROK is of interest here as it is the organisation established jointly by its members for the purpose of coordinating spatial development and spatial planning activities in Austria. These members are the federal government, the provinces (Länder), the cities, and the municipalities as well as the economic and social partners, therefore it is listed in the section referring to socio-economic scenarios as it may be a very relevant source for further work, especially in WP3.

As this case study is particularly interested in transportation sector, relevant insights addressing GHG emissions via economy sectors are also of interest here: The calculations of the nowcast report for 2021 showed that around 77.1 million tonnes of greenhouse gases (GHG) were emitted in Austria [12]. The plants covered by the EU emission trading system (EU ETS) [13] have emitted GHG equivalent to almost 30 million tons of CO₂. Due to the company Voest-Alpine, the most CO₂-intensive industry in the Austrian climate balance is the iron and steel industry with 12.7 million tons of CO₂, well ahead of energy and heat generation (5.8 million tons). The production of building materials - in particular cement, bricks and glass - accounts for 4.6 million tons annually. They are followed by refineries (i.e., Austrian Mineral Oil Administration Stock Company (OMV)) with 2.7 million tons, ahead of airlines with 1.6 million tons and the paper and pulp industry with 1.5 million tons. The chemical industry emits 1.1 million tons of CO₂ [14].

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In comparison to transport sector GHG emissions, the other emissions sector, covering buildings and tertiary industry, emissions reduced slightly since 2006.

GHG projections (WEM, WAM and transition scenarios)

Current situation and projection "with existing measures" (WEM) (first draft by September 2022) is the baseline-scenario, which reflects the status of the measures implemented. It serves as a starting point for implementing existing legal measures and instruments and for making a quantitative assessment of their impact.

Impact Assessment of planned policies and measures "with additional measures" (WAM) (first draft by February 2023) depicts selected measures compared to baseline scenario (WEM). Examples of measures are "CO₂ pricing in the non-ETS" (Emissions Trading Systems) and two variants of redistribution, "out of oil for households" and an analysis of the proposed regulation for emission-free vehicles in the fit for 55 package (i.e., the EU's target of reducing net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030) for Austrian cars ("EU-VOV"). The latter is also compared with the analysis of measures for the Renewable Energy Sources Expansion Act (EAG).

Transition scenario (first draft by February 2023): It depicts net zero emissions in 2040 in Austria. For 2030, the targets of 100% electricity generation from renewable sources (balance) and targets for Austria from the fit for 55 package are illustrated. Other goals such as the use of resources and land or the preservation of biodiversity are qualitatively taken into account.

In Austria, 5,768 km² had been sealed by 2020. This corresponds approximately to 7% of the state area and 18% of the permanent settlement area. The annual loss of productive soil varied between about 38 km² and 104 km² in the period 2001-2020 [15].

Also, the repository of natural hazards maps (link available in Table 5) is mentioned here as a valuable cross-checking source when framing or developing socio-economic scenarios. Maps regarding floods/wild streams, avalanches, erosion and rockfall, as well as historical events can be found at: maps.naturgefahren.at. In the various maps, the user can navigate directly to a specific area by entering the address and query the individual affectedness.

1.3.2 Quick facts

Table 5: Quick facts regarding related documents available

Document	Availability
Austrian Spatial Development Concept ÖREK 2030 in brief [11]	Online: https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/OEREK_2030-in_brief.pdf
EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) [13]	Online: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets_en
Natural hazards maps [32]	Online:

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	https://www.naturgefahren.at/karten/detailkarten.html
Statistics Austria [8]	Online: https://www.statistik.at/en

1.4 Models – backgrounds

This section addresses climate change impacts as recognised by the case study and provide the domains for models that are the subject of the DISTENDER project. In principle four models are addressed HEALTH (including urban heat, air quality, health impacts), WATER, AFLOU (including agriculture, forestry, other land uses) and ENERGY.

1.4.1 Available materials and knowledge

Austria is particularly affected by climate change due to its location within the Alpine region. The temperature in Austria has risen by about 2°C since 1880, and is thus considerably above the global temperature increase of about 1.2°C. The effects are already evident, among other things in the increase of flood risk, shrinking of glaciers, longer vegetation periods and the increase in temperature extremes [16].

In the recent years several research projects have been conducted on the impacts of climate change in Austria as well as on adaptation. The most comprehensive study on climate change impacts (including an economic evaluation) is the COIN-study (“Costs of Inaction”) [17], followed by the projects PACINAS and PATCHES [18] on adaptation.

1.4.2 Domains for simulation models

Here we present the model domain of the Case Study Austria. As observed in Figure 5, there is a unique simulation domain, since this Case Study expands over a national scale. Therefore, all models should provide results within this area. The boundaries and spatial resolution are specified in Table 6.

Figure 5 Models' domain for the Case Study (red box; see above text and Table 6 for details)

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Table 6. Characteristics relative to the models' domain of the Case Study (red box in Figure 5).

Domain characteristics	
Northern boundary	49.591802
Southern boundary	46.019764
Western boundary	9.271000
Eastern boundary	17.289830
Spatial resolution (°)	0.09
Approximate extent (km)	600 x 400

1.4.3 Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest

Tables 7 and 8 display potential climate impacts and impact models as recognised by the case study of Austria. Table 8 shows in detail sectors and models, as suggested by DISTENDER project, and their relation to the interests of the Case Study.

Table 7: Key characteristics of the Case Study

Related starting point	
Potential climate impact	Air pollution GHG emissions
Sectors of interest	Transport Energy Water Health Agriculture could be if interest
Biophysical and/or economic impacts of the climate hazards of interest to the CS	ENERGY: analyse and support the energy baseline for the mobility sector and energy projections for the future based on two scenarios: 1. Business as usual; 2. Action implementations towards country targets (zero emissions in 2040) AFOLU (agriculture, forestry, other land uses): impacts of land use change and land use competition WATER: creation and securing of flood retention and flood drainage areas

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HEALTH: impact of the heat production from road network; impact of the construction of new roads on temperature and air quality; impact of changing speed limits on health and air quality

Table 8: Impact models, relevant for the Austrian case study

SECTORS AND MODELS ADOPTED	Sub-sectors dealt with	CS interest in the sector	Explanation
HEALTH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SUEWS model</u> simulates radiation, energy and water balances • <u>ENVI-met</u> assesses the efficiency of mitigation actions • <u>URBAIR model</u> 	Urban heat	/	Interest in gaining knowledge regarding possible changes in traffic (e.g., speed limits) and road network (e.g., construction of new roads)
	Air quality	YES	
	Health impacts	YES	
ENERGY		YES	Interest in climate-neutral mobility e.g., efficient public transport, increased use of bicycles, energy demand of transport sector in different scenarios, costs of renewable energy only in the transport sector, vulnerability of the energy sector
AFOLU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>YieldSAFE model</u> predicts plant growth, production 	Agriculture	(YES)	This sector is of indirect interest mainly regarding to CO ₂ reduction initiatives, land competition, windmills or solar panels on agricultural fields, economic impact of different agricultural crops (land use change), extensive agriculture
	Forestry		
	Other land use		
WATER <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SWAT model</u> calculates relevant water fluxes at the land surface, in the soil, groundwater and river • <u>Economic assessment</u> evaluates the value of 	Flooding	YES	Interested in hydropower
	Drought	/	

Note: / indicates that the case study did not recognise the interest in the sector/model, whereas () indicates a partial interest.

1.5 Strategies – backgrounds

In this section are presented relevant regulations, action plans for mitigation and strategies on adaptation as selected by the case study, as well as selected facts that the case study assess may be important in relation to WP6 referring to integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies.

1.5.1 Available materials and knowledge: Mitigation related

The main mitigation related policies in the Case Study are listed below:

NECP National energy and climate plan

To meet the EU's energy and climate targets for 2030, EU countries need to establish a 10-year integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) [19] for the period from 2021 to 2030. The national plans outline how the EU countries intend to address energy efficiency, renewables, GHG emissions reductions, interconnections and, research and innovation. The NECP from 2019 can be found [here](#) [20].

The governance regulation [21] states that the plan has to be updated by 2023/2024 (Chapter 2, Article 14). The updated NECP should express a higher level of ambition than in the integrated national energy and climate plan submitted in 2019. The following significant developments are to be considered:

- The government program (2020-2024) sets out the climate neutrality goal for Austria by 2040. Recently, (September 2022), this goal has no legal basis. The coalition has been negotiating the law since 2020.
- The creation of Austria's mobility master plan 2030 [22] on how to reach climate neutrality in 2040 in the transport sector was anchored in the government program (2020-2024). It describes clear transformation pathways by showing ways to avoid, shift and improve traffic and to increase significantly the share of the environmental network of walking and cycling, public transport and shared mobility. In addition to the overarching carbon-neutrality target, a series of basic indicators (e.g., traffic performance, modal split, transport network development) will be used to assess the climate targets in the transport sector. The Austrian climate agency does the collection and evaluation of the necessary data material.
- The 'fit for 55' package is designed to realise the European Climate Law objectives: climate neutrality by 2050 and a 55% reduction of net GHG emissions by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, which also result in new EU climate and energy targets for Austria. According to the new proposed effort sharing regulation, Austria has to reduce its GHG-emissions by 48% compared to 2005.
- Reassessment of the security of energy supply due to the Ukraine war.

- Reassessment from the perspective of affordability/energy poverty and well-being ability against the background of the current situation.

In Austria, 5,768 km² had been sealed by 2020. This corresponds, approximately, to 7% of the state area and 18% of the permanent settlement area. The annual loss of productive soil varied between about 38 km² and 104 km² in the period 2001-2020 [15].

1.5.2 Available materials and knowledge: Adaptation related

The main adaptation-related policies in the Case Study are listed below:

EU's Strategy on adaptation to climate change

Adaptation preparedness scoreboard: Country fiche for Austria [24] is EC document. It assesses the Member States' adaptation policy as of June 2018, including the content of NASs and NAPs, as explained in the text below:

Austrian Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change [23] [24]

In Austria, a National Adaptation Strategy (NAS) was adopted in 2012. The Austrian NAS consists of two parts: a Strategic Framework (or "Context") and an Action Plan (NAP). The aim of the Austrian NAS is to avoid the adverse effects of climate change on the environment, society, and the economy and to fully utilise any opportunities that may arise. The NAS aims to create a national framework to ensure coordination and harmonisation of the various climate adaptation activities in all areas.

In August 2017, a revised version of the NAS was adopted by the Austrian Council of Ministers, which was subsequently also approved by the Conference of the Governor's of the Bundesländer (NUTS II) in November 2017. This new version aims to update and further develop the NAS, while preserving its overall structure. In Austria, the Bundesländer have legislative and executive powers (e.g., with regard to spatial planning, nature protection, transport), which are relevant to climate adaptation. The Bundesländer are also responsible for the administration, implementation and enforcement of certain federal laws at lower levels of government. Representatives from all Bundesländer were actively involved in the development of the NAS and NAP [24].

Currently, the BMK is working on a revised NAS, to publish it in 2023.

ASFINAG strategy for natural hazard management

The maps are currently already available for 85% of Austria's total surface area. The maps contain points and areas that are affected by the natural hazard processes of floods, torrents/landslides, rockfalls, landslides and avalanches. Possible damage to the

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infrastructure or personal injury is derived by means of further risk analyses, which serve as the basis for the development of measures, such as the construction of protective structures.

1.5.3 Quick facts

Table 9: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
Austrian strategy for adaptation to climate change	Pdf online: Austrian strategy for adaptation to climate change – Part 1: Context (PDF, 3 MB)
Austrian strategy for adaptation to climate change	Pdf online: Austrian strategy for adaptation to climate change – Part 2: Action Plan (PDF, 2 MB)
Adaptation preparedness scoreboard: Country fiche for Austria	Pdf online: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/system/files/2018-11/country_fiche_at_en.pdf [20]
Additional relevant material serving as a starting point for impacts and adaptation:	Steininger, K.W., König, M., Bednar-Friedl, B., Kranzl, L., Loibl, W., Prettenthaler, F. (Eds.), 2015. Economic Evaluation of Climate Change Impacts. Development of a Cross-Sectoral Framework and Results for Austria. Springer, Berlin. [16] Bachner, G., Bednar-Friedl, B., 2018. The Effects of Climate Change Impacts on Public Budgets and Implications of Fiscal Counterbalancing Instruments. Environ Model Assess 121–142. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10666-018-9617-3 [25] Bachner, G., Bednar-Friedl, B., Knittel, N., 2019. How does climate change adaptation affect public budgets? Development of an assessment framework and a demonstration for Austria. Mitig Adapt Strateg Glob Change 24, 1325–1341. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-019-9842-3 [26]
Additional relevant material serving as a starting point for mitigation in the transport system:	Dugan, A., Mayer, J., Thaller, A., Bachner, G., Steininger, K.W., 2022. Developing policy packages for low-carbon passenger transport: A mixed methods analysis of trade-offs and synergies. Ecological Economics 193, 107304. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107304 [27]

Sedlacek, N., Steinacher, I., Hartmann, G., Schrampf, J., Bachner, G., Duelli, S., Mayer, J., Steininger, K., Bruckmüller, T., 2021. CLEARER - Climate Neutral Freight Transport (Final report). Vienna, Austria. [28]

Bachner, G., Mayer, J., Fischer, L., Frei, E., Steininger, K.W., Sommer, M., Köppl, A., Schleicher, S., 2021. Application of the Concept of “Functionalities” in Macroeconomic Modelling Frameworks - Insights for Austria and Methodological Lessons Learned (No. 93, 2021), Wegener Center Report. Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Graz. [29]

Actions taken regarding climate change mitigation and adaptation are recognised in land-use planning, renewable energies, decrease carbon fuels, electrical vehicles, public transport, zero/low emissions areas, pedestrian/bike mobility, remote work, and new infrastructures. Some concrete examples for selected adaptation and mitigation strategies are shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Examples of climate mitigation and adaptation selected by the case study

No.	Climate mitigation examples	No.	Climate adaptation examples
1.	Increase of the CO ₂ price: 2022: 30€/t, 2023: 35€/t, 2024: 45€/t, 2025: 55€/t	1.	Transport infrastructure including aspects of mobility: - Further expansion of information and early warning systems - Securing a functioning transport system
2.	Climate ticket [30]	2.	Spatial planning: - Creation and securing of flood retention and flood drainage areas - Clear regulation of dedication prohibitions and restrictions
3.	ÖBB infrastructure plan 2022-2027, 18.2 billion € [31]		
4.	Renewable energy law, 27 TWh by 2030		
5.	Phase-out fossil fuel car engines by 2030		

1.6 Expectations of case study from DISTENDER

The starting point for the case study of Austria are:

- A clear framework conditions committed implementation programs and profound climate policy measures to avoid shift and improve (ASI) traffic are needed. The case study should shed light on the positive spillover effects of a zero-emission transport sector in Austria in the year 2040.
- Special attention is given to infrastructure investments in zero-emission mobility, as they are important building blocks for the green mobility transition. Transport infrastructure influences the length of the route and the choice of means of transport. A further step is to analyse the impacts of changes in the urban land-use for instance from car lanes to bicycle lanes and pedestrian areas.

Accordingly, the main expectations of the Austria Case Study can be summarised as follows:

- Conducting an environmental cost-benefit analysis should shed light on the effectiveness and relevance of ASI-measurements and particularly on infrastructure investments.
- What is the added value created through ASI-measurements particularly through infrastructure investments?
- What societal co-benefits such as regional spill overs, public health, traffic safety, access to mobility, air quality, and noise pollution follow from ASI-measurement?
- What will be the possible consequences on the labour market (broken down according to industries and professions) in Austria's transport sector, if the transition to a new, zero-emission economy by 2040 is successful?
- An analysis with diverse stakeholders will help to identify their needs and potential improvements for further infrastructure investments.

1.7 References

[1] <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/austria>

[2] <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/austria/climate-data-historical>

[3] <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/the-economy-of-austria.html>

[4] <https://www.oebb.at/>

[5] <https://www.asfinag.at/>

[6] <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/>

[7] <https://www.schig.com/>

[8] <https://www.statistik.at/en>

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- [9] <https://www.oerok.gv.at/english-summary>
- [10] <https://www.oerok.gv.at/english-summary>
- [11] <https://www.oerok.gv.at/oerek-2030>
- [12] <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/fileadmin/site/publikationen/rep0819.pdf>
- [13] https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets_en
- [14] <https://futurezone.at/science/co2-emmissionen-oesterreich-industrie-wieder-deutlich-gestiegen-voestalpine-spitzenreiter/401984174>
- [15] <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/umweltthemen/boden/flaecheninanspruchnahme>
- [16] <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-319-12457-5>
- [17] <https://coin.ccca.ac.at/>
- [18] <http://anpassung.ccca.at/en.html>
- [19] https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-strategy/national-energy-and-climate-plans-necps_en
- [20] https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-01/staff_working_document_assessment_necp_austria_en_0.pdf
- [21] https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?toc=OJ:L:2018:328:TOC&uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2018.328.01.0001.01.ENG
- [22] https://www.bmk.gv.at/dam/jcr:eaf9808b-b7f9-43d0-9faf-df28c202ce31/BMK_Mobilitaetsmasterplan2030_EN_UA.pdf
- [23] <https://www.bmk.gv.at/en/topics/climate-environment/climate-protection/austrian-strategy-adaptaion.html>
- [24] https://ec.europa.eu/clima/system/files/2018-11/country_fiche_at_en.pdf
- [25] <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10666-018-9617-3>
- [26] <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11027-019-9842-3>
- [27] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921800921003633?via%3Dihub>

[28] <https://www.klimafonds.gv.at/wp-content/uploads/sites/16/CLEARER-FInal-Report.pdf>

[29]

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[30]

https://www.oesterreich.gv.at/en/themen/bauen_wohnen_und_umwelt/klimaschutz/klimaticket.html

[31] <https://www.railtarget.cz/technologies-and-infrastructure/austria-is-about-to-invest-eur-182-billion-in-the-rail-network-1140.html>

[32] <https://www.naturgefahren.at/karten/detailkarten.html>

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2 Case study 02: The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)

2.1 General description

The case study 02 is specific as it is framed upon certain sectors (mostly energy and water) and then in relation to that also agriculture. It is a regional case study. To be aware of some legislative frames, that may affect the work in DISTENDER, the following note is mentioned: National environmental legislation (de omgevingswet, in Dutch), to be implemented in January 2023, requires integrated environmental management across sectors. Measures to integrate adaptation and mitigation interventions planned within the legislation are, for example, windmills on flood barriers and floating solar panels.

2.1.1 Geography and Economics

The NE of The Netherlands is characterised by agricultural activity, practiced on sea clay in the coastal areas, and sand in the central areas (see area of interest in Figure 7). The agricultural sector, which is an important economical asset in the region, is the main user of water. Historically, the water management system has been primarily designed to serve agricultural productivity.

The coastline to the north has changed, due to the reclamation of land, while the hinterland has subsided. Currently, a sharp separation between the land and the sea can be observed due to the presence of high dikes that protect the hinterland during storms. The IJsselmeer lake on the west serves as a freshwater buffer and flood buffer, through a technical system of dams, pumps, and dikes.

Economically, the northern region of The Netherlands has framed itself as energy region, due to the natural gas fields. Decentralised energy strategies have gained popularity after the induced earthquake in 2012 due to gas extractions, and subsidies for individual energy projects are available. Moreover, solar panel fields are increasing, and centralised regional energy strategies have been developed to enhance climate mitigation. The port of Eemshaven, in the east of the region, is increasingly important for transforming energy from windmills at sea and transportation on land. In the higher laying central area, geothermal energy and water buffers are used to support regional energy strategies.

2.1.2 Quick facts

Table 10 shows general, relevant information about the Dutch case study, considering the area of interest, defined for the purposes of the deliverable as that within their administrative boundaries, the population within the area, the main topographic features and the climate zones that it includes.

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Table 11: Quick facts regarding general information

subject	information
Area of interest (size)	Province of Groningen: 2,900 km ² Province of Friesland: 5,700 km ² <u>Province of Drenthe: 2,600 km²</u> Total: 11,200km ²
Population in area of interest (in 2022) [1]	Province of Groningen: 590,170 Province of Friesland: 654,019 <u>Province of Drenthe: 497,743</u> Total: 1,741,932
Topography of area of interest	Artificially changed landscape due to the reclamation of land, while the hinterland has subsided. The IJsselmeer Lake – a freshwater and flood buffer, through a technical system of dams, pumps and dikes
Climate zone	Maritime climate
Economy	Energy sector

2.2 Participation and co-creation – background

This section addresses two aspects regarding stakeholders. Firstly, it refers to the stakeholders recognised by the case study as relevant, in this case, mostly water authorities, farmers, local authorities and nature organisations. Secondly, responses of the case study on the questionnaire (see Annex I) are elaborated referring to case study familiarity to participatory approaches and its readiness for participation.

2.2.1 Stakeholders

The main stakeholders proposed by the partners from the case study The NE of the Netherlands are listed and described:

- At a regional institutional level, two main bodies are responsible for adaptation and mitigation: **regional water authorities for adaptation and the province for mitigation**. In the NE of The Netherlands, there are three water authorities and three provinces of interest for the project: Water authorities 1) Noorderzijlvest, 2) Fryslân, and 3) Hunze en Aa's (see Figure 6, left), and the three provinces 1) Groningen, 2) Drenthe, and 3) Friesland (see Figure 1, right). Water authority borders differ from provincial borders as they are based on water basins. The institutional bodies work together on specific projects regarding adaptation and mitigation. Moreover, participatory activities are organised by the institutional bodies to consult with the public. Both bodies have a democratic structure; every 4 years Dutch persons entitled to vote can elect parties for the province and the water authorities.

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Figure 6: Water authorities map (left) and provinces maps (right) (Source: both maps provided by HUAS)

- Hanze University of Applied Sciences (HUAS)** is located in the capital city of the province of Groningen. The university works closely with many parties that are involved in climate adaptation and mitigation, including regional energy cooperations and regional adaptation initiatives, innovation labs etc. The university represents the **regional water authority Noorderzijlvest** in DISTENDER, and, therefore, envisions them as potential end-user of the Decision Support System i.e., DSS. As such, HUAS provides a facilitative role in bringing stakeholders together that are considered important for Noorderzijlvest. The most important stakeholders for co-creation in the region are: farmers, the provinces, municipalities, and nature organisations. Noorderzijlvest is required by law to use certain tools and support systems. Legal advice on what tools and data are required to be used is therefore needed for the project. Next to this, European and national environmental laws are of interest when co-producing robust adaptation options that are feasible, or that need a change in laws/regulations.

Insights from T2.1 Progress report

Currently there are 16 stakeholder institutions identified by HUAS. They are set in work packages 2 (Co-Creation & Stakeholder Engagement), 3 (Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios), 4 (Downscaling climate scenarios), 5 (Risk & Vulnerability assessment), 6 (Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies). About 11% of the stakeholders are seen as expertise providers and 17% as data providers.

Insights from WP3 (initial interviews WP3 (WUR) - Case studies)

At the early stage of the WP3 discussion some key stakeholders identified by the HUAS were:

- Water authorities, especially in relation to adaptation;
- Provinces, especially in relation to mitigation;
- Optionally also other stakeholders, such as local government, artists and citizens, as representatives of general public, especially in relation to some specific topics relevant lately, such as earthquake areas.

2.2.2 Quick facts

Tables 12-14 show general information about the readiness of the Dutch case study in terms of stakeholder knowledge, co-creation and participation.

Table 12: Quick facts regarding case study readiness

Case study readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you have experiences with stakeholders' participation?	X		
Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)?		X	
Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users?	X		
Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies? Yes, but with the support from the DISTENDER communication WP.	X		
Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder's side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of? Current farmer protests and unrest regarding national emission rules in the country could create resistance to communicate with farmers. Also, untrust in the government as they are involved in gas extraction (which caused earthquakes in part of the CS area) could be a barrier.		X	

Table 13: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness

Stakeholder readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you know your stakeholder's readiness for participation?	X		
Is it easy for it to take action on an issue? As HUAS, they cannot implement actions, but Noorderzijlvest [2], as end user, yes		X	

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Do you know your stakeholder knowledgeability? Yes, most of the stakeholders are hyper-knowledgeable	X		
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Table 14: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it

Case study involvement	Active participant	Preparation support	Organise/ implement
Workshop back casting and pathway development: organising and facilitating			X
Workshop scenario planning with SSPs and quantitative model output: organising and facilitating			X
Use of semi-quantitative tools: fuzzy cognitive mapping			X

2.3 Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds

This section elaborates on the key concept of WP3 following the socio-economic scenarios as Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP). It shows only a very early stage of this concept application towards the case studies, as it has just started its run within the WP3. Selected focused projects or studies are summarised, justifying that detailed look into them can bring the focused info needed for the WP3.

2.3.1 Available materials and knowledge

The Netherlands is experiencing extreme weather events more regularly. More often, The Netherlands faces torrential rain, heavier storms, or long drier and hotter periods. The Netherlands is particularly vulnerable to flooding because much of the country lies below sea level. Current future scenarios known to the case study estimate a sea level rise along the Dutch coast of 1.2 metres around 2100, compared to the beginning of this century. If the melting of the Antarctic Ice Sheet at the South Pole accelerates, even a 2-metre sea level rise by 2100 is in sight.

The agricultural and horticultural sectors, important for the economy in the region, face several issues due to climate change. Crop growth suffers more frequently from longer dry spells in spring, while wetter summers bring a higher risk of diseases and pests. The extremely dry summers of 2018 and 2019, and the extreme rain and hailstorms of early 2016 already led to extensive damage in agriculture.

The water sector, critical for the region, also faces emphatic implications due to climate change. For instance, there are concerns about the availability of sources of drinking water,

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especially in dry summers and during low river discharges. The stability of the drinking water distribution network and the microbial and chemical safety of water are under pressure. In the future, meeting legal health and environmental targets may be difficult. Furthermore, with a changing climate, the question is whether the water management is optimally designed for the demands placed on it by nature, industry, agriculture, cities and drinking water supply. Moreover, the water sector is expected to make efforts to reduce GHG emissions.

Other urgent effects according to the Dutch National Climate Adaptation Strategy are:

- Increased heat stress in people due to extreme weather events: more sicknesses, hospital admissions, deaths and reduced work performance/increased absenteeism.
- More frequent failure of parts of vital and vulnerable functions due to extreme weather: energy telecoms, IT facilities and main infrastructure.
- Shifting of climate zones causing that some of the flora and fauna - including due to lack of international spatial cohesion in nature - cannot sufficiently move with the shifting climate.
- Loss of health, labour and costs due to a possible increase in infections and allergies such as hay fever or other respiratory complaints.
- Cumulative effects where outages in one sector or location affect other sectors and/or other locations.

In addition, there are effects that may occur later this century but, because of their impact, also need attention now. These include failure of parts of the electricity grid due to extreme weather, restriction of shipping due to extremely high or low water, loss of species and habitats due to extremely low water in estuaries, large-scale IT outages due to failure of critical IT service providers elsewhere in the world, large-scale failure of IT services due to overheating, and changing migration patterns of migratory species. It also involves additional land subsidence with the following consequences: damage to buildings and infrastructure, safety risks such as bursting pipes and additional CO₂ emissions due to peat oxidation.

In response to the droughts of 2018 and 2019, and the extreme flooding in the south of the Netherlands in 2021, adaptation has gained political attention. However, the potential of integrated adaptation and mitigation strategies under multiple socioeconomic and climate/impact scenarios is not yet understood, as the current management heavily relies on biophysical impact models.

The six mentioned key authorities (three water authorities and three provinces, as mentioned in 2.2) all have future visions on their website (see related documents in the table at the bottom of this section). There is also a Dutch National Climate Adaptation Strategy, which explores some of the most pressing effects of climate change for the Netherlands (warmer, wetter, dryer and sea level rising) on 9 sectors: water and space, nature, agriculture, horticulture and fisheries, health, recreation and tourism, infrastructure, energy, IT and telecoms, and security.

Climate impacts (e.g., potential precipitation shortage), basic topography (e.g., land use, green areas) etc. can be found mapped online [3]. Moreover, a national climate change adaptation related knowledge platform can be also found online [4].

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Even though there is a Dutch National Climate Adaptation Strategy, there are no regional exploratory scenarios.

2.3.2 Quick facts

Table 15 lists the key suggested reading when preparing socio-economic scenarios.

Table 15: Quick facts regarding related documents available

Document	Availability
Future vision: Blauwe omgevingsvisie [5]	Online: https://www.noorderzijvest.nl/blauwe-omgevingsvisie
Future vision province of Friesland [6]	Online: https://www.fryslan.fr/downloads-friese-omgevingsvisie
Overview climate risks and impact analysis: National Climate Adaptation Strategy (NAS) [7]	Online https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/overheden/nas/
Climate Atlas [8]	Online maps: https://www.klimaateffectatlas.nl/en/

2.4 Models – backgrounds

This section addresses climate change impacts as recognised by the case study and provide the domains for models that are the subject of the DISTENDER project. In principle four models are addressed: HEALTH (including urban heat, air quality, health impacts), WATER, AFOLU (including agriculture, forestry, other land uses) and ENERGY.

2.4.1 Available materials and knowledge

The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute ([KNMI](#) – the Dutch national weather service) reports on the latest insights regarding the changing Dutch climate. In their recent report from 2021 (KNMI Klimaatsignaal '21) [9], they have identified the following main issues for The Netherlands:

Sea level rise

The future scenarios show greater sea level rise than before. If we do not reduce greenhouse gas emissions, the sea level off the Dutch coast could rise by 1.2 metres around 2100 compared to the beginning of this century. If the melting of the Antarctic Ice Sheet at

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the South Pole accelerates, even a 2-metre sea level rise in 2100 is in sight. In 2014, KNMI calculated that by 2100, the limit would be 1 metre. So, the calculated sea level rise has now been revised upwards. In the long term, the difference in sea level rise between situation as to doing nothing about greenhouse gas emissions and complying with the Paris Climate Agreement, becomes very large. By 2300, this difference could be several metres.

More extreme summer rains

In addition, the new study shows that the heaviest summer rains are becoming more extreme, with the likelihood of fall winds also increasing. Besides extreme showers, the Dutch summer also has another face: that of drought. The likelihood of dry springs and summers has increased. Inland, this increase is due to climate change. Our climate is increasingly shifting towards the climate of southern Europe.

Prolonged drought or heat

The stronger warming of the Arctic may play a role in the greater likelihood of prolonged drought or heat. In fact, they may experience the same type of weather for longer as the jet stream (orbit with high wind speeds at around 10 km altitude) may weaken due to a decrease in the temperature difference between pole and tropics. The slower the jet stream meanders, the more likely the same weather pattern will last longer.

Rivers

In summer, the probability of low water in rivers increases, while in winter, the probability of high-water level increases.

Hurricanes and storms

Hurricanes that occur near Bonaire, St. Eustatius and Saba, the so-called BES islands, increase in strength with more precipitation on average. Hurricanes not only affect the Caribbean Netherlands but can also affect Europe. This already happened once with Hurricane Ophelia in 2017. Remnants of tropical hurricanes can also reach the North Sea and are accompanied by high winds and precipitation. The number of storms in the North Sea is not increasing. The new study shows no increase in North Sea wind strength and associated storm surges.

Urban climate

Cities tend to be warmer than the rural environment. In addition, extreme precipitation and drought are an increasing challenge for cities.

These are also issues detected for the Northern Netherlands. There, the main climate change impacts identified include droughts, flooding, sea level rise, storms and water scarcity.

2.4.2 Domains for simulation models

Here the model domains of the Dutch Case Study are presented. These can be observed in Figure 7, where the black box indicates the domain for meteorological and hydrological models (larger domain), the red box the domain where all modellers have to provide results (domain level 1), and the green box the areas with higher resolution in which all models

have to produce results (domain level 2; see Tables 16-18 for details about the different model domains).

Figure 7 Model domains for the Case Study (black, red and green boxes; see above text and Tables 16-18 for details)

Table 16. Characteristics relative to the larger model domain of the Case Study (black box in Figure 7).

Larger domain characteristics	
Northern boundary	53.932000
Southern boundary	51.535145
Western boundary	3.995002
Eastern boundary	7.839331
Spatial resolution (°)	0.09
Approximate extent (km)	260 x 266

Table 17. Characteristics relative to the domain level 1 of the Case Study (red box in Figure 7).

Domain level 1 characteristics	
Northern boundary	53.932000
Southern boundary	52.071951
Western boundary	4.169413
Eastern boundary	7.407940
Spatial resolution (°)	0.03
Approximate extent (km)	218 x 208

Table 18. Characteristics relative to the domain level 2 of the Case Study (green box in Figure 7).

Domain level 2 characteristics	
Northern boundary	53.465150
Southern boundary	52.609710

Western boundary	5.396200
Eastern boundary	7.244650
Spatial resolution (°)	0.01
Approximate extent (km)	125 x 96

2.4.3 Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest

In this section, the potential climate impacts as recognised by the case study are presented.

Table 19: Key characteristics of the Case Study

Related starting point	
Potential climate impact	Droughts Flooding Sea level rise Storms Water scarcity
Sectors of interest	Agriculture Coastal areas Energy Water
Biophysical and/or economic impacts of the climate hazards	<p>ENERGY: these hazards have an effect on the renewable energy production, extremely dependent on weather conditions (e.g., floating solar panels; windmills at sea and flood barriers; hydrogen plants and underground infrastructure; geothermal warmth grit)</p> <p>AFOLU (agriculture, forestry, other land uses): floods, droughts, sea-level rise, storms and water scarcity on agriculture lead to changes to (i) grassland in relation to milk production; (ii) introduction of salt-resistant crops due to saltwater intrusion; (iii) social debate as to the costs of maintenance of agroforestry practices and feasible alternatives</p> <p>WATER: floods, droughts and sea level rise have multiple effects on economy e.g., future energy system</p>

2.4.4 Quick facts

Table 20 shows sectors and models, as suggested by DISTENDER project, and their relation to the interests of the case study.

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Table 20: Impact models, relevant for the Case Study

SECTORS AND MODELS ADOPTED	Sub-sectors dealt with	CS interest in the sector	Explanation
HEALTH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SUEWS model</u> simulates radiation, energy and water balances • <u>ENVI-met</u> assesses the efficiency of mitigation actions • <u>URBAIR model</u> 	Urban heat Air quality Health impact		CS did not express an interest in this sector
ENERGY		YES	Interest in the impacts of floods, droughts, SLR, storms and water scarcity on energy sector
AFOLU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>YieldSAFE model</u> predicts plant growth, production 	Agriculture Forestry Other land use	YES	Interest in gaining insight into future land use
WATER <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SWAT model</u> calculates relevant water fluxes at the land surface, in the soil, groundwater and river • <u>Economic assessment</u> evaluates the value of water sector climate change impacts 	Flooding	YES	Interest in the upstream and downstream management of the dikes, water quality and temperature.
	Drought	YES	

2.5 Strategies – backgrounds

This section elaborates on knowledge and materials available in relation to climate change adaptation and mitigation known to the case study.

2.5.1 Available materials and knowledge: general

The following types of adaptation and mitigation actions have been selected as relevant by this case study:

- Natural based solutions;
- Water management;

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- Flooding;
- Drainage systems;
- Land-use planning;
- Information campaigns;
- Renewable energies;
- Decrease carbon fuels;
- Zero/low emission areas;
- Adapt crop varieties.

Note: A scoping meeting with the Noorderzijlvest Water Authority resulted in the above list of planned actions for both adaptation and mitigation. In section Strategies-backgrounds, we will go through current developments surrounding these planned actions in more detail. Most actions/strategies and plans can be found in the future visions mentioned in this chapter.

2.5.2 Available materials and knowledge: mitigation related

Planned actions for mitigation

The main mitigation-related actions in the case study are listed below and explained in detail in Table 21.

- Floating solar panels;
- Windmills at sea;
- Windmills on flood barriers;
- Hydrogen plants and underground infrastructure;
- Salt-marshes are kept wet to reduce CO₂ emissions and reduce wave impacts on flood-barriers;
- Regional energy strategies & subsidies, focussing on household level;
- Geothermal warmth grit.

Table 21: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation

Aims	Climate mitigation examples
Energy sector 1. Renewable energy production	Action taken: <i>Floating solar panels [10]</i> Level: implementational Status of the action: Planned Comments: The National Consortium Zon op Water aims to have 2000 hectares of floating solar power plants in the Netherlands by 2023. The floating solar panel park in Sellingerbeetse (within the region of the CS) is the biggest one in Europe, with over 76,600 solar panels. A former sand mining lake was transformed partially in a floating solar panel park. Another floating solar panel park is situated in Tynaarlo (also within the region of the CS, and also a former sand mining lake), that currently holds around 41,000 solar panels.

2. Renewable energy production

Action taken: *Windmills at sea*

Level: implementational, with plans for further implementation

Comments: The North Sea and the Wadden Sea already contain several windmill parks (6 in total to date) and plans to further expand these areas and develop new ones.

3. Renewable energy production

Action taken: *Windmills on flood barriers*

Level: implementational

Comments: The Oostpolder dike (near Eemshaven, Groningen province), the first wind turbines to be built on primary flood defenses. The challenge in this instance is that the wind turbines, weighing many thousands of tons apiece, are not allowed to impact the structure of the dike or affect the flood protection as a whole in any way. In fact, ideally, they should reinforce the system. Wind turbines on dikes have numerous benefits, given that sea dams, which are used to protect against flooding, are ideal sites for wind energy. Due to their location, they boast fantastic wind conditions, similar to those at high sea. These structures have limited negative impacts on the local population since the closest settlements are generally located quite a way away. Wind turbines can also serve as protection against flooding.

4. Renewable energy production

Action taken: *Hydrogen plants and underground infrastructure*

Level: implementational

Comments: Recently, companies have already invested a great deal in hydrogen in the Northern Netherlands. International companies, such as Engie, Equinor, Gasunie, RWE, Shell and Vattenfall, but also small and medium-sized enterprises in the North. Regional and local authorities have also made commitments to enable the hydrogen chain in the Northern Netherlands.

In the last years the Northern Netherlands has received European recognition for its commitment to developing the hydrogen economy. Furthermore, the region has been designated as the leading Hydrogen Valley in Europe, where green hydrogen is produced, transported and applied in industry, transport and buildings.

From now until 2025, the Northern Netherlands will develop and scale up between 5 to 10 PJ (PT corresponds to petajoule = 10^{15} joules) hydrogen capacity per year with various projects

<p>5. Renewable energy production</p>	<p>in the value chain, from production (Eemshydrogen, DJEWELS 1 and 2, HyNetherlands Phase 1, GZI Next Emmen) and infrastructure (Hydrogen backbone Northern Netherlands and HyStock upstream) to use cases (BioMCN, Holthausen, Magnum Power Station, SkyNRG, Hydrogen Hoogeveen, HEAVENN).</p> <p>Action taken: (Geothermal) warmth grit Level: implementational Comments: In the Netherlands, geothermal heat is already used in greenhouse farming, but not yet on a large scale in the building environment.</p> <p>A geothermal warmth grit system is currently being developed in the province of Drenthe. This is a regular geothermal system in which, groundwater a temperature between 70 and 100°C from a depth varying between 1,500 to 4,000 m is used to heat houses or greenhouses. After releasing the heat, the cooled groundwater is returned to the ground.</p> <p>In the province of Friesland, the potential for geothermal warmth grit is currently being researched. Even though the water they found is warm enough, it remains questionable whether there is enough water volume to develop a geothermal warmth grit.</p> <p>The development of a warmth grit in the Northwest of Groningen started in 2017. It is suggested that, in the future, 10,000 companies, institutions and houses will be able to use this grit. This warmth grit runs on rest heat that is released when cooling servers in data centres.</p>
<p>6. Energy waste reduction & Renewable energy production</p>	<p>Action taken: <i>Regional energy strategies & subsidies, focussing on household level</i> Level: strategic (strategies are developed, actions need to be implemented) Comments: Every province (three in total) within the region of the CS has their own Regional Energy Strategy. What follows is a summary of the aims of the three strategies: “As a society in Drenthe, we want to make a sustainable contribution to good living, working and recreation in the region. The Regional Energy Strategy (RES) 1.0 for the Drenthe region states that the aim is to generate a quarter of the energy consumed in Drenthe from wind energy and large-scale solar energy by 2030. That is 3.45 Terawatt hours</p>

(TWh). Until 1 July 2021, the municipal councils, provincial councils and general boards of the water boards in the Drenthe region have the time to decide on the ambitions and agreements in the RES 1.0. The RES 1.0 region of Drenthe is the result of close cooperation between companies, social partners, young people, network managers and authorities. Advice from residents was taken into account in the RES 1.0.” [16]

“Worldwide, we have made agreements to protect our climate. This is necessary to combat global warming. One of the ways we are doing this is by limiting fossil fuel emissions. We are going to save energy and generate sustainable energy. With the RES 1.0, we are continuing to work on the energy transition, among other things. In many places In many places in the province work is already being done and innovative experiments making our energy demand more sustainable.” [15]

“RES 1.0 Groningen is the energy strategy of the Groningen municipalities, the water boards Noorderzijlvest and Hunze en Aa's and the Province of Groningen in collaboration with various stakeholders. With this RES 1.0, we determine what share of the 35 TWh we, as Groningen RES, want to take for our account. On the basis of realised projects and the established policy frameworks of the policy frameworks of the authorities, we state - subject to a number of conditions - that a bid of 5.7 TWh in 2030 is realistic.” [11]

“The RIS3 (regional innovation strategy for smart specialisation) [12] is a combined innovation strategy by the three northern provinces, the bigger municipalities, and subsidy organisation SNN (Northern Netherlands Alliance). This strategy is the foundation for the European Regional Development Fund, which funds the subsidy programs in the Northern Netherlands to implement the goals from the RIS3. The subsidies focus on households as well as SMEs and knowledge institutions.” [12]

**Water sector /
Health sector**
1. Flooding &
Sea level rise &
Air pollution

Action taken: Salt marshes are kept wet to reduce CO₂ emissions and reduce wave impacts on flood barriers.

Level: implementational

Comments: The potential role of salt marshes to adapt the Wadden Sea's flood defenses was explored in the Netherlands Wadden Region Delta Programme [13]. Coastal wetlands e.g., salt marshes, are increasingly recognized as

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valuable natural defenses that protect coasts against strong wave activity. Explorative modelling results indicate that Wadden Sea salt marshes diminish wave heights, even under extreme conditions. Therefore, a salt-marsh zone in front of the Wadden Sea dikes that could keep pace with sea level rise may result in a reduced dike reinforcement task. Furthermore, salt marshes capture silt, partly because salt marsh vegetation inhibits currents. By trapping silt, salt marshes can grow along with sea level rise, improving the water quality, favouring the sequestration of CO₂.

2.5.3 Available materials and knowledge: adaptation related

Planned actions for adaptation

The most relevant adaptation-related actions in the case study are listed below and explained in detail in Table 22.

- Agricultural lands are altered into water buffer areas for both flooding and drought episodes;
- Experiments with salt and drought resistant crops are initiated;
- Innovative flood-barrier concepts are implemented such as twin-dike systems;
- Implementation of green-blue nature-based solutions for flood and drought in cities;
- (Art) festivals to increase climate awareness;
- Mini climate week in cooperation with the Global Centre on Adaptation to increase awareness and share solutions, focussing on youth.

Table 22: Current trends and action taken regarding climate adaptation

Issues	Climate adaptation examples
Water sector 1. Flooding	<p>Actions taken: <i>Innovative flood-barrier concepts are implemented such as twin-dike systems.</i></p> <p>Level: implementational</p> <p>Comments: Along the Wadden Sea, a 2.5 km long double levee section has been constructed. The area between the levees is now being designed with controlled sea water inflow for the farming of salt-tolerant crops and silt sediments.</p> <p>The Twin Dike section is part of a wider levee reinforcement project for all levees near Delfzijl to meet new requirements that prelude on future sea level rise. The requirements also include the levees to be earthquake proof as this part of the Netherlands has one of the world's largest natural gas fields. Gas extractions cause soil subsidence and earthquakes.</p>

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2. Flooding & Drought

In this particular section, the original levee kept its shape but an additional levee has been constructed inland, creating a "bathtub". The original levee has been designed for overtopping so, during a storm sea water can reach this enclosed inland. The concept fits within the general flood protection policy of The Netherlands that sustains the principle of raised levees also having its disadvantages. In general, higher levees increase flood risk in case of a breach causing the water to flow in with much higher force.

Additionally, the Dutch national flood protection policy calls for levee reinforcements that includes additional objectives, e.g., benefits to agriculture, nature and recreation.

Action taken: *Altering of agricultural lands into water buffer areas for both flooding and drought episodes*

Level: implementational

Comments: There are currently around 50 water buffers throughout The Netherlands, with about a dozen located in Northern region. Several new water buffers are currently in development.

One of the larger water buffers in the Northern region is De Onlanden. This water buffer was completed in 2015. However, in January 2012, part of De Onlanden had to temporarily collect water to prevent the area around Tolberter Petten from flooding. The construction of De Onlanden has also led to several important results:

- In the city of Groningen there is no longer any water nuisance. The costs of the construction were much lower than other possible solutions, such as raising all the quays.
- In addition to water storage, new marshland nature has been created.
- Due to De Onlanden, there is less inconvenience in the water system of Noorderzijlvest.

3. Flooding & Drought

Action taken: *Implementation of green-blue nature-based solutions for flood and drought in cities*

Level: implementational

Comments: Throughout the Netherlands, also in the CS region, a broad range of different types of swales have been developed. The first swales were constructed over 20 years ago to store rainwater, infiltrate and treat, and reduce negative

<p>4. Drought</p>	<p>impacts such as sewer overflows. A swale is a ditch filled with gravel and sand, which can both retain and infiltrate water. Because swales are planted, they fit well in green areas and greenbelts.</p> <p>Swales are excellent means of improving the urban water system. In a swale system, water from roofs and roads does not flow into the sewerage system, but rather into the swale via above-ground gutters and/or ditches. A well-designed swale system buffers and infiltrates rainwater; thereby minimising overflows, improving surface water quality and limiting desiccation.</p> <p>Swales are part of a robust stormwater system. Due to their visibility, bottlenecks and overloading are noticed earlier and residents and the municipality can work together on solutions.</p> <p>Action taken: <i>Experiments with salt and drought-resistant crops are initiated</i> Level: implementational Comments: Along the Wadden Sea, a 2.5 km long double levee section has been constructed. The area between the levees is designed with controlled sea water inflow for the farming of salt tolerant crops and silt sediments.</p>
<p>General 1. Climate change</p> <p>2. Climate change</p>	<p>Action taken: <i>(art)festivals to increase climate awareness</i> Level: implementational Comments: Let's Gro – A festival on the future of Groningen. A weekend full of presentations, workshops, lectures and discussions on ideas for the future, new projects in the region, greening the area, and the implications of climate change and how Groningen might adapt to them.</p> <p>Action taken: <i>Mini-climate week</i> in cooperation with the Global Center on Adaptation [14] to increase awareness and share solutions, focussing on youth explore fluctuating water level strategies Level: implementational Comments: Climate Adaptation Week (by Global Center on Adaptation) – a free, interactive international festival experience full of knowledge, inspiration, and action on climate adaptation. A week full of inspiring activities, events, and initiatives in the city of Groningen and the region, on the topic of climate adaptation.</p>

2.5.4 Quick facts

Table 23 lists documents with the contents relevant for the mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Table 23: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
Regional Energy Strategy Drenthe [16]	Online: RES 1.0 regio Drenthe - Energie voor Drenthe
Regional Energy Strategy Friesland [15]	Online: Regional Energy Strategy Friesland: RES-1.0 RES-FRYSLÂN NL DEF digitaal.pdf (resfryslan.frl)
Regional Energy Strategy Groningen [11]	Online: Regional Energy Strategy Groningen: Achtergrondinformatie - RES Groningen
Strategy for the North [12]	Online: RIS3: Strategie voor het Noorden SNN

2.6 Expectations of case study from DISTENDER

The main expectations of the Case Study from the DISTENDER project can be listed as follows:

- To co-produce pathways to integrate adaptation and mitigation strategies: 1. Inclusion of multiple knowledge frame. 2. Creative and structured participatory methods in a set of workshops
- To use the DISTENDER approach to encourage creativity while accounting for multiple socioeconomic scenarios: 1. Focus on worldviews and ontologies associated with socioeconomic scenarios. 2. Creative and structured participatory methods in a set of workshops.

2.7 References

[1] <https://allecijfers.nl/ranglijst/aantal-inwoners-per-provincie-in-nederland/#tablerow>

[2] <https://www.noorderzijvest.nl/>

[3] <https://www.klimaat-effectatlas.nl/en/>

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- [4] <https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/en>
- [5] <https://www.noorderzijvest.nl/blauwe-omgevingsvisie>
- [6] <https://www.fryslan.frl/downloads-friese-omgevingsvisie>
- [7] <https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/overheden/nas/>
- [8] <https://www.klimaat-effectatlas.nl/en/>
- [9] <https://www.knmi.nl/kennis-en-datacentrum/achtergrond/knmi-klimaatsignaal-21>
- [10] <https://groenleven.nl/projecten/uitbreiding-drijvend-zonnepark-tynaarlo/>
- [11] <https://www.resgroningen.nl/default.aspx>
- [12] <https://www.snn.nl/over-snn/europa-2021-2027/ris3-strategie-voor-het-noorden>
- [13] <https://english.deltaprogramma.nl/areas/wadden>
- [14] <https://gca.org/>
- [15] https://www.resfryslan.frl/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/RES-1.0_RES-FRYSL%C3%82N_NL_DEF_digitaal.pdf
- [16] <https://energievoordrenthe.nl/res+10+regio+drenthe/default.aspx#folder=1937417>

3 Case study 03: Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) (EURAF)* description mostly for Dehesas

3.1 General description

Dehesas in Spanish language and montados in Portuguese language, refer to a special type of cultural landscape. The case study 03 is specific as it is framed upon certain landscape typology which results from special agroforestry economy that reflects in land use. Therefore, the case includes parts of region Extremadura (Spain) and Alentejo (Portugal). Detailed information gathered in this chapter mostly refers to the Spanish case, as access to Portuguese stakeholders and data provides was limited at this stage. During the project this gap will be filled in.

3.1.1 Geography and Economics

Dehesas (in Spain) and montados (in Portugal) are agrosilvopastoral land use systems that cover around 3.8 million ha in the Southwestern region of the Iberian Peninsula (see area of interest in Figure 8). In Spain, the dehesa land use covers 2,765,233 ha [1], of which 1,452,228.5 ha are located in Extremadura [2]. Montados and dehesas are low-intensity and low-input farming systems i.e., animal stocking rates, fertilizers and pesticides, with high structural diversity i.e., a mosaic of land cover and land use. The use of seminatural vegetation by livestock, often in combination with the presence of other semi-natural elements (field margins, hedges, ponds and rocky outcrops), are a determinant feature of these systems.

The montado and dehesa land use system has long been highly valued from a socioeconomic point of view and acknowledged as the epitome of multifunctionality as integrated management allows for quality animal production in combination with a range of forest products and ecosystem services, including cork, fuelwood, acorns, hunting, fishing, tourism, biodiversity conservation. As a result, montados and dehesas are considered as a High Nature Value (HNV) [3] land use systems.

Climate change is already having important socioeconomic and environmental consequences in the region. In Mediterranean Europe yearly rainfall is expected to drop by up to 20% of current annual precipitation (with up to 50% reduction in summer). Annual mean temperature increases would be in the order of 3-4°C (4-5°C in summer and 2 -3°C in winter). Models predict changes in frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme events with more hot days, heat waves, heavy precipitation events, and fewer cold days. Rising temperatures and decreasing rainfall will lead to increased occurrence of drought periods. This induces an increase in the most important abiotic risks in the Mediterranean region, water scarcity and fire. In this context, drought will probably be a main factor reducing tree and pasture productivity, driving pest outbreaks and increasing episodes of tree mortality that compromise the long-term persistence of montados and dehesas [4].

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Abandonment of rural areas and aging population results in extensification and abandonment in less fertile and more peripheral areas which, in turn, leads to shrub encroachment and high fire risk. In the more productive areas, the threat comes from increased pressure for intensification that results in overgrazing, vegetation loss and land use change.

DISTENDER will cover two areas where dehesa land use is prevalent. The first area is a portion of the Tagus river basin from the Guadarrama river sub-catchment in the east to the border between Extremadura and Portugal in the west. The second area is the region of Extremadura, comprising the provinces of Cáceres and Badajoz. The Tagus and the Guadiana rivers are the most important drainage basins in southwestern Spain, both cutting through a vast territory of Extremadura, where dehesa land use is dominant.

Extremadura is located in the south-west of the Iberian Peninsula, the average height is approximately 430 m. Most of the region is made up of vast stretches of undulating to flat peneplains and river depressions made up of old schist and greywacke as well as geologically more recent alluvial deposits. Reliefs of quartzite and granite dominate the three main mountain ranges that intersect the undulating plains: The Sistema Central in the north has its highest elevation at the Calvitero peak (2,425 m above sea level) and is mainly comprised of 4 mountain ranges (from east to west): Sierra de Gredos, Sierra de Béjar, Sierra de Francia and Sierra de Gata. The central part of the region is penetrated by the Montes de Toledo range, reaching its maximum elevation at the Villuercas peak with 1,601 m. Montes de Toledo separates the Tagus from the Guadiana river basin. The third area, in the south of the region, belongs to the Sierra Morena range reaching its highest elevation at 1,140 m in the Tentudia peak.

The two major drainage basins formed by the Tagus and Guadiana rivers are located in Cáceres and Badajoz provinces, respectively, which constitutes the two principal administrative divisions of the region (provinces). Both rivers flow east to west entering Portugal. Principal and secondary rivers depend upon the various reservoirs in the area, forming a vast hydrological network that supplies water for crops, electricity and the general consumption by inhabitants (adapted from [5] and [6])

Dehesas in Extremadura are characterized by open canopy woodlands of mainly *Quercus suber* and *Quercus rotundifolia*, mixed in some areas with other Mediterranean tree species, with interspersed patches of shrubs and with natural or cultivated grassland in the undercover, which are grazed by livestock (Iberian pigs, sheep, cows, goats).

According to the case study, there is no estimation on the number of people who are both **economically dependent** and directly involved in the management of dehesas, and therefore, directly affected by climate change and the adoption of adaptation and mitigation strategies. Regional agricultural statistics shows that in 2021 nearly 20% of the working population in Extremadura was employed in the agricultural sector. However, sectorial data are not disaggregated by sub-sector nor by any type of farm category, nor farming system.

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3.1.2 Quick facts

Table 24 shows general, relevant information about the dehesas and montados case study, including the area of interest, defined for the purposes of the deliverable as that within their administrative boundaries, the population within the area, the main topographic features and the climate zones that it includes.

Table 24: Quick facts regarding general information. Please note that the information contained in this Table is mainly for the Spanish domain of the Case Study (Extremadura) since partners reported problems to get the information for the Portuguese part

subject	information
Area of interest (size)	Extremadura Region: 41,635.43 km ² Tagus river basin (within Spain): 55,781 km ² (out of this only 32,726.60 km ² will be included in the project)
Population in area of interest (in 2021)	Population in Extremadura: 1,059,501. Extremadura population density of 25,45 person/km ² , 19% of people > 65, unemployed 13.9% (people 16-64)
Topography of area of interest	<p>Extremadura is located in the south-west of the Iberian Peninsula. Its average height is approximately 430 m, and the surface is mostly in a shape of peneplains and river depressions. Three main mountain ranges intersect the undulating plains (the Sistema Central, the Montes de Toledo range and the Sierra Morena range)</p> <p>The two major drainage basins formed by the Tagus and Guadiana rivers are located in Cáceres and Badajoz provinces. Principal and secondary rivers depend upon the various reservoirs in the area, forming a vast hydrological network that supplies water for crops, electricity and the general consumption by inhabitants (adapted from [5] and [6])</p> <p>Dehesas in Extremadura are characterized by open canopy woodlands with interspersed patches of shrubs and with natural or cultivated grassland in the undercover, which are grazed by livestock</p>
Climate zone:	Climate is Mediterranean semi-arid to dry sub-humid with some oceanic influence. Temporally and spatially variable low precipitation dominates most of the region amounting to 450 mm of mean annual rainfall in the lowest areas, contrasting with 1,200 mm in some parts of the northern mountains of the region and 1,000 mm in the mountainous south

3.2 Participation and co-creation – background

This section addresses two aspects regarding stakeholders. Firstly, it refers to the stakeholders recognised by the case study as relevant. In this particular case, mostly state owned infrastructure companies are presented. Secondly, responses of the case study on the questionnaire (see Annex I) are elaborated referring to case study familiarity to participatory approaches and its readiness for participation. Case study 03 shows very clear picture about stakeholders.

3.2.1 Stakeholders

In the context of the dehesa agro-ecosystems, various categories of stakeholders can be identified based on their roles and responsibilities in the management of dehesa landscapes. The main stakeholders proposed by the partners from the Dehesa and montado Case Study are listed and described:

1. **Decision-makers:** *stakeholders who make decisions on the management of dehesa farms and landscapes, including the adoption of mitigation and adaptation practices. Two sub-categories are considered:*
 - a. *Landowners, farm managers and workers* (including cork harvesters, tree pruners, cattle ranchers and shepherds, apiculturists, and others): they are either fully or partially dependent economically of the goods and services provided by dehesa agroecosystems and they are directly involved in management decisions and in the adoption and implementation of mitigation and adaptation strategies.
 - b. *Regional government officials from the Agricultural Department and Forest Service office:* these include technicians responsible for monitoring, supervision and law enforcement, and providing extension support.
2. **Policy-makers (at regional, national and European level):** these stakeholders have the crucial role of legislating and enacting evidence-based policies that support adaptation and mitigation strategies and practices.
3. **Users:** these include, on the one hand, people who may economically depend on dehesas, but do not make decisions regarding their management, and, on the other hand, those people who have some personal and/or cultural attachment to dehesas. Included in this stakeholder category are:
 - *Entrepreneurs, agribusinesses and associated industries* (including hunting, eco-tourism): these include people working along the product value chain (traders and processors of the various goods and services produced).
 - *Rural people living in dehesa landscapes:* people who live in rural communities within dehesa landscapes, and have thus strong social and cultural bonds, but who are not economically dependent on dehesa systems.
 - *Scientists and researchers* (from the academic and research institutions): their role is to study and generate information on the various environmental, economic and social aspects of the dehesa land use system in order to help dehesa managers and policy makers to make better, informed decisions.

Insights from T2.1 Progress report

Presently, a total of relevant 18 stakeholders have been identified for the case study, from which 15 are external to the DISTENDER project. Work packages of relevance are 6 (Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies) and 7 (Cost-benefits evaluation and impacts). 9% of the stakeholders are expected to provide expertise and 6% to provide data, respectively, to the DISTENDER project. No end-users were listed but may be reached to in future stages of the project.

Insights from the interviews WP3 (WUR) - Case studies

At the early stage of the WP3 discussion some key stakeholders identified by the EURAF were:

- Landowners from 12 farms in Spain and Portugal;
- Policy makers.

3.2.2 Quick facts

Tables 25-27 display general information about the readiness of the Dehesa and montado Case Study in terms of stakeholder knowledge, co-creation and participation.

Table 25: Quick facts regarding case study readiness

Case study readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you have experiences with stakeholders’ participation?	X		
Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)?		X	
Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users?		X	
Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies?	X		
Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder's side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of?	X		

Table 26: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness

Stakeholder readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you know your stakeholder’s readiness for participation?	X (this is known for 8 to 10 of them)		

Is it easy for it to take action on an issue?	X (this is valid for 8 of them)		
Do you know your stakeholder knowledgeability?	X		

Table 27: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it

Case study involvement	Active participant	Preparation support	Organise/ implement
Workshop	X		
SWOT analysis	X	X	
Problem diagnosis	X	X	

3.3 Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds

This section elaborates on the key concept of WP3 following the socio-economic scenarios as Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP). It shows only a very early stage of this concept application towards the case studies, as it has just started its run within the WP3. Selected focused projects or studies are summarised, justifying that detailed look into them can bring the focused info needed for the WP3.

3.3.1 Available materials and knowledge

The main strategies, projects and other sources of information are listed below. Additional scientific studies can be found in the Annex IV.

The regional government of Extremadura has developed a strategy, entitled **Strategy of Green and Circular Economy Extremadura 2030** [7]. It aims to join and align most of the existing material and human resources in Extremadura in the search for a greener and more circular society and economy, where natural resources are a permanent source of opportunities for the regional population. The first achievement of this strategy has been to reach a consensus between political, social and economic stakeholders in Extremadura. In this strategy, participation is key through:

- A broad network of supporters of the strategy, including local government units, businesses and companies, education centres, different collectives and institution, including NGOs, cultural associations, rural development organizations, individuals, foundations, institutions and other entities.
- A comprehensive and in-depth diagnosis study of the current situation to develop a green and circular economy.

The Strategy also includes:

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- Territorial and demographic characterization.
- Sectorial characterization:
 - Agriculture and livestock
 - Agrifood industry
 - Silviculture
 - Construction and energy efficiency
 - Renewable energy
 - Recycling and waste management
 - Tourism
- Business and enterprise resources and capacity
- Technology and scientific capacity.
- Infrastructure and resources:
 - Logistics: Transportation (roads, railways, air transport)
 - Industrial areas
 - Hydraulic infrastructure
 - Energy infrastructure
 - Recycling and waste management
- SWOT analysis [8]
- Identification of challenges and opportunities
- Vision, mission and principles of the strategy
- Objectives: strategic and functional
- A platform to support citizens participation and Participatory processes [9]

For nearly a decade, European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) has been engaged with a number of dehesa stakeholders in action research and knowledge-sharing activities supported through various EU-funded projects. Some of the most relevant are listed below:

Interreg Prodehesa-montado [10] project aims to promote the necessary actions to add value to the Spanish dehesas and the Portuguese montados both environmentally and economically from a sustainable development perspective, through the creation of stable cooperation structures that promote businesses investing in innovation, developing synergies between companies, R&D&i, technology transfer, public service applications and the demand for dehesa and montado products.

AGFORWARD (AGroFORestry that Will Advance Rural Development) [11] was a four-year research project funded by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (FP7). The overall aim of the project was to promote agroforestry practices in Europe that will advance rural development i.e., improved competitiveness, and social and environmental enhancement.

ECCOMAP [12] aimed at determining the priority areas for the management of biodiversity in a coordinated way in Extremadura and Alentejo (Portugal) regions, in order to promote their preferential consideration in future actions of environmental and economic study and management. The project is fundamentally based on the use of the generalized concept of hotspot, including species richness, endemism, rarity, and threat, and on the simultaneous implementation of different methods of selection of sites.

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In this project, a socio-economic regionalization is provided: The ECCOMAP project's regionalization of Extremadura–Alentejo was based on an extensive sample of sites (about 4000) which were characterized on the basis of numerous socioeconomic variables. After its classification, the sample served to delineate the regions by means of interpolation [13]. Ten (10) socioeconomic regions were identified based on an extensive sample of sites (about 4,000) which were characterized on the basis of numerous socioeconomic variables, including heterogenous agricultural and forestry landscapes, dehesas, extensive farming areas, intensive farming areas, forestry landscapes, mountain zones with woodland and scrub, heterogenous farming areas and urban-industrial environments.

3.3.2 Quick facts

Table 28 lists documents which may be relevant for socioeconomic scenarios and SSPs, respectively. For further readings on the topic, the reader is referred to Table 28 and supplementary material in Annex IV.

Table 28: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
Strategy of Green and Circular Economy Extremadura 2030 [20], [21]	Online: https://extremadura2030.com/presentacion-estrategia/ https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/extremadura-2030-green-and-circular-economy-strategy-extremadura-2030
Diagnosis study of the current situation to develop and green and circular economy [22]	Online: https://extremadura2030.com/diagnostico-de-extremadura/
Publications from the Extremadura Statistics Institute [2]	Online: https://ciudadano.gobex.es/web/ieex/publicaciones-tipo
Yearly Statistics of Extremadura regarding different sectors, including e.g., territory [2]	Online: Anuario Estadístico (2013; 2018; 2019; 2020; 2021)
Socioeconomic Atlas of Extremadura, every two years from 2009 to 2021 [2]	Online: Atlas Socio-económico de Extremadura
Demography status of Extremadura (1999-2019) [2]	Online: Informe situación demográfica de Extremadura (1999-2019)
Industrial production index of Extremadura [2]	Online: Índice de Producción Industrial
Interreg Prodehesa-montado [10]	Online: https://prodehesamontado.eu/

AGFORWARD (AGroFORestry that Will Advance Rural Development) [11]	Online: https://agforward.eu/
ECCOMAP [12]	Online: https://www.eweb.unex.es/eweb/gic_eccomap/en/?PARTNER

3.4 Models – backgrounds

This section addresses climate change impacts as recognised by the case study and provide the domains for models that are the subject of the DISTENDER project. In principle four models are addressed: HEALTH (including urban heat, air quality, health impacts), WATER, AFLOU (including agriculture, forestry, other land uses) and ENERGY.

3.4.1 Available materials and knowledge

The challenge for scientists, policy makers, and land managers working on developing effective and productive mitigation and adaptation strategies is to strengthen current farming systems practices while making them less vulnerable to climate variability.

The most significant climate hazards identified for the area include:

- Droughts and torrential rains;
- Extreme temperatures and heat waves;
- Water scarcity;
- Locally observed strong winds.

The negative impacts of these climate hazards are:

- Reduced natural regeneration;
- Tree mortality;
- Soil erosion when there are torrential rains;
- Decreased primary productivity;
- Decreased animal productivity.

3.4.2 Domains for simulation models

Here we present the model domains of the Dehesa and montado Case Study. These are shown in Figure 8, where the black box indicates the domain for meteorological and hydrological models (larger domain) and the red box the domain where all modellers are required to provide results (domain level 1) (see Tables 29 and 30 for details about the different model domains).

Figure 8 Model domains for the Case Study (black and red boxes; see text above and Tables 29 and 30 for details)

Table 29. Characteristics relative to the larger model domain of the Case Study (black box in Figure 8).

Larger domain characteristics	
Northern boundary	41.69773838
Southern boundary	37.830126
Western boundary	-9.846654
Eastern boundary	-0.749997
Spatial resolution (°)	0.09
Approximate extent (km)	785 x 430

Table 30. Characteristics relative to the model domain level 1 of the Case Study (red box in Figure 8).

Domain level 1 characteristics	
Northern boundary	40.896063
Southern boundary	37.830126
Western boundary	-9.846654
Eastern boundary	-3.350000
Spatial resolution (°)	0.09
Approximate extent (km)	560 x 335

3.4.3 Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest

In this section, the potential climate impacts as recognised by the case study are structured.

Table 31: Key characteristics of the Case Study

Related starting point	

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Potential climate impact	Droughts and torrential rains Extreme temperatures and heat waves Water scarcity Locally observed strong winds
Sectors directly affected	Agriculture
Biophysical and/or economic impacts of the climate hazards commented in relation to the topics of models applied	AFOLU (agriculture, forestry, other land uses): climate hazards have a long-term effect on the health of trees (e.g., tree species distribution) and livestock, with the concomitant economical losses WATER: droughts can affect the availability of hydric resources, which are of relevance for the region and its socioeconomic development

3.4.4 Quick facts

Table 32 shows sectors and models, as suggested by DISTENDER project, and their relation to the interests of the Case Study.

Table 32: Impact models, relevant for the Dehesas and montados Case Study

SECTORS AND MODELS ADOPTED	Sub-sectors dealt with	CS interest in the sector	Explanation
HEALTH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SUEWS model</u> simulates radiation, energy and water balances • <u>ENVI-met</u> assesses the efficiency of mitigation actions • <u>URBAIR model</u> 	Urban heat Air quality Health impact		The CS is not interested in the HEALTH sector
ENERGY			The CS is not interested in the ENERGY sector
AFOLU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>YieldSAFE model</u> predicts plant growth, production 	Agriculture Forestry Other land use	YES YES YES	Interest in long-term health of trees and the impact on livestock (note: YieldSAFE cannot model tree species distribution)
WATER	Flooding		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SWAT model</u> calculates relevant water fluxes at the land surface, in the soil, groundwater and river. • <u>Economic assessment</u> evaluates the value of water sector climate change impacts 	Drought	YES	Interest in upstream and downstream management flow of the reservoir (Tagus Basin) at the watershed and at the farm level, respectively, as well as the water availability for plants and animals
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3.5 Strategies – backgrounds

This section elaborates on knowledge and materials available in relation to climate change adaptation and mitigation known to the case study. It should be noted that this case considers some of the adaptation and mitigation actions jointly, under the name ‘Mitigadaptation’, which is also one of the novelty this case study would like to address (see section 3.6 Expectations). Therefore, some of the relevant materials were not able to divide between adaptation- and mitigation-related materials, respectively. This is one of the challenges to be addressed within the WP6 and discuss respectively whether it can be applied to agroforestry sector only or would there be challenges also for other sectors in the same direction. Thus, unlike in other case studies, in this case the aspects of adaptation and mitigation are not given separately.

3.5.1 Available materials and knowledge: general

The LIFE Programme [14] is the EU’s funding instrument for the environment and climate action. Since 1992 the LIFE Programme has been investing in sustainable management and conservation of priority habitats and species across the European Union. As HNV agroecosystems Montados and Dehesas have not been left behind. A search in the LIFE public database [15] results in 15 large projects implemented in Montado and Dehesas agroecosystems with a total contribution from the EU of more than 22 million Euros.

“DEHESA/MONTADO & CLIMATE: A NEED TO ADAPT” (LIFEDEHESA/MONTADO-ADAPT) [16]. Project aim was to support adaptation and mitigation actions in Dehesa and Montado farms of Spain and Portugal to improve their economic, social and environmental sustainability.

Climate change mitigation and adaptation (CCMA), together with Nature and biodiversity, Circular economy and quality of life and Clean energy transition, are the new sub-programmes of the LIFE programme 2021-2027. The four sub-programmes are clearly interrelated, with CCMA becoming an ‘umbrella’ program cutting across the other sub-programmes. Substantial investments in CCMA are therefore expected in the coming years.

European Agroforestry Conference takes place every two years since 2012, where many topics, relevant for the adaptation and mitigation strategies are presented and discussed.

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The project **LIFE-Montado-adapt** [17] is a 5-year initiative, lasting from September 2016 to June 2022. It aimed to contribute to the EU climate policy priorities of “Climate Change Adaption” and, to a lesser extent, to “Climate Change Mitigation”. The overall objective was to demonstrate innovative adaption and mitigation practices and technologies and to ensure their replication among Montado and Dehesa (hereafter “M/D”) farmers in Portugal and Spain, and to help curb abandonment, socioeconomic decline and environmental degradation in M/D landscapes. The project offered new and/or improved methods, management practices and techniques that help restore the original vigour and resilience of these systems and their multifunctional properties, yielding benefits for people, the environment, biodiversity and climate. Besides introducing innovative techniques, new, lesser-used (but native to the region) species were promoted to ensure that the ecosystem maintains its resilience to climate change in the future and that help local communities meet changing market demands in the face of declining international demand for traditional products, with cork being the notable example. This was achieved, among others, by interplanting existing tree stands with new species that are known for their climate resilience (in this particular part of the world) as well as their productivity and market value. In that sense, a more holistic ecosystem approach was taken by placing land use into a larger framework of ecosystems management with a central role for local people and their interactions with the larger landscape. In summary, the project had two objectives:

1. Introducing innovative adaption technologies in Portuguese and Spanish M/D landscapes and communities, through demonstration of sustainable and profitable Integrated Land Use (ILU) systems that help restore the landscape’s multifunctional character and its contributions to socioeconomic development, environmental services, biodiversity conservation and carbon sequestration.

2. Maximizing the transformational impact of these adaptation technologies and ecosystem services and securing their replication and upscaling, through a farmer-to-farmer ILU adoption plan, developed commercialization channels, sustainability and carbon certification and a marketing plan for regional produce.

The project involved **5 dehesas in Spain (3 private and 2 public) and 7 montados in Portugal** which tested a range of adaptation and mitigation measures and techniques in a total area of 1,250 ha. The project also aspired to replicate the most successful adaptation and mitigation measures and techniques to an additional 120 M/D landowners. The actions, technologies and management practices promoted in the LIFE Montado-adapt project support both adaptation (ensuring that the land cover can deal with likely climate changes without major loss of function) and mitigation (reducing net emissions by enhancing terrestrial carbon storage). Adaptation and mitigation measures implemented include:

1. Productive and profitable tree crops (e.g., cork oak, chestnuts, almond trees, figs, and several other species);
2. Alternative agricultural crops (e.g., aromatics; red berries);
3. Fodder trees and shrubs (Cytisus proliferus, Celtis australis, Fraxinus angustifolia among others);
4. Improved pasture with leguminous grasses;

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5. Soil and water conservation practices (keyline, biochar use, tree planting on erosion hotspots);
6. Livelihood diversification: agrotourism, enterprise development (e.g., elaboration and commercialization of organic fertilizer; islands of vegetation for water bodies);
7. Diversification of tree species (tree and shrub hedgerows, tree planting);
8. Biodiversity promotion (nest boxes, insect hotels, melliferous plants for pollinators);
9. Promoting rotational grazing;
10. Promotion by planting and protection of natural regeneration.

LIFE DESERT-ADAPT [18] spanned from January 2017 to April 2022. It was an EU-funded project supporting mitigation and adaptation to climate change in Mediterranean ecosystems, including dehesas and montados. The Main Goal of the project was to demonstrate innovative climate adaption strategies and technologies to improve land quality, soil conservation and plant support for private and public lands in Mediterranean areas under desertification risk.

Other useful resources:

The European Climate Adaptation Platform **Climate-ADAPT** [19] is a partnership between the European Commission and the European Environment Agency (EEA). Climate-ADAPT is maintained by the EEA with the support of the European Topic Centre on Climate Change Impacts, Vulnerability and Adaptation (ETC/CCA).

Climate-ADAPT aims to support Europe in adapting to climate change helping users to access and share data and information on:

- Expected climate change in Europe;
- Current and future vulnerability of regions and sectors;
- EU, national and transnational adaptation strategies and actions;
- Adaptation case studies and potential adaptation options;
- Tools that support adaptation planning.

3.5.2 Available materials and knowledge: mitigation and adaptation related

The main mitigation- and adaptation-related actions, at landscape and farm level, respectively, in the Case Study are listed below and explained in detail in Table 33.

Mitigation and Adaptation strategies (landscape level)

- Afforestation/Reforestation;
- Establishment of new agroforestry areas;
- Forest grazing to reduce fire risk;
- Protection/increase of tree landscape features.

Mitigation and Adaptation measures (farm level)

- Tree planting and protection of natural regeneration Establishment of new agroforestry areas;
- Protection/increase of tree landscape features;
- Grassland management (legume overseeding) and pasture improvement;

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- Grassland management (rotational/adaptive grazing);
- Feed supplements and tree/shrub fodder;
- Farm bioenergy production/energy savings;
- Biochar production and/or use as fertilizer;
- Minimum tillage;
- Water management (keyline; erosion control);
- Wetland conservation/restoration (riparian vegetation);
- Biodiversity promotion;
- Farm business portfolio diversification (e.g., agrotourism).

Table 33: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation and adaptation

Aims/Issues	Climate mitigation and adaptation examples
Forestry sector 1. Nature based solutions (NBS), reforestation	Action taken: <i>Tree planting and protection of natural regeneration (densification, afforestation): tree shelters, nurse shrubs, irrigation support (only first summer after planting)</i> Level: implementational
Water and/or Biodiversity sectors 1. Water conservation and quality	Action taken: <i>Soil and water conservation practices (keyline, biochar use, soil retention)</i> Level: implementational
Biodiversity sector 1. Loss of biodiversity	Action taken: <i>Biodiversity promotion (nest boxes, insect hotels, melliferous plants for pollinators)</i> Level: implementational
Various sectors 1. Reducing vulnerability 2. Reducing animal stress 3. Preventing tree pests and diseases	Action taken: <i>Diversification (multipurpose trees and shrubs): Planting productive and profitable tree crops (e.g., almond, fig, etc.), alternative agricultural crops (e.g., aromatics; red berries), fodder trees and shrubs (e.g., Fraxinus angustifolia)</i> Level: implementational Action taken: <i>Animal feed and fodder based on rotational/adaptive grazing, pasture improvement, alternative tree crops</i> Level: implementational Action taken: <i>Tree pruning practices</i> Level: implementational

4. Erosion control, reduce compaction, enhanced fertility	Action taken: <i>Improved pasture with leguminous grasses</i> Level: implementational
5. Increase profitability through farm enterprise diversification	Action taken: <i>Farm enterprise diversification: agrotourism, enterprise development (e.g., elaboration and commercialization of organic fertilizer; islands of vegetation for water bodies)</i> Level: implementational

3.5.3 Quick facts

Table 34 lists documents with the contents relevant for the mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Table 34: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
LIFE public database [15]	Online: https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/search/advanced
DEHESA/MONTADO & CLIMATE: A NEED TO ADAPT [16]	Online: https://www.lifemontadoadapt.com/?l=en
LIFE-Montado-adapt [17]	Online: https://www.lifemontadoadapt.com/index.php
LIFE DESERT-ADAPT [18]	Online: http://www.desert-adapt.it/index.php/en/
The European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT [19]	Online: https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/about

3.6 Expectations of case study from DISTENDER

The DISTENDER project rests on the rationale that there is a real risk that climate funding may support initiatives that are actually harmful for the Montado/Dehesa socio-ecological systems, i.e., that may foster adaptation in the short-term, but insidiously affect the systems' long-term vulnerability and/or adaptive capacity to climate change. This generally defines "maladaptation", a process that results in increased vulnerability to climate variability and change, directly or indirectly, and/or significantly undermines capacities or opportunities for present and future adaptation.

DISTENDER affirms that avoiding maladaptation is a first key concrete step towards adaptation in a broader sense. With this in mind, it is therefore necessary, even imperative,

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to provide a Decision Support System (DSS) and tools that will guide the upcoming EU investments in appropriate and effective mitigation and adaptation measures across these sectors and that minimize the risk of ‘maladaptation’. DISTENDER will develop a case study in the agricultural sector by assessing the impacts and trade-offs of the project “Montado & Climate: A need to adapt” (LIFE-Montado-adapt) [17], a project on mitigation and adaptation to climate change in the montado and dehesa agroecosystems of the southwestern Iberian Peninsula.

In more detail, the Case Study expects from the DISTENDER project the **development of an evaluation framework** that will take into account driving forces of vulnerability and adaptation in Montado and Dehesa landscapes (e.g., the role of montado and dehesa agroecosystems, risk perception by landowners and local communities, policy incentives and barriers to mitigation and adaptation, etc.). We anticipate that the evaluation framework will rest on the following key concepts:

- a) ‘Mitigadaptation’ or the mitigation and adaptation capacity of implemented technologies, practices and measures.
- b) ‘Maladaptation’ or the process that results in increased vulnerability to climate variability and change, directly or indirectly, and/or significantly undermines capacities or opportunities for present and future adaptation, and;
- c) ‘Sustainagility’ or the capacity to allow farmers and landowners agility to adapt to climate change to continue developing their activity in the future.

The framework will strongly rely on the aim of avoiding irreversibility and strengthening Montado and Dehesa socioecological systems’ flexibility (sustainagility) to adapt to climate change. It will also consider how mitigadaptation, sustainagility and resilience aspects are influencing and affecting each other, in particular exploring trade-offs and synergies through biophysical and economic modelling (e.g., quantifying the carbon footprint of products; Life cycle assessment, etc.) to explore how individual mitigation and adaptation measures (e.g., afforestation, application of biochar, improved pastures, agroforestry, etc.) affect system resilience.

The evaluation of climate mitigation and adaptation options and their suitability under different conditions, and comparison of their trade-offs will pave the way to provide tailor-made recommendations to farmers on how to improve the resilience and adaptive capacity of the Dehesa and Montado systems and will help prevent and counteract poor agricultural management practices which leads to maladaptation, degradation and related loss of agroecosystem functioning.

3.7 References

[1] <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/>

[2] <https://www.juntaex.es/>

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[3] <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/high-nature-value-farmland-1>

[4] Case Study archive

[5] <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.884>

[6] <http://extremambiente.juntaex.es/files/INFORME%20AMBIENTAL%202019.pdf>

[7] <https://extremadura2030.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/estrategia2030.pdf>

[8] <https://extremadura2030.com/analisis-dafo/>

[9] <https://participaextremaduracircular.org/>

[10] <https://prodehesamontado.eu/>

[11] <https://agforward.eu/>

[12] https://www.eweb.unex.es/eweb/gic_eccomap/en/?PARTNER

[13]

https://www.eweb.unex.es/eweb/gic_eccomap/en/?RESULTS:Socioeconomic_Regionalization

[14] https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/life_en

[15] <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/search/advanced>

[16] <https://www.lifemontadoadapt.com/?l=en>

[17] <https://www.lifemontadoadapt.com/index.php>

[18] <http://www.desert-adapt.it/index.php/en/>

[19] <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/about>

[20] <https://extremadura2030.com/presentacion-estrategia/>

[21] <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/extremadura-2030-green-and-circular-economy-strategy-extremadura-2030>

[22] <https://extremadura2030.com/diagnostico-de-extremadura/>

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4 Case study 04: Guimarães (GUIMARAES)

4.1 General description

The case study of Guimarães is the only case study representing the municipal level.

4.1.1 Geography and Economics

Guimarães is a city and municipality located in northern Portugal, in the district of Braga (see area of interest in Figure 9). The Municipality covers a surface area of 241 km² and is divided in 48 parishes. In 2021, there were 156,852 inhabitants and its high population density reached 651 inhabitants/km² - with high percentage of young people. The city of Guimarães is one of the most important and relevant historical cities in Portugal, engaging its patrimony in urban landscape as a transformation tool in the territorial expansion. Its historic town centre has been listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site since 2001, in recognition for being an "exceptionally well-preserved and authentic example of the evolution of a medieval settlement into a modern town" in Europe. This makes it one of the largest touristic centres in the region.

The climate is temperate with Mediterranean characteristics and a strong Atlantic influence. Because it is near the sea (about 40 km away), the winter is normally cold and rainy, whilst the summer is warm and slightly more humid than the typical Mediterranean climate with Atlantic influence. The average annual temperature is about 14°C. However, relatively high annual thermal amplitudes occur due to its geographical location.

Guimarães is located in a valley and surrounded by hills, cut by three rivers from which, two of them, run in the periphery of the city and one through the city. The territory is very diverse, with agriculture developed in the lower parts and forests covering highest points of the territory. With successive population growth, normally associated with the industrial expansion, the city started to grow towards its periphery, with industry spaces and housing. Guimarães is one of the most industrial municipalities in Portugal. Its primary industries are textiles, shoe and metal industry.

4.1.2 Quick facts

Table 35 shows general, relevant information about the Guimarães Case Study, including the area of interest, defined for the purposes of the deliverable as that within their administrative boundaries, the population within the area, the main topographic features and the climate zones that it includes.

Table 35: Quick facts regarding general information

subject	information
Area of interest (size)	~241 km ²

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Population in area of interest	~157,000 Population density: ~651 inhabitants/km ²
Topography of area of interest	Valley surrounded by hills, cut with three rivers. The territory includes agriculture in the lower parts and forests covering highest points of the territory
Climate zone	Temperate climate with Mediterranean characteristics and a strong Atlantic influence
Economy	Guimarães is one of the most industrialised municipalities of Portugal (e.g., textiles, shoe and metal industries)

4.2 Participation and co-creation – background

This section addresses two aspects regarding stakeholders. Firstly, it refers to the stakeholders recognised by the case study as relevant. In this particular case, they are mostly recognised among various municipal departments or bodies and universities as knowledge providers. Secondly, responses of the case study on the questionnaire (see Annex I) are elaborated referring to case study familiarity to participatory approaches and its readiness for participation.

4.2.1 Stakeholders

The main stakeholders proposed by the partners from the Guimarães Case Study are listed and described:

- At the Guimarães local administration level, the themes of mitigation and adaptation are under the responsibility of different departments (Office of Energy Efficiency - Mitigation; Department of territory development - Adaptation). However, the collaboration of much of the municipal structure is essential to work on both themes namely, the departments and divisions of: Urban and environmental services, transport, municipal works and intelligent systems. Collaboration between departments is essential for the production and retrieval of data from the municipality and with them to produce relevant information. The Energy Efficiency Office, in charge of DISTENDER is, therefore, the recipient of the data produced in the different departments.
- In the municipal sphere, the local administration has the Landscape Laboratory, an institution constituted by the city council of Guimarães and two other universities that have as main activities Research and Development and environmental education. The landscape laboratory looks at all the projects in the environmental areas with interest and is therefore a stakeholder with an interest as an end user of the project.

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At the moment, a total of 47 stakeholders have been identified by the Case Study, of which 36 are external to the project. These stakeholders will importantly contribute to and also benefit from the work packages 3 (Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios), 4 (Downscaling climate scenarios) and 5 (Risk & Vulnerability assessment). About 7.57% of the stakeholders are seen as data providers, 19% as end users and 15% as expertise providers.

4.2.2 Quick facts

Tables 36-38 show general information about experiences and readiness of the Guimarães Case Study in terms of stakeholder knowledge, co-creation and participation.

Table 36: Quick facts regarding case study readiness

Case study readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you have experiences with stakeholders' participation?		X	
Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)?		X	
Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users?		X	
Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies?	X		
Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder's side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of?	*The CS did not provide this information.		

Table 37: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness

Stakeholder readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you know your stakeholder's readiness for participation?		X	
Is it easy for it to take action on an issue?		X	
Do you know your stakeholder knowledgeability?		X	

Table 38: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it

Case study involvement	Active participant	Preparation support	Organise/ implement

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Workshop	X		
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4.3 Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds

This section elaborates on the key concept of WP3 following the socio-economic scenarios as Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP). It shows only a very early stage of this concept application towards the case studies, as it has just started its run within the WP3.

4.3.1 Available materials and knowledge

The CS does not have any existing socioeconomic scenarios or Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) at the municipal level. However, they exist at the national level: SSPs can be found in **Cenários socioeconómicos de evolução do país no horizonte 2050** [1]. Regarding the socioeconomic scenarios on national level, many useful information can be found in the **Roadmap for Carbon Neutrality 2050 (RNC2050)** [2]. RNC2050 aims to explore the feasibility of trajectories leading to carbon neutrality in 2050, to identify the main vectors of decarbonisation and to estimate the potential for reduction of the various sectors of the national economy, such as energy and industry, mobility and transport, agriculture, forests and other land uses, waste and wastewater. RNC2050 suggests four areas of intervention, which will be based on three multifaced aspects. One of them are also socioeconomic scenarios [3].

Climate projections exist at the regional level (NUTS 2), where the region of Braga covers the Guimarães territory - **Climate Change Knowledge Portal** [4].

Furthermore, the CS operates with an extensive set of documents, which provide contents, directly or indirectly relevant for the development of socio-economic scenarios and are in this document provided in the section 4.5 Strategies – backgrounds.

4.3.2 Quick facts

Table 39 lists documents which directly address socioeconomic scenarios and SSPs, respectively. For the documents which indirectly encompass these topics, the reader is referred to Table 47.

Table 39: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
Roadmap for Carbon Neutrality 2050 (RNC2050) [2]	Online: https://descarbonizar2050.apambiente.pt/en/documents/
Cenários socioeconómicos de evolução do país no horizonte 2050 [1]	Online: https://descarbonizar2050.apambiente.pt/uploads/181220_Cenarios_RNC2050.pdf

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4.4 Models – backgrounds

This section addresses climate change impacts as recognised by the case study and provide the domains for models that are the subject of the DISTENDER project. In principle, four models are addressed HEALTH (including urban heat, air quality, health impacts), WATER, AFLOU (including agriculture, forestry, other land uses) and ENERGY.

4.4.1 Available materials and knowledge

Climate change impacts identified by the stakeholders of the Guimarães Case Study include:

- Droughts;
- Extreme temperature;
- Flooding (river overflow);
- Storms and strong winds;
- Extreme precipitation (rainstorm);
- Forest fires.

Information regarding current climatic characteristics as well as climate projections is available from different sources, however most of them is on regional or national level. For example, Weather Spark [5] provides information on climate and average weather year round in Guimarães. Furthermore, on the website of the World Bank Group [4], information on the current climate and climate projections can be found to the NUTS 2 level, which also includes the municipality of Guimarães.

According to available information, the locations in Guimarães that have been most affected by forest fires are those with the highest slopes. Exposures with greater incidence are in the south and east, close to bordering areas of the Municipality of Guimarães. In the north of the municipality, there is a significant representation of forest fires, originating from a large fuel load (bush), by the cessation of anthropic activities, such as, obtaining weeds for animal bedding and cutting firewood. In the north of the municipality of Guimarães exists a dense net of non-permanent watercourses that, in the summer season, are converted into complex areas of vegetation, allowing a vertical and horizontal continuity of fire, also contributing to increasing the impacted area.

4.4.2 Domains for simulation models

Here we show the model domains of the Guimarães Case Study. These are displayed in Figure 9, where the red box indicates the domain for meteorological and hydrological models (larger domain) and the domain where all modellers are required to provide results (domain

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level 1), the green box the areas with higher resolution in which all models are required to produce results (domain level 2) and the blue box domain level 3; see Tables 40-42 for details about the different model domains).

Figure 9 Model domains for the Case Study (red, green and blue boxes; see above text and Tables 40-42 for details)

Table 40. Characteristics relative to the larger domain of the Case Study (red box in Figure 9).

Larger domain characteristics	
Northern boundary	41.701477
Southern boundary	41.182889
Western boundary	-8.666000
Eastern boundary	-7.765000
Spatial resolution (°)	0.01
Approximate extent (km)	58 x 76

Table 41. Characteristics relative to the domain level 2 of the Case Study (green box in Figure 9).

Domain level 2 characteristics	
Northern boundary	41.592000
Southern boundary	41.349000
Western boundary	-8.462000
Eastern boundary	-8.130000
Spatial resolution (°)	0.005
Approximate extent (km)	28 x 27

Table 42. Characteristics relative to the domain level 3 of the Case Study (blue box in Figure 9).

Domain level 3 characteristics	
Northern boundary	41.462000
Southern boundary	41.415000
Western boundary	-8.373000

Eastern boundary	-8.256000
Spatial resolution (°)	0,001
Approximate extent (km)	10 x 6

4.4.3 Potential climate impacts and sectors of interest

In this section, the potential climate impacts as recognised by the case study are structured.

Table 43: Key characteristics of the Case Study

Related starting point	
Potential climate impact	<p>Droughts</p> <p>Extreme temperatures</p> <p>Flooding (river overflow)</p> <p>Storms and Strong winds</p> <p>Extreme precipitation (rainstorm)</p> <p>Forest fires</p>
Sectors directly affected	<p>Agriculture</p> <p>Water</p> <p>Heritage</p> <p>Business</p> <p>Energy</p> <p>Forestry</p> <p>Health</p>
Biophysical and/or economic impacts of the climate hazards commented in relation to the topics of models applied	<p>ENERGY: climate hazards could have an impact on the energy system in the city, especially the evolution of the mobility technologies and thus on energy consumption and emissions</p> <p>AFOLU (agriculture, forestry, other land uses): the relevance lies in carbon sequestration in adaptation to wildfires. Also, forestry sector is important in floods prevention</p> <p>WATER: flooding could cause river overflow and this may affect agriculture, heritage sites in the city, business, energy sector, and forestry. Droughts can cause forest fires and consequently impact mainly agriculture and forestry sectors but also heritage, business and energy. The Case Study would be particularly interested in water quality and flood protection</p>

HEALTH: the focus is on the impact of traffic on air quality

4.4.4 Quick facts

Table 44 shows sectors and models, as suggested by DISTENDER project, and their relation to the interests of the Case Study.

Table 44: Impact models, relevant for the Guimarães Case Study

SECTORS AND MODELS ADOPTED	Sub-sectors dealt with	CS interest in the sector	Explanation
HEALTH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SUEWS model</u> simulates radiation, energy and water balances • <u>ENVI-met</u> assesses the efficiency of mitigation actions • <u>URBAIR model</u> 	Urban heat	YES	Interested in impacts of extreme temperature effects on health
	Air quality	YES	Interested in air pollution effects on health due to road transportation and industry
	Health impacts	YES	Artificial lighting
ENERGY		YES	Interested in gaining insight into the change in vehicle type (no diesel, towards electric mobility), energy consumption regarding the industry (quite a lot, but is decreasing), domestic energy consumption (increasing) energy poverty
AFOLU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>YieldSAFE model</u> predicts plant growth, production 	Agriculture	YES	Interested in this sector mainly for forestry sub-sector, since 30-40% of the surface of the Case Study is covered by forests. The CS shows special interest in carbon sequestration, adaptation to wildfires
	Forestry		
	Other land use		
WATER <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SWAT model</u> calculates relevant water fluxes at the land surface, in the soil, groundwater and river. • <u>Economic assessment</u> evaluates the value of 	Flooding	YES	Interest in avoiding floods, especially in forest areas.
	Drought	YES	Interest in water scarcity, which is not a problem at the moment but, it could occur in the future since desertification is becoming an issue in the north of Portugal. Rivers are also of concern

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4.5 Strategies – backgrounds

This section elaborates on knowledge and materials available in relation to climate change adaptation and mitigation known to the case study.

4.5.1 Available materials and knowledge: general

The Municipality of Guimarães is a signatory to the Covenant of Mayor’s initiative [6] since November 2013, with the approval of the Action Plan for Sustainable Energy (PAES) and has joined to the new goals of the Covenant of Mayors for 2030 since 2016, submitting its Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP). Further, the Municipal Strategy to Climate Change Adaptation has been approved by Guimarães in 2016 and is currently being implemented. This strategy focusses on identifying planned adaptation options and actions that aim to promote the mitigation of the climate change effects. From the identification and prioritization of current climate vulnerabilities and risks as well as their projection until the end of the century, the municipality of Guimarães seeks to promote an integrated set of adaptation options to respond, not only to the future climate conditions, but also to different climatic impacts observed. The municipality also joined the 100 cities challenge with an aim to make them carbon neutral by 2030.

Apart of the above-mentioned documents, the Case Study operates with several strategic documents, action plans and projects which are planned or already implemented. In the continuation, the details about these documents are listed according to their mitigation- or adaptation-related purposes.

4.5.2 Available materials and knowledge: mitigation related

In this section, we present various documents which are relevant for mitigation-related strategies. The documents may encompass strategic documents, action plans or descriptions of implemented projects which the Case Study considered as relevant to contribute to the development of mitigation-related strategies.

Planned actions for mitigation

The main mitigation-related actions in the Case Study are related to the energy and transportation sectors. The details about specific actions, measures and documents are listed in Table 45.

Table 45: Current trends and actions taken regarding climate mitigation

Aims	Climate mitigation examples
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Energy sector	<p>Action taken: <i>Replacement of inefficient lighting equipment with other energy efficient ones, without compromising the population's demand and the quality of light, reflecting in a reduction of consumed energy and, consequently, a reduction in CO₂ emissions and energy bills</i></p>
1. Energy waste decrease	<p>Level: implementational</p> <p>Status of the action: <u>Implemented</u>: Sodium (VSAP) technology luminaires were replaced by LED technology; more than 10,000 VSAP technology luminaires were replaced by LED technology, which allows for savings in electricity consumption between 30 to 40%. Also 43 luminous flux regulators were installed in the public lightning circuit, allowing a reduction around 30%.</p> <p><u>Planned</u>: An intention to install a Smart Grid technology is currently in place. The purpose is to have control over the municipality lighting system and collect, at every instant, decision-making relevant data to ensure a detailed application of energy efficient measures and high-level maintenance notifications. So far, the municipality estimates to have 50% of its public lighting covered with LED technology. Regarding smart grid systems the aim is to select specific locations for its implementation in the future.</p>
2. Renewable energy increase	<p>Action taken: <i>Development of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) in industrial parks and in social housing neighbourhoods, installing PV solar power.</i></p> <p>Level: implementational</p> <p>Status of the action: So far there is no RECs in the municipality, the aim is to promote its creation in industrial areas and social housing. The industry is privately owned, and these private stakeholders are difficult to reach. However, there are some initiatives in place (see e.g., EUCF [7] investment concept).</p>
3. Improvement of building efficiency	<p>Action taken: <i>Implementation of energy efficiency (EE) measures and technologies in social housing neighbourhoods,</i> aiming to improve buildings efficiency, while improving life conditions of those in more adverse social contexts. This action covers households and consists of thermal insulation and replacement of equipment.</p> <p>Level: implementational</p> <p>Status of the action: There are already some renewables implemented in social housing buildings in the municipality. This has resulted in an improvement in the energy efficiency of 358 social housing units with an increase of 2 levels in the</p>

	efficiency class through the installation of thermal insulation, replacement of glazing and installation of solar thermal and photovoltaic systems
Transport sector 1. Reduction of the gas emissions	Action taken: <i>Installation of electric mobility charging stations across the RECs and the ECO Pathway of 50 km, as well as an integrated management system.</i> Level: implementational Status of the action: The implementation is increasing. In this context, DISTENDER's results will be of great interest for Guimarães

4.5.3 Available materials and knowledge: adaptation related

This section gathers strategic documents, action plans or descriptions of implemented projects which are relevant for adaptation-related strategies.

Planned actions for adaptation

The most relevant adaptation-related actions in the Case Study are listed below and explained in detail in Table 46.

The climate change adaptation strategy (“Estratégia Municipal de Adaptação às Alterações Climáticas, EMAAC) [8] evaluates and predicts the climate vulnerabilities of Guimarães territory. The main climate changes projected for the territory are:

- Decrease in average annual precipitation
- Increase in the average annual temperature, in special the maximum
- Decrease in the number of days of frost
- Increase in extreme precipitation phenomena

These changes could have several impacts on the territory, as well as on the natural and human systems that compose it. Even in the presence of responses based on planned adaptation to future climate scenarios, there will always be climate risks that will affect the municipality in multiple environmental, social, and economic aspects.

Further, the **Municipal Strategy to Climate Change Adaptation** has been approved by Guimarães in 2016 and is currently being implemented. This strategy focusses on identifying planned adaptation options and actions that aim to promote the mitigation of the climate change effects.

Flood Zones Projection map [9] shows hazardous areas of the territory which are likely to be flooded.

Municipal Plan for the Defence Against Forest Fires [10] seeks, at the municipal level, to satisfy the objectives and goals advocated in the five strategic axes:

Axe 1. Increased territory's resilience to forest fires;

Axe 2. Reduction of fire incidence actions;

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Axe 3. Improving fighting effectiveness and fire management;

Axe 4. Recover and rehabilitate ecosystems, and

Axe 5. Adaptation of a functional and effective organic structure defined.

The objectives and goals are organized according to their expected impact on solving the problems identified in each locality. Concrete actions within these axes range from creation and maintenance of networks of fuel management lanes, implementation of fuel management gaps and promotion of forestry actions within the scope of the forest defence, as well as pasture management actions, to dissemination of landscaping techniques with greater resilience to forest fires, development of awareness programs at the local level, aiming at target groups according to the risk behaviours, conduction of awareness sessions with shepherds focusing on areas where fire is recurrent, and definition of rehabilitation typologies to be applied in the areas identified in the assessment phase, promoting erosion control and protection of the hydrographic network, and defence of the most sensitive infrastructures, stations and dwellings, to name some of them.

Besides, among the adaptation measures, there are also activities foreseen for increase and promotion of urban green parks/areas for public use, such as a new **Eco pathway along the Ave River** [11] with a total length of 34 km and passing through 14 parishes, with new points of interest along the route, and promoting the contemplation of fauna and flora, and the valorisation of natural heritage and the approach to the river. Preserving the landscape integration of the entire riparian gallery is one of the predefined objectives of the project, allowing to consciously recover the existing routes and inform the population of the importance of preserving and promoting the biodiversity of Guimarães.

Retention Basins [12] are more implementation-oriented adaptation actions, where natural engineering is used to improve and maintain hydraulic function in water streams crossing urban areas. Such actions clearly indicate involvement of nature-based solutions in floods-related impacts.

Table 46: Current trends and action taken regarding climate adaptation

Issues	Climate adaptation examples
<p><i>Various sector</i></p> <p>1. Heat islands prevention</p> <p>2. Extreme natural events (forest fires disaster risk reduction)</p>	<p>Action taken: <i>Increase and promotion of urban green parks/areas for public use</i>, taking advantage of the cooling effect generated by trees and other plants, in densely populated areas</p> <p>Level: implementational</p> <p>Status of the action: Since approximately 2018, more than 0.53 km² of green parks/areas were created.</p> <p>Action taken: <i>The Municipal Plan for the Defence of the Forest Against Forest Fires (PMDFCI) followed</i>. Some actual actions such as: Annual management and cleaning is carried to create wood discontinuity, serving as a protection to the building and an opportunity to extinguish in case of</p>

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	<p>forest/rural fire; Creation of water points to fight against forest fires; Increasing human capital to fight fires Level: implementational and strategic Status of the action: Implemented and on-going</p>
<p>Water sector 3. Flooding</p> <p>4. Flooding</p>	<p>Actions taken: <i>Creation of retention basins using natural engineering to improve and maintain hydraulic function in water streams crossing urban areas creating a solution to prevent flooding in the lower areas.</i> This adaptation action consisted in the construction of three basins to control the water levels in a water stream named “Ribeira da Costa”, providing a solution to avoid flooding in low urban areas close to the stream sides Level: implementational Status of the action: <u>Implemented:</u> Yearly, more than about 2 million cubic meters are regulated, since the basins are provided with water level sensors and their gates can be remotely controlled. Every year, before the start of the hydrological year, several actions take place to prevent urban floods, including cleaning of gutters, clearing of obstruction courses water, cleaning of vegetation in the vegetable garden retention basins, as well as the public awareness and information campaign <u>Planned:</u> Special Plans for Prevention and Adaptation to floods are also currently in place</p> <p>Action taken: <i>Flood Zones Projection (Mapping) - GIS planning instrument that allows to anticipate the (re)actions in flood situations, including this knowledge in territorial management through the inclusion of the Municipal Master Plan</i> <i>Flood vulnerable areas can be previously identified, and their management may include the introduction of measures aimed at the soil characteristics, as well as the application of strategies for controlling problems at the source, in an integrated space management model</i> Level: strategic Status of the action: implemented</p>

4.5.4 Quick facts

Table 47 lists documents with the contents relevant for the mitigation and adaptation strategies.

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Table 47: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
The climate change adaptation strategy (EMAAC) [8]	Online: https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/municipio/camara-municipal/servicos/ambiente/estrategia-municipal-de-adaptacao-as-alteracoes-climaticas
Action Plan for Sustainable Energy (PAES), 2013	Case Study archive
Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP), 2016	Case Study archive
Municipal Strategy to Climate Change Adaptation, 2016	Case Study archive
Flood Zones Projection maps [9]	Online: https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/cmguimaraes/uploads/document/file/6192/j_Carta_das_zonas_inund_veis.pdf
Municipal Plan for the Defence Against Forest Fires [10]	Online: https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/municipio/camara-municipal/servicos/ambiente/gabinete-florestal/pmdfci
Guimaraes 2030 Biowaste Management Plan	Case Study archive

4.6 Expectations of case study from DISTENDER

The main expectations of the Guimarães Case Study can be summarised as follows:

- To compare future climate vulnerabilities identified for the municipality to those derived from the DISTENDER project.
- To use the DISTENDER results to evaluate (e.g., robustness, effectiveness, costs) the past, present and future climate actions in the municipality.
- To enhance the understanding regarding climate change actions, supported by the project's output, and with that, to make the best decisions (technically and politically) to overcome the climate change challenges.
- To verify which economic production sectors interfere the most with the environmental indicators, identified by the Municipality, compared to other cities.
- To promote the interaction with other cities and institutions, as well as to gain experience across the EU climate projects and network creation.
- To contribute to enhanced collaboration among climate action strategies, including taking social benefits from other cities' know-how.
- To gain project experience and transfer the results to other future projects and initiatives.
- To transfer scientific-based knowledge into climate change relevant policies.

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4.7 References

[1] https://descarbonizar2050.apambiente.pt/uploads/181220_Cenarios_RNC2050.pdf

[2] <https://descarbonizar2050.apambiente.pt/en/documents/>

[3] <https://descarbonizar2050.apambiente.pt/en/roadmap/socioeconomic-scenarios/>

[4] <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/portugal/climate-data-projections>

[5] <https://weatherspark.com/y/32437/Average-Weather-in-Guimar%C3%A3es-Portugal-Year-Round>

[6] <https://www.covenantofmayors.eu/>

[7] <https://www.eucityfacility.eu/home.html>

[8] https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/cmguimaraes/uploads/writer_file/document/7277/emaac_guimaraes.pdf
<https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/municipio/camara-municipal/servicos/ambiente/estrategia-municipal-de-adaptacao-as-alteracoes-climaticas>)

[9] https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/cmguimaraes/uploads/document/file/6192/j__Carta_das_zonas_inund_veis.pdf

[10] <https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/municipio/camara-municipal/servicos/ambiente/gabinete-florestal/pmdfci>)

[11] <https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/conhecer/noticia/ecovia-do-ave-liga-varias-freguesias-de-guimaraes-pelas-margens-do-rio>

[12] <https://www.cm-guimaraes.pt/participar/guimaraes-mais-verde/noticia/bacias-de-retencao-em-guimaraes-sao-exemplo-nacional-na-prevencao-de-cheias-em-meio-urbano>

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5 Case study 05: The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

5.1 General description

The metropolitan city of Turin is the most complex case in DISTENDER. It occupies a very heterogeneous territory, with significantly urbanised areas, from dense urban areas to small towns, but also incredible natural places, as well as considerable rural territories, spanning from the Alps to the basin of the river Po.

5.1.1 Geography and Economics

The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0) is a wide area (NUTS3), second level local authority which replaced the former Province of Turin from January 1st 2015 (see area of interest in Figure 11). CMT0 borders with France (Départements Savoie and Hautes Alpes), with the Valle d'Aosta Region, and with the provinces of Biella, Vercelli, Asti, Cuneo and Alessandria. CMT0 brings together 312 municipalities and is the largest metropolitan city in Italy (6,827 km²), fourth in population size (2.2 million inhabitants) and seventh in population density (330 inhabitants/km²). 40% of the population resides in the City of Turin (whose surface is equal to 2% of the total area of the CMT0); 80% of the municipalities have a population less than 5,000 inhabitants and 36% less than 1,000 inhabitants.

As stated above, it covers a very large and heterogeneous territory i.e., the urban pole of Turin City (almost 1 million inhabitants), the peri-urban area, part that is flat or hilly in the south and east, and the mountain region in the Alps to the west and north along the border with France and with the Valle d'Aosta. The split is around 52% of mountain territory, 27% of plains, 21% of hills. The highest point in the Metropolitan City of Turin is the Roc (4,026 m), located in the Gran Paradiso massif on the border with Valle d'Aosta. The southern end of the territory is marked by Monte Granero (3,171 m) in Valle Pellice, from which the ridge winds from south-east to north-west, over 3,000 m, reaches Punta Galisia (3,346 m) on the watershed between Italy and France. The westernmost point is at the head of the Susa Valley (extreme western Italy) in Gran Bagna, while the northernmost point is located near the Mombarone. To the east, the CMT0 borders the Provinces of Vercelli and Novara (River Po). A multiplicity of green and blue corridors crosses the CMT0, connecting the Alpine and Po Valley ecosystems.

The Po River is the main Italian natural watercourse (652 km). It originates on the side of the Monviso and crosses the entire metropolitan area. The main catchment areas are located on its left hydrographic bank and belong to the rivers of Dora Riparia and Dora Baltea and to smaller streams such as Chisola, Sangone, Stura di Lanzo, Malone, Orco, and Pellice. There are also numerous left tributaries of the Po and the canals that descend towards Turin from the hilly areas. Hundreds of small natural lakes are located near the great mountain formations (between 1,800 m and 2,800 m above sea level). The most significant natural basins such as Viverone Lake, Candia Lake, Piccolo and Grande Lakes of Avigliana, or Lake Sirio are in the plain or valley floor area. The plain is characterized by soils of high agronomic value, threatened by anthropic activity (urbanization and road infrastructures).

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The metropolitan city of Turin is a part of a larger urban region, spanning from Milan to Venice and reaching out the port city of Genoa, partially reinforced by the high-speed railway line. At the same time, the metropolitan city works as a large functional area but is also subdivided into six local labour systems (SLLs), defined by the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT). The largest of them is Turin with 112 municipalities. Although there is a strong concentration of economic activities and jobs around Turin and the surrounding municipalities of the first two belts, the other SLLs have specific and important economic specialisations as well. In the Turin SLL manufacturing activities represents a share of 22.4% (mainly work in service sectors), wholesale and retail trade 17.3%, professional, scientific and technical activities 9.1%, whereas administrative and support services 8.8%, and information and communication activities 6.8%. In most of the service sectors, employment grew between 2012 and 2017, especially accommodation and food services activities (+28.4%), human health and social work activities (+22.3%) and administrative and support services activities (+20.7%).

The decentralization of productive activities towards more peripheral areas has resulted in a large series of disused sites, particularly concentrated in the city of Turin (around 3.5 million squares meters), with an exacerbated dynamic in the last years, where the real estate has never been able to generate consistent demand for either residential or other economic uses. As such, the number of industrial abandoned areas grew exponentially, in particular in the city, but also in the metropolitan area. Despite this, actors emphasize that recently, speculative dynamics have tried to generate new land value offering new industrial sites, which still result empty. In terms of size, brownfields are in both urban and suburban areas, inside and outside Turin. Today, the exclusive recurring function that manages to occupy brownfields areas is logistics (or trade activities but in a smaller percentage). The manufacturing of the CMTo is characterized by a high number of specializations organized around the core of the advanced mechanics sector, with a production structure generating numerous opportunities for innovation, through connections and relationships between similar productions. However, the automotive sector accounts more than half of the overall manufacturing activities in the Turin area [1].

CMTo's climatic conditions are strongly influenced by the Alps. The protection afforded by the Alps is reflected in a weak and irregular windiness with average annual speeds ranging from about 5-6 km/h in the lowlands to approximately 10-15 km/h in some locations in the high Alpine valleys (11 km/h in Susa, 13 km/h in Oulx). Local gusts are limited to a few days a year and can be attributed to the Foehn, which, especially between autumn and spring, blows even over 100 km/h. The number of days with Foehn winds is quite high (about 65 per year), with a tendency to increase, especially in winter. In the mountains, there is an increase of about 1.7 days/year in the days with gusts above the 90th percentile of distribution (14.6 m/s). CMTo is part of the Piedmont Region, where the generalized acceleration trend of climate warming is confirmed. The increases concern both maximum temperatures (T_{max}) (approximately +2.1°C) and minimum temperatures (T_{min}) (approximately +1.5°C), with more acute levels of increase in mountain areas (T_{max} +2.5°C, T_{min} +1.8°C). For more information related to climate changes relevant for Turin, as well as other insights relevant to geographic information, see Annex IV.

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5.1.2 Quick facts

Table 48 shows general, relevant information about the case study of the Metropolitan city of Turin, including the area of interest, referring to the case study's administrative area or boundaries; the population within the area, the main topographic features, the climate zones that it includes, and main economic activity.

Table 48: Quick facts regarding general information

subject	information
Area of interest (size)	6,827 km ²
Population in area of interest	~2 million in the entire metropolitan area, ~860.000 inhabitants in the City of Turin
Topography of area of interest	It is a heterogeneous territory, with dense urban areas to peri-urban areas, part of that is flat or hilly in the south and east. There is a mountain region in the Alps to the west and north. The split is around 52% of mountain territory, 27% of plains, 21% of hills
Climate zone	Temperate climate, sub-continental type, which in the Alps becomes gradually temperate-cold and cold obviously going up with the altitude
Economy	Manufacturing (automotive sector), logistics, various services, retail

5.2 Participation and co-creation – background

This section addresses two aspects regarding stakeholders. Firstly, it refers to the stakeholders recognised by the case study as relevant. In this particular case, the activities of WP2 have shown that CMT0 elaborated quite a comprehensive list of stakeholders with a lot of details and concrete contacts. Secondly, responses of the case study on the questionnaire (see Annex I) are elaborated referring to case study familiarity to participatory approaches and its readiness for participation. The case study of the Metropolitan city of Turin proves to be confident in the field of stakeholders and participation.

5.2.1 Stakeholders

The main stakeholders proposed by the partners from the CMT0 Case Study are summarised in the chart provided by the Project Partner Smart Continent and was shown at the WP2 project partners meeting, September 16th 2022.

Figure 10 Structure of the stakeholders recognised by the case study CMT0 (source: Smart Continent, ppt presentation of WP2, UIRS, 2022)

Insights from T2.1 Progress report

Currently, a total of 87 stakeholders have been identified by the Metropolitan city of Turin, from which 61 are external to the DISTENDER project. The stakeholders are of importance for WP3 (Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios), WP4 (Downscaling climate scenarios), WP5 (Risk & Vulnerability assessment), WP6 (Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies), WP7 (Cost-benefits evaluation and impacts), WP8 (Decision Support System), WP9 (Case studies). About 11.24% of the stakeholders detected are expected to be end users, 18% of them data providers and 20% are expected to provide their expertise assistance.

5.2.2 Quick facts

Tables 49-51 show general information about the readiness of the case study of the Metropolitan city of Turin in terms of stakeholder knowledge, co-creation and participation.

Table 49: Quick facts regarding case study readiness

Case study readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you have experiences with stakeholders’ participation?		X	
Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)?	X		
Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users?			X
Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies?	X		

Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder's side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of?		X (must consider institutional rules)	
--	--	---------------------------------------	--

Table 50: Quick facts regarding stakeholder readiness

Stakeholder readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you know your stakeholder's readiness for participation?		X	
Is it easy for it to take action on an issue?		X	
Do you know your stakeholder knowledgeability?		X	

Table 51: Quick facts regarding familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it

Case study involvement	Active participant	Preparation support	Organise/ implement
Workshop	X		

5.3 Socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds

This section elaborates on the key concept of WP3 following the socio-economic scenarios as Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP). It shows only a very early stage of this concept application towards the case studies, as it has just started its run within the WP3. Selected focused projects or studies are summarised, justifying that detailed look into them can bring the focused info needed for the WP3.

5.3.1 Available materials and knowledge

The city of Turin has flourished consistently during the fifties and sixties of the 20th century with the automotive sector, this being largely due to the presence of the most important Italian car manufacturing, FIAT. In this period, work-related immigration mainly came from the south of Italy. The rest of the region has been an engine for growth, so that the city of Turin and metropolitan area have experienced for several decades a consistent trend of demographic growth. However, the reorganisation of the automotive sector and the economic crisis of the early seventies brought in a quite disruptive process of change, and the whole area was heavily affected both in economic and sociodemographic trends. In particular, it has been characterised by a progressive relocation of population from the city of Turin and the first belt municipalities, to the second and third belts, with a general movement of high classes to the hills and mountains, while working classes moved or remained stuck in the suburbs. In the background, the mountain arc kept shrinking demographically and in its already weak economic role. All in all, the city of Turin lost one

quarter of its population, while the surrounding municipalities kept growing of one third, generating a strong residential pressure. Within this framework the city started shrinking from both residential and industrial function, which has resulted in empty factories and abandoned manufacturing buildings mostly located in the central urban area.

Over the last two decades, after a short demographic recovery in the '90s - because of the progressive phenomenon of suburbanization, the increasing ageing population and the low birth rate - the city of Turin kept losing population (even if at a steady low increasing trend - 2%), while the surrounding municipalities kept growing at a higher trend [2]. Next to this, the more recent massive waves of immigration, mainly from North-African and Eastern Europe countries, have changed the social structure of the resident population. Recent studies have shown that in the city of Turin the incidence of the foreign population on the total population has increased in the last twenty years, from 3% in 1998 to 13% in 2008 and 15% in 2018. Currently, data reveals that the inflow and outflow are balanced and suggesting that the phase of expansion of the migration dynamic is coming to an end [2].

Today the metropolitan city of Turin is far from its "car monoculture" past and the "total embedding" dynamic exercised by FIAT, which has dictated the economic development of the whole area for decades [3]. However, the manufacturing activities still play a crucial role in the economy of the Turin SLL (accounting for the 22.4%), but employees mainly work in service sectors: 17.3% in wholesale and retail trade, 9.1% in professional, scientific and technical activities, 8.8% in administrative and support services activities, 6.8% in information and communication activities, etc. In most of the service sectors employment grew between 2012 and 2017, especially accommodation and food services activities (+28.4%), human health and social work activities (+22.3%) and administrative and support services activities (+20.7).

This generated a new concentration of job offer in the central city, partly contrasting the effects of deindustrialisation, and of new economic activities in the Susa Valley and around Turin. The haste to quickly abandon the industrial vocation of the area in favour of a "wannabe global city", however, has proved to be an "hyper-optimistic aspiration" when the area was struck by the global financial crisis in 2007 [3], [4]. The economic crisis of 2007 strongly hit the area, generating additional stress to its already fragilized manufacturing structure that has lived on the total dependence of the FIAT, and, consequently, has not been able to completely discard from its unique industrial vocation and heritage.

The case study outlined the preferred topic for scenarios:

- Consumption and soil waterproofing;
- Ecological functionality and forest area;
- Energy efficiency and district heating;
- Exploitation of water resources.

There is a challenge on how to frame these selected topics into the system of the SSPs. This will be addressed in WP3.

Activities conducted in recent years on its territory regarding climate change and environment are evident via various projects and studies, some also addressing socio-economic issues or aspects:

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1. Metropolitan strategic plan (PSM) [5] covering PLANNING TOOLS WIDESPREAD DEVELOPMENT AND REBALANCING BETWEEN LOWLAND AND MOUNTAIN AREAS

The PSM is the reference document (required by law) for the economic and sustainable development of the CMTo. The PSM is divided into 6 axes, which correspond to the 6 programmatic points envisaged by the Next Generation Europe program and to the 6 missions of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan. The axes are in turn divided into 24 strategies and take up some of the above actions (ecological network, adaptation to climate change). The future scenarios object of DISTENDER must therefore be consistent with the PSM and with the objectives it sets itself together with the plan below (GENERAL SPATIAL PLAN).

2. Metropolitan territorial plan (PTGM) [6] - GENERAL SPATIAL PLAN, which contains 5 MACRO OBJECTIVES, 8 MACRO STRATEGIES, and 100 ACTIONS.

The PTGM defines objectives, strategies and actions for the development of the metropolitan territory and “territorialises”, where possible and within its competence, the Strategic Framework of the PSM. The PTGM action areas are defined by law (Infrastructural system: urban residential, productive, metropolitan level roads; Metropolitan level green and protected area system). Attention to adaptation to climate change is a novelty that is now being included in the new plan being approved. The PTGM defines the general territorial framework of rules within which individual municipalities must implement / modify their local urban planning instruments. It can introduce binding prescriptions that municipalities must comply with, on topics of supra-local interest (e.g., climate change). It is hoped that the results of DISTENDER can be used to improve the PTGM and make it more effective.

The indications / standards of the PTGM can guide and influence the actions implemented by different sectors of the CMTo (transport, environment etc.).

Summarised from the sources listed in Table 52, Table 60 and in additional sources summarised in Annex IV, the most significant climate-change related issues identified for the MCTo and that shall be considered when developing socio-economic scenarios, are:

- Adaptation to extreme temperatures, flooding by land use planning using PTGM and by this address urban, agricultural, financial sectors. The aim is to preserve the capacity of soils for food and wood production; moderate the flow of water and filter the water; and regulate the microclimate in urban environment;
- Adaptation to droughts, extreme temperatures, flooding, water scarcity, which affect decline of species and ecosystems and alteration of natural system by nature-based solutions (NBS), reforestation, land use planning, using planning tool: CIRCA Catalogue – PTGM to improve the ecological functionality and water management during periods of drought (see more in Annex IV);
- Mitigation to droughts, extreme temperatures, flooding, air pollution, water scarcity that cause decline of species and ecosystems and alteration of natural system, and for improvement measures based on NBS, reforestation, and land use planning (CIRCA Catalogue – PTGM) to enhance biodiversity, achieve ecological functionality and increased CO₂ absorption, as well as improvement of water management during periods of drought are suggested;
- Mitigation towards energy efficiency with environmental permits.

5.3.2 Quick facts

Table 52 lists the documents relevant to form socio-economic scenarios.

Table 52: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
Metropolitan Ecological Network	Case study archive: Metropolitan Spatial Plan – PTGM: maps + documents (1:100.000)
Catalogue for environmental compensation CIRCA	Case study archive: Catalogue: Database + maps
Regional strategy for climate change and Agenda for sustainable development	Case study archive
Metropolitan strategic plan [5]	Online: http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/risorse/sviluppo-economico/dwd/psm/PSM_2021-2023_finale.pdf
Metropolitan territorial plan [6]	Online: Metropolitan Spatial Plan - PTGM (with map): maps + database (1:100.000) http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/territorio-urbanistica/ufficio-di-piano/ufficio-di-piano

5.4 Models – backgrounds

This section addresses climate change impacts as recognised by the case study and provide the domains for models that are the subject of the DISTENDER project. In principle, four models are addressed HEALTH (including urban heat, air quality, health impacts), WATER, AFLOU (including agriculture, forestry, other land uses) and ENERGY.

5.4.1 Available materials and knowledge

Summarised from the sources listed in Table 52, Table 60 and in additional sources summarised in Annex IV, an overview of the expected risks from climate change for the case study of the Metropolitan city of Turin, as indicated by the partners, reflects the following:

Main expected effects related to warming:

- Intensification of extreme heat waves;
- Extension of the ranges of spread of insect pests and pathogen vectors;
- Weakening of vegetation (crashing, drying up, alteration of growth rates etc.);
- Onset of arid situations and decrease in soil productive capacity (increase in evapotranspiration, alteration of structure, due to changes in tree cover composition and structure);

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- Decrease in water reserves (due to melting of glaciers whose surface area, in the province, could almost disappear in 2050);
- Destabilization of high-altitude slopes (increase in landslides and possible damage to infrastructure, mountain huts, ski lifts, due to thawing of permafrost);
- Increase in forest fires.

Main expected effects for changes in snowfall precipitation:

- Changes in the hydrological regime (influence on runoff times, flood flow formation- especially during heavy winter and spring rainfall events);
- Severe flow transit difficulties in riverbeds and "debris flow", in areas at high elevations, with not infrequently destructive effects;
- Changed flow regime, with anticipation of the late-spring soft period (now assessable on average in about 15 days);
- Thawing of permafrost, with possible negative effects on stability of high-altitude infrastructure above 2,700 m (alpine huts, ski lifts);
- Problems to winter tourism (alpine skiing).

Main expected effects for changes in the rainfall regime:

- Decreased availability of the water resource;
- Changes in river regimes and floods;
- Increase in forest fires;
- Hydrogeological instability;
- Changes in groundwater levels.

Extreme events:

In recently deglaciated high-altitude areas, there is a large increase in loose sediment that can be mobilized along streams during intense precipitation. Especially summer events, mostly localized and very intense, cause increasingly severe effects (also due to different land use than in the past). The phenomenon of flooding is aggravated by the poor maintenance to which the territory is subjected: this is evident in the hillside area of Turin, where an accelerated process of slope occupation without adequate infrastructure causes inconveniences and sometimes tragedies destined to be increasingly frequent if the current climatic processes continue (e.g., San Raffaele Cimena landslide of November 6, 1994). Without assuming a further increase in instances of heavy rainfall, even at high altitudes, erosion and transport of incoherent moraine deposits released by retreating glaciers, as well as flood flows in the cold semester and intermediate seasons, may increase. In the mountain environment, hydrological aspects are complicated by the interaction with slope instabilities and solid transport, which cause severe damage to infrastructure and can result in destruction and bereavement. The poor predictability of such phenomena, which develop in a very short time frame (a few minutes) even following very localized downpours, calls for a rethink on building management (strict regulations and effective relocation policies to prevent new construction in the areas at greatest risk). An increasing trend in economic losses is evident, related to the increase in assets exposed to risk from river floods, torrential floods with concomitant solid transport events, slope instability, etc.

Cumulative effects:

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The effects of climate change are likely to adversely affect the health and dynamics of natural ecosystems and human systems: agriculture, forests, natural ecosystems, alpine tourism, slope stability, the safety of humans and their artifacts, energy production, and the possibility of future land development. Already, the ongoing extinction of several species is attributed to global warming. A significant reduction in biodiversity is expected in the Alps during the 21st century, with about 50% of living species threatened with extinction. Exacerbating the crisis may be the shortage of fossil energy that today fuels the production of fertilizers and pesticides essential to ensure high crop yields. Changes in climate and rainfall patterns, the triggering of hydrogeological disruption phenomena, loss of agricultural productivity, and altered food chains, compounded by the pressing search for new deposits of fossil energy sources and raw materials, which are increasingly scarce, introduce a future scenario that is likely to be marked by increasing conflict at the global and local levels.

Main expected affects by cumulative effects:

- Reduction in the availability of water for drinking and non-drinking uses;
- Reduction in biodiversity;
- Loss of agricultural productivity and food crisis;
- Human migration and increased conflict;
- Increased sea level;
- Spread of pests and diseases.

5.4.2 Domains for simulation models

Here we show the model domains of the Metropolitan City of Turin Case Study. These are displayed in Figure 11 where the black box indicates the domain for meteorological and hydrological models (larger domain), the red box the domain where all modellers have to provide results (domain level 1), and the blue box the areas with higher resolution in which urban heat model has to produce results (domain level 2; see Tables 53-55 for details about the different model domains).

Figure 11 Model domains for the Case Study (black, red and blue boxes; see above text and Tables 53-55 for details)

Table 53. Characteristics relative to the larger model domain of the Case Study (black box in Figure 11).

Larger domain characteristics	
Northern boundary	45.997065
Southern boundary	44.121578
Western boundary	6.371770
Eastern boundary	8.744733
Spatial resolution (°)	0.03
Approximate extent (km)	189 x 209

Table 54. Characteristics relative to the model domain level 1 of the Case Study (red box in Figure x11).

Domain level 1 characteristics	
Northern boundary	45.650000
Southern boundary	44.670000
Western boundary	6.500000
Eastern boundary	8.200000
Spatial resolution (°)	0.01
Approximate extent (km)	131 x 110

Table 55. Characteristics relative to the domain level 2 of the Case Study (blue box in Figure 11).

Domain level 2 characteristics	
Northern boundary	45.293150
Southern boundary	44.835000
Western boundary	7.366611
Eastern boundary	8.011350
Spatial resolution (°)	0.005
Approximate extent (km)	51 x 52

5.4.3 Potential climate impact and sectors of interest

In this section, the potential climate impacts as recognised by the case study are structured.

Table 56: Key characteristics of the Case Study

Related starting point	
Potential climate impact	Extreme temperatures Flooding Droughts Water scarcity Air pollution Forest fires
Sectors directly affected	Environment

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	Agriculture Forestry Water management Economic
Sectors indirectly affected/involved	Health Society Tourism Food Energy
Biophysical and/or economic impacts of the climate hazards aspects of interest to the CS	<p>AFOLU (agriculture, forestry, other land uses): droughts and water scarcity on the fertile soil could affect ecosystem services with the concomitant economic losses. MCTo is planning to plant about 100 ha of forest in the flatlands of the territory. The questions that arise are whether this measure could contribute to mitigation, increase the resilience of the territory or to what extent these types of actions should be incremented to have a significant impact</p> <p>WATER: CMTo releases the derivation permits for the use of surface water (hydroelectric and agricultural use). This type of competence can be used to satisfy different expectations of the territory (energy production, agricultural production, biodiversity protection etc.). To approach this issue the case study proposes a development of a case study within the case study</p> <p>HEALTH: heat island may affect population distribution. CMTo is also interested in heat effects on O₃ and CO₂ which is included in the air quality assessments</p> <p>ENERGY: to reduce GHG emissions and improve air quality in the MCTo, alternatives to the use of methane to heat the city should be assessed</p>

More specifically:

Risk of	Risk for
Droughts	Health Water supply Agriculture (soil-food) Forest fire Biodiversity

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Extreme temperatures	Health Forest fire Energy supply
Flooding	Population Buildings Infrastructure
Water scarcity	Health Water supply Food Energy
Air pollution	Health

5.4.4 Quick facts

Table 57 shows sectors and models, as suggested by DISTENDER project, and their relation to the interests of the Case Study.

Table 57: Impact models, relevant for the CMT0 case study

SECTORS AND MODELS ADOPTED	Sub-sectors dealt with	CS interest in the sector	Explanation
HEALT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SUEWS model</u> simulates radiation, energy and water balances • <u>ENVI-met</u> assesses the efficiency of mitigation actions • <u>URBAIR model</u> 	Urban heat	YES	Interest in identifying urban green infrastructures that could mitigate the heat impact, as well as the influence of heat impact on demography
	Air quality	YES	Interest in the % of deaths caused by heat and air pollution, considering the aging rate
	Health impacts	YES	Interest in the impact of pollutants emission; % CO ₂ adsorbing from urban green infrastructure related to the amount of emission
ENERGY		YES	Interest of climate hazards on the energy sector

AFOLU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>YieldSAFE model</u> predicts plant growth, production 	Agriculture Forestry Other land use	YES	Interest in gaining insights into the effects of droughts, water scarcity and wildfires on crops
WATER <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>SWAT model</u> calculates relevant water fluxes at the land surface, in the soil, groundwater and river 	Flooding	YES	Interest in a small and detailed case study to understand if its competence could be used to manage the territory
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Economic assessment</u> evaluates the value of water sector climate change impacts 	Drought	YES	Interest in gaining insights into the effects of droughts, water scarcity and wildfires on crops

5.5 Strategies – backgrounds

5.5.1 Available materials and knowledge: general

In this section existing strategies that address climate change adaptation and/or mitigation or related topics as well as studies addressing them are listed.

ARTACLIM Adaptation and resilience of Alpine territories to climate change - ALCOTRA Project [7]

The project focused on a portion of the CMTo (Pinerolese) territory comprising 45 of the 312 municipalities (132,000 inhabitants, 20% of the total area of the CMTo). A study addressing climate change was carried out related to the following sectors: agriculture, forests, biodiversity, tourism and settlement system and on the basis of this, proposals for adaptation actions to climate change were identified to be adopted within the planning tools at metropolitan and local level. The proposals for adaptation actions are being considered in defining the strategies of DISTENDER.

Regional strategy for climate change and Agenda for sustainable development

The preparation by the Piedmont Region of the Regional Strategy on Climate Change (SRCC) is the first component, by the institution, of the implementation of the National Sustainable Development Strategy – therefore, also of the Regional Sustainable Development Strategy (SRSvS). The Strategy is the tool through which Piedmont intends to contribute to actions to combat climate change and cope with the resulting emergency by aligning itself with the goals of Objective 13 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development: "Fight against climate change". The strategy aims to become the tool to refer to for integrating and aligning sector plans and programs to mitigation and adaptation policies (mainstreaming process). The strategy is being defined (the first excerpt was approved in February 2022) The future scenarios outlined in DISTENDER must be consistent, for CMTo with this strategy. For further reading, see references [8], [9], [10], [11].

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The CMTo has available 4 relevant strategies:

1. Strategy for CONTRASTING CONSUMPTION AND SOIL WATERPROOFING,

The PTGM requires all municipalities to zonate their territory by identifying “densely built areas” (in these it is allowed to build new buildings, in compliance with the maximum legal thresholds), “free areas” (in which any type of new building is prohibited, except in particular cases of public works), “transition areas” (i.e. areas already compromised with anthropogenic activity, on the edge of dense areas, where possibly to build to improve the design of the existing building), “free areas included in the built areas” (in which it is possible to build/densify the already built, but it is recommended to evaluate its role in terms of urban green or public spaces for adaptation to climate change).

The goal is for the municipalities to prepare their own regulatory plans limiting new buildings as much as possible (to be contained in any case within the perimeters of dense areas) and to protect and keep all alters free. This cannot be imposed on them, but the PTGM can impose the above zoning, response to which the municipalities must reason and with respect to which they must provide adequate reasons to CMTo and the Region, when they decide not to respect it. The ultimate aim is to reach a net consumption equal to 0 by 2050. CMTo provides municipalities with an initial zoning (dense, free, transition, etc.) on a metropolitan scale, which the municipalities are then required to verify at the local scale. For further reading see Annex IV.

2. Strategy to IMPROVE ECOLOGICAL FUNCTIONALITY & INCREASE FOREST AREAS,

The CMTo has foreseen an ecological network project which includes the establishment of some new protected areas, the implementation of the CIRCA catalogue, the forestation of urban areas. The final goal is to bring the allocation of green areas to 45 m²/inhabitant in the urban areas and to implement the general design of an ecological network including the recovery of the CIRCA areas, to protect and increase biodiversity and contribute to counteracting the negative effects of climate change.

3. Strategy to RATIONALIZE THE EXPLOITATION OF WATER RESOURCES,

The problem of water scarcity, in particular for agricultural use, has been increasingly felt in recent years, despite the presence of mountains and numerous waterways. CMTo, which is responsible for authorizing the withdrawal from surface water bodies for hydroelectric use, has for some time been thinking of redefining the maximum thresholds that can be authorized for surface water derivation concessions, due to the multiple uses of the resource. The aim is to ensure a balanced availability of water for hydroelectricity, agriculture and for the protection of biodiversity.

4. Strategy for ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND DISTRICT HEATING,

Turin has a large-size district heating network which provides heat more than 50% of the overall city heating volume. The heat produced in the system is generated by high-efficiency natural gas-fired combined cycles power plants. The largest part of the energy supply is produced by three combined heat and power (CHP) plants located in Turin (1) and Moncalieri (2), which provide approximately 95% of the annual thermal energy demand with an average overall efficiency equal to 74%. Integration gas-fired boilers and thermal storage systems are used during peak hours and to optimise the overall system performance.

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Thanks to the use of CHP plants, the district heating (DH) network has always been considered more efficient than the separate production of heat and electricity, and an additional advantage in comparison with individual gas boilers is related to the higher effectiveness in filtering pollutants emissions, especially NO_x.

5.5.2 Available materials and knowledge: mitigation related

Mitigation measures for energy efficiency are addressed via environmental permits. NBS and reforestation, plans using the CIRCA Catalogue, will enhance biodiversity to achieve ecological functionality and increased CO₂ absorption.

Planned actions for mitigation

The main mitigation-related actions in the Case Study are listed below and explained in detail in Table 58. Additional in-depth information is available in Annex IV.

Table 58: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation

Aims	Climate mitigation examples
Energy sector 1. Energy efficiency	Action taken: <i>Planning tool: Environmental permits. Implementation of the Memorandum of understanding for the district heating development, to improve air quality and energy efficiency</i> Level: implementational Status of the action: ongoing
Various sectors 4. Response to droughts, extreme temperatures, flooding, air pollution	Actions taken: <i>Reforestation: Increasing forestry surface in lowland areas to achieve increased CO₂ absorption, improved air quality; facing decline of species and ecosystems. Using planning tools: CIRCA Catalogue – PTGM, PSM, NRRP - Next generation EU</i> Level: implementational Status of the action: ongoing Comments: the measure is needed because of a decline of species and ecosystems and alteration of natural system

5.5.3 Available materials and knowledge: adaptation related

Adaptation measures are identified for extreme temperatures, and flooding and will be taken at the strategic level by land use planning using PTGM, addressing especially urban, agricultural and financial sectors. The aim is to preserve the capacity of soils for food and wood production; moderate the flow of water and filter the water; and regulate the microclimate in urban environment. To improve the ecological functionality and water

management during periods of drought, PTGM will be followed taking actions using NBS and reforestations, for example.

Planned actions for adaptation

The most relevant adaptation-related actions in the Case Study are listed below and explained in detail in Table 59. Additional in-depth information is available in Annex IV.

Table 59: Current trends and action taken regarding climate adaptation

Issues	Climate adaptation examples
Various sector 1. Extreme temperatures, flooding	<p>Action taken: <i>Land use planning</i>: Identify (in the municipal regulatory plans):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "dense" urban areas – new buildings are possible - "transition areas" – limited extensions are possible to complete the urban design - "free areas" – new construction is not allowed <p>Level: strategic within the entire CMTo Status of the action: ongoing</p>
2. Droughts, extreme temperatures, flooding, water scarcity	<p>Action taken: <i>Census and rehabilitation of degraded area or in need of preservation</i> (Catalogue of Environmentally Compensating Redevelopment Interventions (CIRCA)).</p> <p>Comments: the measure is needed because of a decline of species and ecosystems and alteration of natural system</p>
3. Droughts, water scarcity	<p>Action taken: <i>Guarantee hydric resources availability for agriculture</i></p> <p>Comments: the measure is needed to improve water management during periods of drought</p>

5.5.4 Quick facts

Table 60 lists documents with the contents relevant for the mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Table 60: Quick facts on relevant documents available

Document	Availability
ARTACLIM Adaptation and resilience of Alpine territories to climate change [7]	http://artaclim.eu/index.php/it/

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Metropolitan Ecological Network	Case study archive: Metropolitan Spatial Plan – PTGM: maps + documents (1:100.000)
Catalogue for environmental compensation CIRCA	Case study archive: Catalogue: Database + maps
Regional strategy for climate change and Agenda for sustainable development	Case study archive
Metropolitan strategic plan [5]	Online: http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/risorse/sviluppo-economico/dwd/psm/PSM_2021-2023_finale.pdf
Metropolitan territorial plan [6]	Online: Metropolitan Spatial Plan - PTGM (with map): pdf file + maps + database (1:100.000) http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/territorio-urbanistica/ufficio-di-piano/ufficio-di-piano
Strategy for CONTRASTING CONSUMPTION AND SOIL WATERPROOFING	Case study archive: PTGM + Guidelines: pdf + maps (1:100.000)
Strategy for IMPROVE ECOLOGICAL FUNCTIONALITY & INCREASE FOREST AREAS	Case study archive: PTGM + Guidelines + DOSSIER (forestation): pdf file + maps + database (1:100.000)
Strategy for RATIONALIZE THE EXPLOITATION OF WATER RESOURCES	Case study archive
Strategy for ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND DISTRICT HEATING	Case study archive

5.6 Expectations of case study from DISTENDER

The expectations of the Metropolitan city of Turin originated from its complex territorial and functional situations and are very much linked to support of spatial planning and decision making. They are expecting to use the project-derived knowledge to:

- Plan and manage adaptation and mitigation strategies deriving from transformation and use of the territory;
- Verify the effectiveness in terms of adaptation and mitigation measures and their interactions (synergies and trade-offs);
- Implement, in particular, spatial and urban planning;
- Improve the sustainability of the territory, increasing its climatic resilience, considering the differences and specificities of the territories of the CMT0 (plains, mountains, hills, urban and rural areas);
- Transfer the acquired knowledge to the local territorial bodies.

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5.7 References

- [1] http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/risorse/territorio/dwd/urbanistica/ProgEurop/Annex_3.4_Case_Study_Turin.pdf
- [2] <https://www.rapporto-rota.it/rapporti-su-torino/2019-futuro-rinviato.html>
- [3] <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccs.2015.01.003>
- [4] <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781446288948>
- [5] http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/risorse/sviluppo-economico/dwd/psm/PSM_2021-2023_finale.pdf
- [6] <http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/territorio-urbanistica/ufficio-di-piano/ufficio-di-piano>
- [7] <http://www.artaclim.eu/index.php/it/>
- [8] <http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/ambiente/agenda-metro-svil-sostenibile/percorso-cmto>
- [9] http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/risorse/ambiente/dwd/agenda-metropolitana/ASvSCmTo_documento_orientamenti.pdf
- [10] https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/sites/default/files/media/documenti/2022-02/010601_allegato_dgr_220217_h.pdf
- [11] https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/sites/default/files/media/documenti/2020-12/srcc_doc_visione.pdf

6 Conclusions

6.1 Discussion

This valuable document emerged at the very initial stage of the project. It is a result of an iterative process which included multiple discussions, predominately bilateral conversations with case studies' representatives, updated with the information resulting from the focussed online-workshops, as stated in the Introduction. Thus, on the one hand, the document shows mostly the case studies' reflection on the project and provides relevant insights from their point of view. On the other hand, the document frames case studies' perspectives and gives key input to the knowledge partners from other work packages (e.g., WP3, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8) as to how to include this information as a baseline of the project from the applicative point of view.

Some of the information contained in this piece of work may be subjected, as it is natural, to changes along the project's life. For example, in the case of dehesa and montado, in section Strategies – backgrounds mitigation and adaptation measures were addressed at once (not separately as in other cases), and relationally in the section Expectations several merged concepts were exposed to be looked at (e.g., mitigadaptation, maladaptation, sustainability), as some of the results, that may interest them. This seems interesting for discussion at least in the context of WP6. Also, their interest in the currently selected climate impacts may change once model results are available, as well as their strategies once they are aware of their potential synergies and trade-offs.

Case studies involved address one or more climate adaptation and mitigation issues related to several sectors i.e., health, energy, agriculture and forestry, or water. However, they are very diverse in terms of scale, climate conditions and impacts exposure. Therefore, although generally they may address similar topics, when dealing with how to search for solutions, the approaches may differ greatly, as they may be scale related. Accordingly, there can be three groups of case studies recognised: 1. National, 2. Regional, and 3. Local (see Table 61).

Table 61: Quick facts regarding case study scale-related characteristics

Case study	National level	Regional level	Local level
01: Austria (BMK)	X		
02: The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)		X	
03: Dehesa (Spain) and montado (Portugal) (EURAF)		X	
04: Guimarães (GUIMARAES)			X
05: The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)		X	X

In this respect, the scale, territorial characteristics, climate-change related issues, possible adaptation and/or mitigation strategies in each case study is of key importance for the

followers. This serves the follower case studies to orient themselves as to which case study and/or which issues and related measures to closely follow. To provide an overview, the case studies identified the interest in the sectors shown in Table 62.

Table 62: Quick facts regarding case study interest for the climate impacts with references to the proposed models

CASE STUDIES		01: Austria	02: the NE of the Netherlands	03: dehesas/ montados	04: Guimarães	05: CMTo
SECTORS	subsector					
HEALTH	Urban heat	/	/	/	X	X
	Air quality	X	/	/	X	X
	Health impact	X	/	/	X	X
ENERGY			X		X	X
AFOLU	agriculture	(x)	X	X	/	X
	forestry	(x)	(x)	X	X	/
	other land use	(x)	(x)	X	/	/
WATER	flooding	X	X	/	X	X
	drought		X	X	X	X

Note: (x) indicates optional or indirectly interested, / indicates not interest

6.1.1 Relations to the followers

The partners representing follower case studies have been present at the meetings with the core case studies. Thus, they had a chance to follow the discussion and the process of development of this document. In the process of creation of this document, they were asked the following:

- To indicate which core case study (Austria, the NE of The Netherlands, dehesa and montado, Metropolitan City of Turin, Municipality of Guimarães) they would like to follow, and
- If they cannot indicate a given case study, they should let us know which issues indicated and addressed by the models at hand (health; energy; water; agro-forestry), would be of their interest.

The followers of Nova Gorica, Alcorcon, Lviv, Valencia, Gdansk and Miškolc indicated the case studies to follow (see Table 63) with the following arguments:

- Nova Gorica: Metropolitan City of Turin or Municipality of Guimarães, as they see themselves facing similar issues addressing air quality, floods, also droughts. Alternatively, when addressing wider landscapes, they could have an interest in dehesa and montado.

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- Alcorcon: Municipality of Guimarães, as both cities Alcorcon and Guimarães are quite similar, and this city would be more interesting for them.
- Valencia: the most relevant case study for Valencia could be the Metropolitan City of Turin, so they would like to follow it.
- Lviv: The most interesting for them are air quality, urban heat islands, and energy in models. Municipality of Guimarães will be the best option for them.
- Miškolc: Miškolc will follow all core case studies.
- Gdansk: Gdansk will follow all core case studies.

Table 63: Matching table about the quick facts regarding case studies' related characteristics and interests of the followers

CASE STUDIES	01: Austria	02: the NE of the Netherlands	03: dehesas/ montados	04: Guimarães	05: CMT0
<i>Nova Gorica (GOLEA)</i>			(x)	x	x
<i>Alcorcon (ALCORCON)</i>				x	
<i>Lviv (LVIV)</i>				x	
<i>Valencia (VCE)</i>					x
<i>Miškolc (MISKOLC)</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Gdansk (GDANSK)</i>	x	x	x	x	x

(x) potentially for landscape characteristic areas

6.2 Final remarks

A solid conclusion from this document is that the case studies are highly knowledgeable about their current situation. Also, they are aware of the existence of various relevant documents which so far have been produced to address some of the issues central to DISTENDER. Provided information was framed into six sections addressing: general information, participation and co-creation - backgrounds, socio-economic scenarios – backgrounds, models – backgrounds, strategies – backgrounds, and expectations, which represent a baseline for the project. However, for each of the topics addressed via its dedicated work package, further steps will be elaborated within the corresponding work packages. Detailed further shaping of the key questions addressed will help to further distil the information from the available materials provided by the case studies, and so will the detailed frames relevant for each model need to be finalised between the case studies and the model providers in the next steps of the process.

This initial analysis also highlights that the followers mostly orient themselves on the combination of climate-change related issues and the scale-related aspects. Also, this shall be born in mind in further development of the project.

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Annexes

Annex I: Questionnaire: Case Study Description

INTRODUCTION

Objectives of T 9.1 (Development and planning of the case studies) according to the Project Management Plan are:

1. Planning, and set-up of the case studies
2. Set-up relationships of the core case studies with followers.
3. Set-up the definition of the cases, which includes the establishment of an area of interest in which to apply the models (requiring a collaboration and agreement with WP4 and WP5)
4. Outline the co-creation actions to achieve priorities for application of adaptation and mitigation strategies for each location (requiring collaboration and agreement with WP6 and WP2)
5. Outline the co-creation actions to co-develop future localized socio-economic scenarios (requiring collaboration and agreement with WP3 and WP2)

T 9.1 is divided into two consecutive sub-tasks (with little overlap):

T 9.1.1 Definition of Case Studies (1.6.2022 – 30.10.2022)

T 9.1.2 Participation to co-develop socio-economic scenarios (1.2.2023 – 31.8.2023)

The following document is aiming to fulfil the task T9.1.1. that will result into D 9.1. a Full description of the core case studies and relationships with followers (1.10.2022 – 30.11.2022).

According to the Project Management Plan, this document will clearly outline the main climate risks, possible adaptation and mitigation strategies and define areas of simulation accordingly. At the same time, it will prepare a foundation for the task T.9.1.2. which includes the participation of the core and follower case studies to generate the future socio-economic scenarios.

The document is divided into 6 sections:

1. General
2. Participation and co-creation background
3. Socio-economic scenarios background
4. Models background
5. Strategies background
6. CSs expectations from DISTENDER

Note:

The T.9.1. working group has prepared this document with an intention it being a base for working process with CSs across all CS-related WPs. We pulled out the information available through the

documents prepared by the CSs (1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th, 3. Information discussed via working meetings (informal discussions), 4. Provided information from the wishlist of T2.1.).

This is an “on-going” working document, which final shape will be achieved in October 2022, using the co-creation process. This current document is a mixture of solid texts either copied or summarised from the sources mentioned above and the T9.1. core group suggestions or questions as well as requests for WPs and CSs on the subjects addressed. Usually, text marked in red is either questioning or suggesting on the subject addressed.

CSs: 1. Please have a look, check the filled-in information, and adjust if needed. 2. Please provide the missing information.

CS-related WPs: 1. WP representative, please have a look, especially the sections referring to your WP, and help to shape the directions as to what to ask, so each WP can gain as clearer picture as possible about the CS for a successful start. 2. Please, have a look also the section Expectations, and comment whether the expectations can be met in relation to what the WP you are conducting is intending to do/produce.

All: Please see also “informal section” For discussion, where we tried to pull out the most significant point of the CS based on the available information. Opinions on its relevancy are crucial. Please comment on.

Thanks for your cooperation. In case on any doubt or difficulty, please contact Vita (vitz@uirs.si) and Barbara (barbara@uirs.si).

Prepared by: Barbara Goličnik Marušić, Vita Žlender, Sergeja Praper, Ieva Girdvainiene, Egle Kalasnikovaite.

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Case study no.XX: name of the case study

SECTION I: General description

Instructions: Please give a brief information about the location of the case study and its main characteristics regarding the main economic activities, conditions needed for that, as well as conflicts among these activities in line with landscape characteristics and conditions.

Text provided by the CS (from sources such as 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Quick facts:

Area of interest (size):	
Population in area of interest:	
Topography of area of interest:	
Climate zone:	
Micro-climate specifics (if relevant/ if any):	
Other:	

SECTION II: Participation – co-creation background (as input for WP 3, 5, 6):

Instructions: Please indicate the stakeholders that are responsible and/or in any form active in the field of your case study. Describe their usual role or function in relation to the subject of your case study. If known, also indicate a concrete relationship between the CS and the stakeholder (for example: CS already cooperates with the “department A of stakeholder 1”. This “department A” provides data (provide a list of data)/regulations (provide a list of regulations)/recommendations (provide a list of recommendations)/is active as civil society...). Please provide this information here in a descriptive manner. Detailed information collected for T.2.1 can be used as a source for this text, and if agreed these final detailed tables can become an appendix of the final document.

Text provided by the CS (from sources such as 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Quick facts: The section Quick facts is a kind summary of the text provided.

	YES	PARTL Y	NO
<p>CS readiness (Please mark with X the most appropriate cell option for each question)</p> <p>Do you have experiences with stakeholders’ participation? Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)? Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users? Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies? Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder’s side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of?</p>			
	YES	PARTL Y	NO
<p>Stakeholder readiness*</p> <p>Do you know your stakeholder’s readiness for participation? Is it easy for it to take action on an issue? Do you know your stakeholder knowledgeability? <i>*Put the collective number of stakeholders in each cell (e.g. if you have experiences with 7 relevant stakeholders, indicate how many of them can be described with YES/PARTLY/NO: e.g. YES 4, PARTLY 3, NO 0)</i></p>			
	ACTIVE PARTICIPAN T	PREPARATIO N SUPORT	ORGANIZE/ IMPLEMENT
<p>Techniques used for participation (Please list the techniques of participation you are familiar with and indicate your usual role in it) e.g. workshop (name specific technique used if known)</p> <p>1. 2.</p>	X		
Any other important note/issue:			

SECTION III: Socio-economic scenarios – background:

Instructions: Please provide any observation known to you that may inform WP3 and indicate on the internal documents that can inform about current/future CS development: CS relevant spatial planning documentation, CS action plans, CS expert studies or any other documents that can well inform about the current state about socio-spatial-economic situation and/or can be a fruitful input for future local scenarios. Please provide a name of the document and up to 3 sentences summary including availability of georeferenced maps and data (e.g. shp files).

WP3 – please provide any additional directions or questions you would like to ask CSs to shape the scenarios preparation work.

Text provided by the CS (from sources such as 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Quick facts: The section Quick facts is a kind summary of the text provided.

Related documents available: Title of the document 1 Title of the document 2	Document type (insert such as action plan, expert study, spatial plan etc.)	Maps (scale)/data files:
Climate change impact:	Impact 1 Impact 2 ...	
Sectors directly affected:	Sector 1 Sector 2 ...	
Sectors indirectly affected/involved:		
Main conflicts recognised (up to 3):		
Preferred topic for scenarios:		
Any other important note/issue:		

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SECTION VI: Models-background:

Instructions: Please clearly provide climate change impacts identified for CS and vulnerability aspects caused by that.

WP5 – please provide questions you would like to ask CSs to shape the models. Based on Karl's comment at the online discussion, we suggest a simplified table, in section Quick facts, that grasped some of his ideas. Please add/adapt.

What are the main climate risks and their areas of simulation?

CS: Please provide, if there is any participatory action needed (workshop, interviews, focus groups...) with external stakeholders to identify that?

Potential climate impacts indicators?

CS: Any thoughts about that?

Text provided by the CS (from sources such as 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Quick facts:

Risk of	Data provider (stakeholder) for subject of "risk of"	Risk to	Data provider (stakeholder) for subject of "risk to"
Droughts			
Flooding			
Sea level rise			
Storms			
Water scarcity			

SECTION V: Strategies-background:

Instructions: Please build upon the information provide in section Socio-economic scenarios background and indicate regarding the (implemented) strategic mitigation and adaptation measures the strategies, visions, legislation, programs and projects implemented, including solutions proposed/implemented. Please also indicate the stakeholder/sector/group of stakeholders that are behind the measures. If known, please indicate the tensions between different stakeholders.

WP6 – please provide any additional directions or questions you would like to ask CSs to shape the strategies preparation work.

WP6 – T9.1. provide some comments in the table of current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation and adaptation, summarised upon PPT of the CS. Please have a look and if they do not lead towards useful inputs for WP, please delete or adjust.

Text provided by the CS (from sources such as 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Table 1: Current trends and action taken regarding climate mitigation and adaptation (The CSs information about current trends shall be put into that table (sources: 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Climate mitigation	Climate adaptation
1. aim: Actions taken: Level: Status of the action: Evaluation: Comment:	1. issue: Actions taken: Level: Status of the action: Evaluation: Comment:
2. aim: Actions taken: Level: Status of the action: Evaluation: Comment:	2. issue: Actions taken: Level: Status of the action: Evaluation: Comment:
...	...
n. aim: Actions taken: Level: Status of the action: Evaluation: Comment:	n. issue: Actions taken: Level: Status of the action: Evaluation: Comment:

Note: Level in this table addresses the hierarchy mode of the aim or issue, which means whether does it appear at either implementational or strategic. Status refers to the stage of the action is in (e.g., planned, executed, on-going).

Quick facts: The section Quick facts is a kind summary of the text provided.

Related documents available	Document type (EU Directive, National legislation, etc.)	Sector(s) released it:
Adaptation related: Title of the document 1A Title of the document 2A ...		
Mitigation related: Title of the document 1M Title of the document 2M ...		
Adaptation & Mitigation related: Title of the document 1AM Title of the document 2AM ...		
Sectors directly affected by the documents: Title of the document 1A Title of the document 2A ... Title of the document 1M Title of the document 2M ... Title of the document 1AM Title of the document 2AM ...		
Sectors indirectly affected/involved:		
Main conflicts recognised (up to 3):		
Main tried offs recognised (up to 3):		
Preferred topic for scenarios:		
Any other important note/issue:		

SECTION VI: Expectations:

Note: This section has very important implications for T2.2 Co-creation methods and activities, where according to the so called ‘co-design-test-transfer’ approach, that supports active stakeholder and societal engagement in the end-user needs analysis, is to be followed. One of the inputs for end-user needs analysis is its expectations.

At this point T9.1 core group would like to do a “reality check” of CS expectations regarding the focus of the project.

Text provided by the CS (from sources such as 1. Pdf provided for the purpose of Proposal Submission, 2. PPT prepared for presentation on June 14th + additional bilateral discussions)

Quick facts: The section Quick facts is a kind summary of the text provided.

Expectations:		Focuses/Priorities
Expectation 1	Short description (1-2 sentences)	
Expectation 2	Short description (1-2 sentences)	
...		
Expectation n	Short description (1-2 sentences)	

For discussion:

Possible point of departure for this CS

Based on the information provided in this document some points of departure for the CS will be generated.

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Annex II: Models

This annex shows the models overview addressing the current situation emerged from the workshops taking place on-line on 12.10.2022 and 19.10.2022 organised by WP9, and short description of some models provided by PPs being experts for them.

Models overview

SECTOR	Sub-sector	Modelling tool	Outputs	Modeller
HEALTH	Air quality and emissions	URBAIR	Changes in pollutant concentrations for different future time frames	UAVR
	Urban heat	SUEWS (It calculates urban land surface model that simulates radiation, energy and water balances using standard meteorological variables and surface cover information)	Air and surface temperature at a low computational cost	NKUA
		ENVI-met (It is about direct and detailed assessment of the efficacy of mitigation solutions, such as green infrastructure (street trees, green roofs and facades, etc.) and the use of reflective materials or coatings at a high computational cost)		NKUA
Health impacts	T 5.1 (air pollutant concentrations) + T 5.2 (extreme temperature events) + WP9 (mortality rate) + WP9 (population by age groups) = health indicator	Computation of health indicators such as the excess of mortality during heat waves or premature deaths due to air pollution Economic evaluation of the health impacts.	UAVR	
ENERGY				RdA
AFOLU	Agriculture Forestry Other land use	YieldSAFE (It predicts plant growth, production, etc.)	Yearly yields for the different agricultural and forestry systems	UPM
WATER	Flooding Drought	SWAT (It calculates relevant water fluxes at the land surface, in the soil, groundwater and river)	Management options related to soil, land use, ponds/reservoirs	UoC
		Economic assessment (It evaluates the value of water sector climate change impacts)		UB

Annex III: Short descriptions of the models regarding WP5

T 5.1 Air quality and emissions (UAVR).

Human activities release greenhouse gases and air pollutants into the atmosphere that may affect the quality of the air we breathe, and consequently our health. The air quality model to be used in DISTENDER simulates, through mathematical formulations, the dispersion of air pollutants in the atmosphere. It uses as inputs the air pollutants emitted by the different activities in the region of study and considers the meteorological conditions for each scenario provided by WP4. The outputs consist of maps of air quality levels for the health concerned pollutants (particulate matter, ozone and nitrogen dioxide).

T 5.2 Urban heat island (UAVR).

There are two types of models presented:

Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS)

Urban energy balance models can simulate surface-air exchanges in response to land cover, surface geometry, and meteorological conditions. The Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS) is a widely used urban heat model that simulates radiation, energy, and water balances using standard meteorological variables (e.g., air temperature, wind, and relative humidity) and surface cover information. The model has been applied and tested in various cities under a range of different climates worldwide; model outputs include air and surface temperature. A main advantage of SUEWS is that it enables long-term urban climate simulations for the entire city with a relatively low computational cost.

SUEWS is designed for neighbourhood-scale simulations; simulations are typically performed **with a 500 m horizontal resolution**. It describes the underlying urban surface in terms of basic surface types: roads, buildings, trees, low vegetation, bare soil, and water; each grid cell comprises fractions of these surface types. A wide number of parameters can be prescribed for these surfaces; e.g., the height of buildings, the reflectance of urban materials or the vegetation phenology. This allows the evaluation of the impact of different urban development pathways on neighbourhood climate and thus support the objective of the DISTENDER project to establish a methodology for the selection of the optimal mitigation and adaptation strategies, taking into account the trade-offs between them.

Being a “simple” model, SUEWS comes with some limitations; for instance, it does not explicitly account for the advection between grid cells (this climatic information should be incorporated in the forcing data), and the 3-D representation of the urban structure in the model is rather simplified.

ENVI-met

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) enable sophisticated microclimate (numerical) simulations of the flow inside urban canyons. ENVI-met is the most widely adapted microscale model and allows for a very precise representation of the urban environment with a horizontal and vertical resolution of few meters. It explicitly couples the exchanges of momentum (airflow), energy and mass; in this way, the properties of the surface and atmosphere evolve together.

ENVI-met offers a vast range of different surface and wall materials to digitize urban areas. Since different objects, materials, and surface types have their own physical parameters, such as albedo, emissivity and heat transfer coefficient, the possibility to accurately replicate

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the variety of the urban environment increases the accuracy of the model results. Moreover, in recent versions of the model, a 3D vegetation module has been added that allows complex vegetation geometries and improved modelling of the microclimate effects of trees. ENVI-met allows for a detailed and direct assessment of the efficacy of adaptation solutions to urban heat (thermal environment at the urban scale, urban heat island and heat waves) such as green infrastructure (street trees, green roofs and facades, parks, etc.) and the use of reflective materials or coatings. To this end, it supports planners and policymakers in terms of adaptation and resilience plans.

Due to its high complexity, ENVI-met needs a vast amount of computer resources. Thereby, ENVI-met simulations will be conducted for specific episodes and for smaller domains (with an extent approximately of 300 m × 300 m). Core Case Studies may refer to a list of few neighbourhoods that are considered of high priority; for instance, these may correspond to the most thermally vulnerable spots of the city or to typical residential areas.

T 5.3 Health impact (UAVR).

The health impact model calculates the impacts of extreme weather events (heat waves) and of air pollution on human health. It needs as inputs meteorological indicators of heat waves (from WP4 and WP5.2) and air quality indicators (from WP5.1) to estimate health indicators like the number of premature deaths and number of Years of Life Lost (YOLL) due to high levels of air pollution. In relation to heat waves, excess mortality will be considered. These health indicators are based on functions that relate the exposure to a risk of health effect.

The economic assessment of health impacts (WP7, T7.2) considers the cost of each health loss through the Value of Statistical Life (estimated by country). The health indicators from WP5.3 are translated into a monetary value. Then, a balance can be made, by comparing the total cost of implementation of a given scenario and the expected benefits (external cost) considering all impacts evaluated in WP5. This cost-benefit analysis is very useful from a decision-making point of view, it informs on how much one can pay and save when implementing a given scenario.

T 5.5 Water (UoC).

There are two types of models presented:

The hydrological impact model SWAT

In the sector water, we use a widely used and scientifically accepted model named SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool). SWAT works on catchments (also called watersheds). These are areas from which runoff resulting from rainfall is collected and drained through a common point (usually in a stream or river). It simulates the quantity and quality of surface and ground water and predicts the environmental impact of land use, land management practices, and climate change. SWAT is used in assessing water fluxes and storages, soil erosion prevention and control, non-point source pollution control and regional management in watersheds. The model is physically based thus the relative impact of alternative input data (e.g., changes in management practices, climate, vegetation, etc.) on water fluxes and water quality can be quantified. SWAT is a continuous time model that enables users to study long-term impacts. It is not designed to simulate detailed, single-event flood routing. SWAT simulates the relevant water fluxes of runoff (surface, soil, groundwater), infiltration, evapo(transpiration) and storages (interception, soil water, groundwater, reservoirs) with a

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daily time step. It has a large range of management options. Validation is typically done by comparison to measured runoff. The spatial discretization is sub-catchments. Within these sub-catchments, the land area is divided into combinations of land use, soil texture and slope are discrete classes (without an explicit spatial location) describing the hydrological response to an input. Water balance modelling is the key concept of SWAT.

The method of economic assessment: benefit transfer

For assessing the economic value of CC impacts on the water sector, UB will apply the 'benefit transfer' (BT) approach. This involves taking the results from one or more primary economic studies with estimated values for similar impacts, and modifying and transferring them to the project being evaluated. BT can provide useful information for decision-making and, frequently, it is the only way of providing such information. So, the idea is to attribute an economic value to CC impacts on this sector (water scarcity, floods and drought). This economic value will represent the cost of no action in Round 1 in different socio-economic scenarios. It will be compared with the cost of action (city of tomorrow according to case studies' vision) in Round 2. In Round 3, the economic value of CC impacts will be compared with the cost of policy and measures implemented to reduce them, in a kind of CBA (Cost-Benefits analysis)

Methodology:

- An economic/monetary value will be associated with each impact (and co-benefits), according to a Total Economic Value approach in order to consider all impacts generated in an integrated way
- The economic/monetary value will be defined using the benefit transfer technique. Through a literature review, economic/monetary value will be identified for each category of impacts/benefits by determining a unit of measurement.
- Variables affecting the variability of economic values identified will be considered (es. territorial context, degree of water scarcity at the local level, quality of water resources)
- For hydrogeological and floods risks, the analyses will consider hazards, exposure and assets vulnerability at the local level
- Where necessary, the benefit transfer can be integrated with the willingness to pay and surveys to be carried out in collaboration with other partners based on operational feasibility.

Annex IV: Supplementary material, provided by the case study partners

IV.1 Supplementary material of the CS 03 Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) (EURAF)

Numerous scientific studies have focused on the contents which may be relevant for the development of the socio-economic scenarios. Some of them are listed below.

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Dehesas as high nature value farming systems: a social-ecological synthesis of drivers, pressures, state, impacts, and responses [1]. This is a synthesis of a large body of international literature focusing on the links between land use and management practices, biodiversity, and policy, from a “high nature value farming systems” perspective. The review comprises 128 empirical studies carried out in Spain and Portugal. Conservation trends were assessed according to categories adapted from the DPSIR (Drivers - Pressures - State - Impacts - Responses) framework. Socio-cultural factors, economic dynamics, and agricultural policies were found to be key drivers of change, resulting in intensification of livestock production and land use simplification, among other effects. Insufficient tree regeneration and a broad range of other factors were identified as pressures that have often negative impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services, moving the system away from its archetypical ecological state. The need to move from single-topic to landscape-level approaches with a broader integration of different disciplines and perspectives is highlighted.

Stakeholder perspectives of wood-pasture ecosystem services [2]. The authors performed 34 face-to-face semi-structured interviews to describe stakeholders’ appreciation of ecosystem services (ES) from dehesa landscapes in northern Extremadura, Spain. A total of 45 ES were mentioned and compared among different sectors and levels of governance. At the local level, people appreciated especially provisioning and cultural services. In contrast, regional level respondents showed more appreciation for regulating and supporting services, which included biodiversity conservation and climate regulation. Private and public sector respondents appreciated provisioning services more, whereas the civil sector mentioned supporting and regulating services more (e.g., water regulation was only mentioned by civil and public sector respondents, while genetic resource preservation was only expressed by the private sector). All sectors noted cultural services as key ES.

Mapping sensitivity to land degradation in Extremadura. SW Spain [3]. The authors developed a model to identify environmental sensitive areas (ESA) that resulted in two maps expressing the regional distribution of four and eight classes of sensitivity to degradation. The model included elements and parameters related to land degradation and obtained from databases and thematic cartography at different scales, and some others produced ex nova for the study. Those elements consisted of some of the main environmental and socioeconomic issues related with the sensitivity to land degradation at a regional scale: soil, climate, vegetation and management issues.

The Private Economy of Dehesas and Ranches: Case Studies [4]. The authors measured and analyzed total private income and profitability for five case study privately-owned dehesas and oak woodland ranches by using The Agroforestry Accounting System at the farm scale. Results were estimated for individual forestry, game, livestock, crop, and service activities, and for activities aggregated as a whole. The case study application incorporates landowner consumption of private amenities as part of the total income from the dehesa or ranch, showing that these private amenities are the most important contributor to total income, while the contribution from livestock production is low or even negative.

The Dehesas of Extremadura, Spain: A Potential for Socio-economic Development Based on Agritourism Activities [5]. In this study spatial statistics, in particular the grouping analysis, was used to consider the location of the rural accommodation and its

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proximity to areas of dehesas and protected natural spaces, livestock paths and trashumance corridors and natural swimming pools. The results lead to the creation of 5 homogeneous groups of which 3 correspond to accommodation establishments capable of setting up agritourism and agrietourism initiatives; this affects 45% of the establishments. The need for implementing tourist policies to encourage tourism specifically intended to exploit the potential of the dehesa as a complement to the current availability of rural accommodation was identified.

Towards the Dehesa Total Income Accounting: Theory and Operative Monfragüe Study Cases [6]. This paper shows a complete accounting system that can incorporate any economic benefit and cost that could accrue from active and passive uses of forestland, whether or not the economic effects are the result of on-site and off-site land uses. An application to the Spanish dehesas at Monfragüe area gives a tentative total income measurement under this new accounting proposal.

Environmental report Extremadura 2019 [7].

References:

- [1] <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12647-260323>
- [2] <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.10.022>
- [3] <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.884>
- [4] https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-94-007-6707-2_13
- [5] <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10080620>
- [6] <https://doi.org/10.5424/733>
- [7] <http://extremambiente.juntaex.es/files/INFORME%20AMBIENTAL%202019.pdf>

IV.2 Supplementary material of the CS 05 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

Additional information supporting information on physical and human geography and related topics:

population

TERRITORIAL DIMENSIONS

CMT0 = 2.219.206 inh.

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Figure 12 Territory and population

territorial characteristics

The region includes many areas of the Natura 2000; in particular, there are one national park (Gran Paradiso National Park), 21 parks / reserves with regional management and eight parks / reserves managed by CMTo (approximately 7,250 total hectares; see Figure 12).

Figure 13 Graphical representation on some territorial characteristics

CMTo is rich in cultural and landscape assets and members of the UNESCO World Heritage List, including: Residences of the House of Savoy (mainly located in Turin and in the municipalities of the first and second belt), Ivrea Industrial City of the 20th century, the Sacro Monte di Belmonte. In addition, there have been 2 UNESCO MAB sites in the territory, Monviso Biosphere Area (2014), and Protected Areas of the Po river and the Turin Hill (2016).

climate

CMT0 is part of the Piedmont Region, where the generalized acceleration trend of climate warming is confirmed: here the average temperature has recorded in the last 60 years (1958-2018) an increase in maximum temperature (Tmax) with a rate of 0.38 ° C / 10 years, with a rate (0.58 ° C / 10 years) almost doubled in the last 30 years (1981-2018). The increases concern both maximum temperatures (approximately +2.1°C) and minimum temperatures (Tmin) (approximately +1.5°C), with more acute levels of increase in mountain areas (TMax +2.5°C, TMin +1.8°C). TMax has increased especially in winter (and in spring in the last thirty years), while TMin follows a positive trend in all seasons, more relevant for spring in the last thirty years. The season that has seen a significant increase in the last thirty years is always spring. The extreme values of T max and T min also increased, particularly in the winter season. Trends in annual cumulative rainfall show no significant changes. On the other hand, inter-annual variability is very high. The average values have slightly decreased in the last 30 years compared to the entire historical series, especially in the plains (about -4%). Precipitation is increasing in the fall and decreasing in the spring. Considering the series available since 1958, there is a generalized decrease in winter precipitation (-13-14%) and a slight increase in spring precipitation in the mountains; in the plains there is a slight decrease in summer and autumn, while the wettest season tends to be, in the latter period, spring, unlike what can be seen from the historical series, where autumn dominates. The maximum cumulative daily rainfall increases with a trend of about 1.28 mm / year for the plains and 1.38 mm / year for the mountains. The main contribution is made by autumn, followed by spring. The duration of dry periods also increases (no. of consecutive days without rain), particularly at lower altitudes, with great inter-annual variability (very rainy years in a drier climate or where precipitation is more concentrated). While in the previous century drought predominantly characterized the plains, the driest years in the new millennium also involve the mountainous areas. The standardized anomaly index (SAI) shows a decrease in the quantities of fresh snow in the last 20 years compared to the previous twenty years, with a fair inter-annual variability, even if the positive extremes are rarer and more contained. The decrease is more relevant for stations below 1500 meters. The ground thickness curves show a widespread reduction in the last 30 years compared to the previous thirty years. Compared to staying on the ground, there are no obvious trends of increase or decrease, but rather a greater variability especially at the beginning of the season.

Strategy for CONTRASTING CONSUMPTION AND SOIL WATERPROOFING – further reading:

In the territory of the Metropolitan City of Turin, land consumption is progressing with little justifiable regularity, especially when compared to a substantially stable demographic curve.

The increase in land consumption is not evenly distributed throughout the metropolitan area. It is particularly evident how, in spite of past urban development, the growth of the homogeneous Zones of the metropolitan area is unceasing (which in the AMT South and the Chivassese area exceeds abundantly 2% between 2012 and 2020), while it is clearly decreasing in the direction of the morphologically less "welcoming" areas from the point of view of urban expansion.

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With these projections, by 2050 they could end up having consumed 14 percent of available land, about two-thirds more to the 8.6 percent consumed at present, without, moreover, the rising trend finding any response in the demographic picture. In fact, from 2012 to 2020, CMTo's population has decreased by more than 11,700 (resulting in a per capita land consumption, as of 2020, of 263 m²/inhabitant).

Figure 14 Land consumption and population

Table 38: Land consumption and resident population trends - 2012-2020 (elab. UdP PTGM/CSI)

SALDO DELLA POPOLAZIONE 2012-20	-41.724
Soil consumed 2012-20 (ha)	958
Soil consumed 2012-20 (%)	1,67
Velocity (m ² /giorno)	3.282
Density (m ² /ha/anno)	1,36
TMAI (average annual rate of increase)	0,18
Per capita consumption 2020 (m ² /ab)	263,2

Table 39. Land consumption and resident population 2012-2020 (Elab. UdP PTGM/CSI on ISTAT and ISPRA data)

HOMOGENEOUS ZONE	POPULATION [2019]	SUP. [SKM]	CONSUMATED [HA 2012]	CONSUMATED [HA 2020]	CONSUMATED [% 2020]	BOOKED (BY LOCAL PLAN) [%]
1 - Torino	848.196	130	8.408,2	8.462,4	65,1	-
2 - AMT Ovest	234.386	203	4.957,8	4.983,8	24,5	1,0
3 - AMT Sud	265.408	386	7.354,1	7.501,0	19,4	1,6
4 - AMT Nord	135.818	175	4.050,4	4.332,7	24,7	2,8
5 - Pinerolese	130.487	1.302	6.081,7	6.111,7	4,7	0,4
6 - Valli di Susa e Sangone	102.563	1.247	4.572,7	4.553,0	3,7	0,3
7 - Ciriacese, Valli di Lanzo	100.097	973	4.653,9	4.647,7	4,8	0,4
8 - Canavese occidentale	81.162	975	4.037,0	4.017,6	4,1	0,4
9 - Eporediese	86.903	551	3.960,8	3.976,4	7,2	0,8
10 - Chivassese	98.595	423	4.393,7	4.481,3	10,6	0,9
11 - Chierese - Carmagnolese	129.381	462	5.123,0	5.171,2	11,2	0,6

Figure 15 Soil consumed by Homogeneous Zone & Soil consumed by Homogeneous Zone

Key facts:

- Land consumption causes habitat fragmentation and contributes to the loss of biodiversity necessary to maintain the homeostatic balance of ecosystems on which the ability to provide ecosystem services depends;
- Soil sealing reduces the absorption capacity of rainwater causing extensive damage especially during so-called water bombs;
- Soil consumption causes the loss of areas useful to agriculture for food supply;
- Land consumption leads to an increase in the construction of transport infrastructure, with particular reference to roads whose dark surface reduces the absorption capacity of solar energy. This contributes, especially in cities, to rising temperatures;
- The decrease in forested areas for building purposes, especially in hilly areas, leads to the hydrogeological instability of slopes;

The Territorial Spatial Plan (PTGM) introduces a land zoning into dense, free, transitional zones by placing percentage limits on buildability aimed to control land consumption. It also identifies interlocking areas eligible for interventions that could be useful to become urban green or public spaces for adaptation to climate change.

Strategy to IMPROVE ECOLOGICAL FUNCTIONALITY & INCREASE FOREST AREAS

Fragmentation of ecosystems, disfigurement of the landscape, lower carbon sequestration capacity, and hydrogeological disruption are just some of the impacts caused by the loss of biodiversity that collectively led to lower quality and quantity of ecosystem services provided free of charge to humans. Improving the ecological functionality of the land is one of the goals of the metropolitan ecological network and the green and blue infrastructure project that is a multifunctional network consisting of strategically planned natural and semi-natural areas.

This includes the Urban and Suburban Forestation Plan defined by the Italian Ecological Transitional Ministry, which provides for the planting of 6.6 million trees throughout the country. The objectives of the Forestation Plan (absorb and remove air pollutants, protect and recover man-made landscapes by enhancing inland areas in direct ecological relationship with urbanized areas, enhance the system of protected areas, curb land consumption, combat heat islands) are in line with the objectives of the Green Infrastructure project of the PTGM.

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Another tool provided by the PTGM for the improvement of the ecological functionality of the territory is the CIRCA catalogue, which provides for the census of areas suitable for the location of interventions for the conservation and/or improvement of the ecological functionality of the territory, to protect its biodiversity, implement the Green infrastructure. The interventions are aimed at improving the environmental matrices, increasing the naturalness and ecological functionality of the territory, preserving areas of naturalistic value not yet protected, and restoring degraded habitats. A 2014 study conducted by the CMT0 with support from ENEA - National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, identified different classes of ecological functionality of the land (high, moderate, residual, and none) highlighting areas of higher fragmentation and ecological fragility.

Figura 6. Carta della funzionalità ecologica del territorio (stralcio Chierese)

Figure 16 Ecological functionality of land (ecological fragmentation and fragility)

Figure 17 Municipalities that provided areas suitable to requalification actions (CIRCA) + Areas identified for reforestation plan

Additional information on ecological networks and environmental issues:
Metropolitan Ecological Network (included into Metropolitan Spatial Plan)

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Europe recognizes the role of biodiversity and the 2000 Network (ecological network at CMT0 level) in reducing concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere and in regulating the climate. The Metropolitan Ecological Network project is composed of a series of natural and semi-natural elements, linear and areal (parks, rivers...) of particular naturalistic interest, to provide a wide range of Ecosystem Services and Benefits to the population. The realization of the ecological network project, at the different metropolitan and local / municipal scales, is one of the strategies that constitute a possible evolutionary scenario to be considered in DISTENDER. GIS data are available on the spatial elements that make up the network (parks, rivers, wetlands) and new proposals for areas of the network

CIRCA - Catalogue of the Environmental Redevelopment and Compensation Interventions

A territory characterized by a better environmental quality, more respectful of natural balances, is a guarantee of greater well-being for citizens and allows them to better respond to current climatic emergencies. The CIRCA Catalogue is part of the CMT0 environmental strategy aimed at containing the processes of consumption of the soil and primary natural resources to favour the adaptation and mitigation of climate change, and to promote biodiversity through the environmental redevelopment of the territory. The Catalogue lists the areas in which it is necessary and possible to implement conservation and / or improvement of ecological functionality, protect biodiversity, implement the network of green infrastructures and in general increase their capacity to respond to change. climatic, preserve the naturalistic value of unprotected areas, restore deteriorated habitats and degraded areas. The Catalogue is a tool to support local administrations and allows you to identify and disseminate knowledge of the areas of interest, to identify the best redevelopment and protection actions and the most suitable financing opportunities to satisfy them. The implementation of the actions provided in the Catalogue (constantly updated) is one of the scenarios that CMT0 proposes to evaluate in DISTENDER.

GIS data (areal / point) of the areas are available. A more detailed description of some of them is also available (photos, characteristics of the areas, intervention hypotheses)

Additional information on energy sector:

Turin northeast project

The Torino Nord Est project is aimed at extending the district heating service to a catchment area which in the first phase will be equal to approximately 6.3 million m³, corresponding to approximately 1,000 buildings laying approximately 70 km of network and in the second phase it will reach 9.0 million m³, corresponding to approximately 1,400 buildings, laying approximately 90 km of network in the north-eastern area of the City of Turin. The project also includes the construction of the backbone connecting the Turin district heating network to the ENGIE Produzione thermoelectric plant in Leini, which will be the main producer of the thermal energy required by the new users.

With regard to satisfying the thermal demand of the users served by the North East Turin Project, the construction of the connection between the district heating network and the Leini thermoelectric plant will make it possible to achieve greater energy efficiency of the system through the use of heat deriving from the cogeneration of a plant already in service and will avoid having to build a new plant for heat generation or to integrate existing plants with new

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co-generators or new integration and reserve boilers or even to upgrade them. In the proposed design solution, the heat required for the extension of the district heating service will in fact be provided in cogeneration, both by the ENGIE Produzione thermoelectric plant in Leini through the aforementioned connection, and by the other IREN plants already in service today. At the Basse di Stura site, as part of the project, the installation of a heat accumulation system with related pumping systems is also planned.

At the end of the realization of the North East Turin Project and of the projects under development in the areas already served and in the immediate vicinity of the same, a single metropolitan district heating system of over 90 million m³ will be established, powered almost exclusively by the main thermoelectric cogeneration plants present in the metropolitan area of Turin, able to allow a high reliability of service supply for customers and, also thanks to the heat accumulation systems distributed throughout the territory, a low use of the existing integration and reserve boilers, thus pursuing the objective of decarbonisation of production processes.

With reference to the various parts that make up the North East Turin Project, the extension of the district heating network within the Municipality of Turin is the responsibility of the company IREN Energia SpA, while the construction of the connection between the district heating network and the Leini plant. The images shown below show the expansion of the TLR planned in the next few years (Figure 18) and that planned with the implementation of the TORINO NORD EST project (Figure 19).

Area metropolitana – Fotografia nel 2030 – Planimetria e volumetrie

Figure 18 Expansion of the TLR planned

Area metropolitana – Fotografia nel 2030 con Torino Nord Est

Figure 19 Expansion planned with the implementation of the TORINO NORD EST project

Environmental and energy performance improvement of the Leini (To) plant

The project consists of carrying out some interventions on individual components of the plant aimed at optimizing its environmental and energy performance with the following interventions:

- 1) Installation of a new gas turbine to replace the existing one, of the same class (F), but with better energy and environmental performance
- 2) Installation of a new electric generator associated with the TG
- 3) Installation of a catalytic DeNOx in the GVR, to reduce NOx emissions
- 4) Installation of a CO Oxidizer in the GVR, to reduce CO emissions
- 5) Installation of a new electric auxiliary boiler (e-boiler), which it will replace the existing one, powered by natural gas (which will remain in cold reserve anyway)
- 6) Installation of three fluid ring pumps to be used in place of the ejectors, to create a vacuum in the condenser during start-up and operation of the cycle combined
- 7) Retrofit of the condenser, with replacement of the gearmotor groups and increase performance in all conditions, especially in the case of high outside temperatures
- 8) construction of a thermal storage system to support future developments in district heating and / or the existing one, which will consist of a group of 10 hot water storage silos and related controls.

The objectives of the interventions listed above are:

- 1) the drastic reduction of the current NOx (-66.7%) and CO (-50%) emissions of the plant in all phases of operation, despite an increase in CCGT power of approximately 23 MWe
- 2) the total elimination of NOx, CO, and CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere by the aux boiler during the start-up phases of the plant
- 3) the drastic reduction (-90.7%) of the water consumption by the auxiliary boiler in the start-up phases of the plant

Expectations:

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

and

DISTENDER

The district heating system was developed with the aim of a more efficient use of energy. The system is currently almost completely dependent on the use of methane. It would be interesting to evaluate how the heat demand of buildings will change in the future, both in relation to climate change and to the thermal efficiency interventions that are underway. It would also be useful to understand how this system can abandon the use of methane in favour of a greater use of energy from renewable sources.

Additional insights on district heating system

The network is operated at 120–95 °C supply and 80–45 °C return temperatures, depending on the month of the year. Pumping stations are installed at each thermal plant, and different booster pumping groups are located along the network to ensure acceptable pressure levels in all the network branches. The main characteristics of the DH system components are listed in Table 64.

Table 64: Main parameters of Turin district heating system.

Production Plant	Cogenerative Power Plant		Integration Boiler	Storage
	MWe	MWt		
Torino Nord	400	220	340	5000
Moncalieri	800	420	141	
BIT			255	2500
Politecnico			255	2500
Martinetto				5000
Incineration plant	80	100		
Grugliasco			42	
Rivoli			62	

The extension of the district heating network operating in the Turin metropolitan area will reach the volumetry of 91,500,000 m³ in 2030 (74,500,000 m³ in 2020) through a more extensive use of existing infrastructures and the construction of the following projects:

- Turin northeast project, aimed at extending the district heating service in this area of the city;
- environmental and energy performance improvement of the Leinì (To) plant, which will power most of the new volumes installed. MCTo verifies that the implementation of the projects pursues the highest environmental standards, guarantees compliance with the timing of the procedures and verifies that the projects are carried out in compliance with the permit's conditions.

